

BLUEMISSION AA

Building a coordination hub to support the mission implementation in the Atlantic and Arctic Basin

D1.2 Report on Atlantic and Arctic Policy and Governance Frameworks

Marine protection and
restoration

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List of key acronyms

Abbreviation	Full name
ABNJ	Area(s) beyond national jurisdiction
BlueMissionAA	BlueMission Atlantic & Arctic
CBD	1992 Convention on Biological Diversity
EU	European Union
IMO	International Maritime Organization
ISA	International Seabed Authority
ITLOS	International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
LOSC	1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
MPAs	Marine Protected Areas
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Marine Spatial Planning
NEAFC	North-East Atlantic Fisheries Commission
OECSs	Other effective area-based conservation measures
OSPAR Convention	1992 Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organisation

List of key terminology

Term	Definition
Marine protected areas (MPAs)	<p>The CBD recognises that MPA governance is integral to ensuring an enduring future. The IUCN has defined marine protected areas as:</p> <p><i>"Any area of intertidal or subtidal terrain, together with its overlying water and associated flora, fauna, historical and cultural features, which has been reserved by law or other effective means to protect part or all of the enclosed environment."</i> IUCN 17th Session in San Jose, Costa Rica, 1-10 February 1988</p>
Strict Protection	<p>Internationally, the CBD itself does not contain a specific target or criteria for 'strict protection' of marine protected areas. However, guidance and best practices endorsed by the CBD Conference of the Parties (COP) encourage the establishment of strictly protected MPAs as part of representative MPA networks. The EU Biodiversity Strategy specifically includes targets for strict protection, defined by the EU as:</p> <p><i>"Strictly protected areas are fully, and legally protected areas designated to conserve and/or restore the integrity of biodiversity-rich natural areas with their underlying ecological structure and supporting natural environmental processes. Natural processes are therefore left essentially undisturbed from human pressures and threats to the area's overall ecological structure and functioning, independently of whether those pressures and threats are located inside or outside the strictly protected area."</i>(Dinerstein et al., 2019)</p> <p>The EU definition is largely aligned with the IUCN 'Guidelines for Applying Protected Area Management Categories', and it is generally associated with the definitions of categories Ia, strict nature reserve, Ib, wilderness area, and II, national park (where strict protection can apply as part of the zoning). The EU definition focuses on leaving natural processes undisturbed and excluding extractive activities while allowing some non-extractive activities on a case-by-case basis if compatible with conservation objectives (Dinerstein et al., 2019).</p>
Other effective area-based conservation measures (OECMs)	<p>The CBD's official definition from 2018 defines OECMs as:</p> <p><i>"A geographically defined area other than a Protected Area, which is governed and managed in ways that achieve positive and sustained long-term outcomes for the in-situ conservation of biodiversity, with associated ecosystem functions and services and where applicable, cultural, spiritual, socio-economic, and other locally relevant values."</i> (CBD Decision 14/8)</p> <p>Unlike MPAs, which are primarily 'designated' for conservation purposes, OECMs are rather being 'recognised.' This underscores the broader approach to conservation, acknowledging existing management interventions for their positive contribution (IUCN-WCPA Task Force on OECMs, 2019). These areas might prioritise conservation as a secondary goal or long-term conservation benefits may naturally arise from their management activities. OECMs are typically implemented through sectoral legislation (e.g., fisheries, flood prevention, etc.) and contribute to maintaining ecosystems, supporting threatened species, securing ecosystem services, enhancing resilience, and connecting fragmented landscapes (IUCN-WCPA Task Force on OECMs, 2019). The EU considers OECMs eligible toward the Biodiversity Strategy targets if minimum criteria for national protection sites apply</p>

	(long-term, specified conservation objectives and measures; management effectiveness). Further clarification on the recognition of OECMs in international and EU policy contexts is required (Dinerstein et al., 2019).
Restoration	This report adopts the Society of Ecological Restoration's (2002) definition of <i>"the process of assisting the recovery of an ecosystem that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed."</i>
Governance	<p>Governance is not government. (Pjs et al., 2019) defines governance as: <i>"a broader set of elements that includes all the groundwork through to the negotiations and discussions that underpin management and influence human behaviour. It is a continuous process that involves negotiations among people, norms of behaviour, and economic influences."</i></p> <p>As stated by the European Environment Agency, <i>"International Ocean governance is about managing and using the world's oceans and their resources in ways that keep them healthy, productive, safe, secure and resilient."</i> (European Environment Agency, 2022) .</p> <p>Visual depictions of governance themes identify disparities in the terminology used. Notably, there are differences in governance, but despite this, the literature is consistent in providing governance principles and themes.</p>
Management	<p>Management can be defined as: <i>"part of governance and is a formal representation of official decisions that can be readily seen, such as management plans, management groups and regulations."</i> (Pjs et al., 2019)</p> <p>This distinction highlights the difference between management and governance. While management focuses on achieving specific objectives, governance addresses the strategic aspect of decision-making, determining who sets the objectives and how to pursue them (Borini-Feyerabend & Hill, 2015).</p>
Shared governance	<p>The IUCN and CBD recognise four main types of governance: centralised governance, shared governance, or co-management, locally led governance, and private governance. These categories can be partially overlapping. Whereas centralised governments traditionally constituted the main authority to designate and manage MPAs, an increasing shift towards shared governance models can be observed (IUCN-WCPA Task Force on OECMs, 2019).</p> <p><i>"Shared governance (used inter-changeably with co-management) refers to a cooperative approach where governmental organizations, local communities, indigenous peoples and stakeholders work together to manage and conserve MPAs. Co-management is therefore seen as an important compromise between strict top-down as well as locally led bottom-up approaches and is regarded as an important approach to ensure accountability and legitimacy of the protection process"</i> (Petursson & Kristofersson, 2021). Shared governance arrangements can take many forms, with varying degrees of power-sharing and decision-making authority between government and stakeholders.</p>

Executive Summary

Marine ecosystems, vital for global biodiversity and ecological balance, are under increasing pressure from human activities and climate change. The urgency of the situation is reflected in the ambitious targets set by the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) for marine protection, with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework aiming to conserve 30% of global marine areas by 2030. The European Union (EU) is actively supporting these goals through its Biodiversity Strategy 2030, including an additional target to achieve strict protection for a third of the protected areas. The EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters' launched by the EU Commission is a testament to the importance and relevance of these objectives, targeting the protection and restoration of marine ecosystems by 2030 through regional 'Lighthouses' focusing on specific objectives for each lighthouse.

BlueMissionAA is the coordination and support action in the Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse focusing on protection and restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems for increased climate resilience in the Atlantic and Arctic basin providing a central coordination hub for implementing the EU Mission's objectives in the Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse. Specifically, it aims to support the Mission's targets of protecting 30% of sea areas in these regions by 2030, with one-third of the areas under strict protection, as well as contribution to upcoming nature restoration targets.

This report provides an overview of the current marine governance landscape as well as the framework and use of area-based management measures across the lighthouses. A comprehensive governance baseline is presented, mapping out the policy and governance frameworks relevant to the Mission's objectives. Governance parameters identified and assessed through this report have been categorised into the strategic direction, existing legal frameworks, and implementation mechanisms.

A cross-comparison between the regions and States is provided in chapter 4, summarising key observations. This highlights the heterogeneity in governance approaches across the Atlantic and Arctic, as well as across individual States, which some argue affects the delivery of Mission Objectives. 17 key observations have been made, 6 associated with strategic direction, 5 with the existing legal frameworks and the remainder associated with implementation of the governance frameworks.

These key observations have been informed by an examination of BlueMissionAA governance landscape at multiple levels: section 5 focuses on the regional perspective, while sections 6 and 7 provide an assessment of individual States of the Atlantic and Arctic basins, respectively. This multi-tiered approach provides a thorough understanding of the governance structures in place across the lighthouse, showcasing to what extent existing frameworks support the implementation of the Mission.

The report suggests reflection points to enhance commonalities and address differences in governance frameworks to support the implementation of international and BlueMissionAA objectives. These include shifting strategic thinking from quantitative targets towards increased focus on impacts and ecosystem-based approaches, incorporating marine protection into existing strategies, strengthening the legal framework and alignment of conservation frameworks with other sectoral activities, and emphasising the role of participatory processes. These findings, along with case studies on ecological restoration, will inform discussions with the Expert Panel (established under Task 1.4) to develop proposals for the Mission's implementation phase.

Given this, this report represents a vital resource for providing an overview and initialising the development of conceptual thinking to advance governance associated with area-based management measures (MPAs and OECMs) and restoration within the Atlantic and Arctic.

Report structure

The full report provides a mapping exercise of governance underpinning ecosystem restoration and protection within the Atlantic and Arctic. This report constitutes the following six parts:

Part 1: Purpose statement

This section provides the purpose statement and objectives of this report.

Part 2: Introduction

The introductory section outlines the aim and scope of the report, the contextual background for the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters', and the delineation of the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse Area.

Part 3: Methodology

The methodology section describes the approach and guiding questions used to determine the current governance baseline for marine protection and restoration.

Part 4: Key observations across Atlantic and Arctic governance frameworks

This section is a cross-comparison of sections 5 - 7, identifying key observations within the scope of BlueMissionAA (describing commonalities, synergies, and differences) associated between States and the regional levels. These are structured in terms of the following governance principles: strategic direction, legal framework, and the implementation.

Part 5: Regional governance baseline within the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse

This section provides an overview of regional governance arrangements across the Atlantic and Arctic that have a structuring effect on the marine governance and the implementation of area-based management measures across States. Recognising substantial differences across the Atlantic and Arctic basin, the regional governance arrangements are addressed separately. OSPAR is presented in a separate sub-chapter, since it spans both basins of the Lighthouse.

Part 6: Atlantic national governance baseline

This section provides a description of the marine governance landscape within each of the BlueMissionAA Atlantic States. The strategic direction for marine protection and restoration, the legal framework and the measures of implementation are being assessed.

Part 7: Arctic national governance baseline

This section provides a description of the marine governance landscape within each of the BlueMissionAA Arctic States. The strategic direction for marine protection and restoration, the legal framework and the measures of implementation are being assessed.

Part 8: Reflections

This section provides the reflections for the next steps of the project. These reflections are aligned with the key observations from section 4.

1. Purpose statement

This report directly supports the BlueMissionAA work package 1 (WP1) overarching goal of advancing an effective governance framework. It assesses policies, initiatives, and actions at the national, regional, and EU levels to consolidate and mobilise a wide community of relevant stakeholders and EU citizens toward the achievement of Mission objectives at the basin level.

The identified critical gaps, synergies, and discussion areas from this report, in combination with the findings from the Task 1.3 (T1.3) report on ecological restoration, as well as inputs from citizen-oriented tasks and other Mission projects, will be advanced through T1.4 of this work package. An expert panel has been established for the purpose of T1.4, with the objective of discussing the outline of a region-specific proposal for the implementation of the Mission Ocean.

Objective of the report

The European Union (EU) and the individual States across the Atlantic and Arctic lighthouse are already committed to delivering ambitious goals regarding climate action, environmental protection, ecosystem restoration, and biodiversity. The Mission aims to catalyse and fast-track the cooperation and governance needed to deliver on these targets. To create effective lighthouse architecture in the Atlantic and Arctic regions, it will be essential to map (Deliverable 1.2) and understand the existing strategic, policy, and legislative frameworks that underpin ecosystem and biodiversity protection and restoration across these regions and associated action plans and delivery mechanisms. The thematic scope of this report is strongly focused towards area-based management measures for conservation, which can also positively contribute to restoration targets.

Marine conservation efforts rely on robust governance and policy frameworks. Understanding the existing landscape of these frameworks, identifying commonalities, and addressing gaps is crucial for advancing marine area-based conservation. In this report, we explore regional and national governance structures that contribute to or intersect with the objectives of the Mission Ocean.

The specific objectives of the report are:

1. To map the existing strategic, policy, and legislative frameworks that underpin ecosystem and biodiversity protection and restoration across the Atlantic and Arctic regions and associated action plans and delivery mechanisms (at the regional and national level).
2. To make observations on commonalities, synergies, inconsistencies, and gaps.
3. To make suggestions for discussion areas to be progressed as part of BlueMissionAA task T1.4, as well as the effectiveness of protection areas, provide valuable insights.

2. Introduction

International context

Marine ecosystems are vital for global biodiversity and play a crucial role in maintaining ecological balance. The oceans are under increasing pressure due to anthropogenic disturbance and the effects of climate change (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change (IPCC), 2022). As we exploit the seas, multiple pressures arise that lead to unprecedented, combined effects on marine species, habitats, and ecosystems (Halpern et al., 2008). As a result, it is estimated that globally about 40% of the marine environment is now severely altered (European Environment Agency, 2019). To address these challenges, area-based management measures such as marine protected areas (MPAs) and other effective conservation measures (OECMs) are crucial tools for conserving marine biodiversity and maintaining ecosystem services (Lausche & Burhenne-Guilmin, 2011).

The 1982 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (LOSC), also known as the 'Constitution of the Ocean,' provides the international legal framework for various aspects of ocean use, including conservation and resource management. UNCLOS places an unqualified obligation on states to protect and conserve the marine environment, with varying obligations across the jurisdictional zones (Art. 192). This legal framework supports the establishment of MPAs and OECMs within the exclusive economic zones (EEZ) of States, facilitating the achievement of international conservation targets.

Recognising the importance of biological diversity, the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) has set ambitious targets for area-based marine protection. The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, adopted during the 15th Conference of Parties to the CBD, replaced the Aichi Biodiversity Targets with increased ambitions:

“Ensure that at least 30% globally of land areas and of sea areas, especially areas of particular importance for biodiversity and its contributions to people, are conserved through effectively and equitably managed, ecologically representative and well-connected systems of protected areas and other effective area-based conservation measures and integrated into the wider landscapes and seascapes” (Target 3, CBD Kunming-Montreal)

A previous draft of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework included a target for 10% strict protection; however, this has been removed in the final adopted version (Harrison, 2021).

The CBD targets provide an overarching framework for conservation actions at regional and national levels. The EU, as a signatory to the CBD, actively integrates and reinforces these objectives through its EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and subsequent legal and policy frameworks. Moreover, the EU Biodiversity Strategy strengthens global targets for EU Member States (MS) by specifically mandating that a third of the protected areas should be strictly protected (Harrison, 2021). In the Arctic, national objectives related to area-based protection are directly influenced by the international CBD framework and regional collaboration platforms, including the Arctic Council.

EU Mission ‘Restore our Ocean and Waters’

The EU Mission ‘Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030’ (hereafter Mission Ocean) aligns closely with the international CBD objectives and is designed to support the implementation of these targets at a regional and national level.

Mission Ocean is one of five EU Missions launched in 2021. These missions have been devised to tackle some of our greatest challenges and aim to deliver concrete results on ambitious goals by 2030. Mission Ocean, together with the other EU Missions, supports Commission priorities such as the European Green Deal (The European Green Deal - European Commission, 2021).

Mission Ocean's objective is to restore the health of the EU's oceans and waters by 2030 by reaching the European Green Deal targets for biodiversity, zero pollution, and decarbonisation, thereby addressing the three principal drivers of degradation.

The Mission supports regional engagement and cooperation to achieve the Mission objectives through area-based ‘Lighthouses’ in major sea and river basins: Atlantic-Arctic, Mediterranean Sea, Baltic-North Sea, and Danube-Black Sea. Mission lighthouses are sites to pilot, demonstrate, develop, and deploy Mission activities across EU seas and river basins. Each lighthouse leads on a different Mission objective, with the Atlantic-Arctic lighthouse focusing on objective 1, the protection and restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems for increased climate resilience in the Atlantic and Arctic basin. The specific Mission Ocean objective and associated targets for the Atlantic-Arctic Lighthouse are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mission Ocean Objective and Associated Targets for the Atlantic-Arctic Lighthouse. From (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2023)

Objective	Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity
Target 1	Protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's Sea area and integrate ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network
Target 2	Strictly protect at least 10% of the EU's Sea area
Target 3	Contribute to relevant upcoming marine nature restoration targets including degraded seabed habitats and coastal ecosystems

The European Commission's Implementation Plan for Mission Ocean (European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2023) sets out the approach to meet the Mission objectives. Implementation of the Mission takes place in two phases:

1. The development and piloting phase (2021-2025), which includes area-based ‘Lighthouses’ in four major European sea and river basins, with each lighthouse addressing one specific objective.
2. The deployment and upscaling phase (2026-2030), during which solutions developed in the lighthouses from the first phase will be scaled up and replicated across basins.

Geographical scope of the report

The BlueMissionAA lighthouse encompasses the North-East Atlantic and covers maritime space under national jurisdiction, including the marine space of the EU Member States, EU Overseas Countries and Territories (OCTs), countries that are part of the European Economic Area (EEA), and non-EU countries with close relations to the EU.

For this report, the delineation of the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse Area is as follows:

- Atlantic:** the marine waters of Ireland, France, Spain, and Portugal. The Atlantic Lighthouse Area comprises the following EU regional seas within the Northeast Atlantic Ocean: Celtic Seas, Bay of Biscay, and the Iberian Coast; Macaronesia. See Figure 1.
- Arctic:** the marine waters covered by the term 'European Arctic region' have been described in several EU documents, as shown in Figure , by the European Environment Agency (*Macro Regions in Europe and Arctic*, n.d.). This definition covers Northern Norway (including Svalbard and Jan Mayen), Greenland, Iceland, and the Faroe Islands. While these states are not direct members of the EU, they all have close relationships with the EU and will be considered relevant for the Arctic Lighthouse in this report. See Figure 2.

Figure 1 EEA marine assessment areas. From (European Environment Agency, 2022a)

Figure 2 The Arctic region in relation to the EU. From (European Environment Agency, 2017)

3. Methodology

The report is a baseline mapping exercise conducted primarily as a desk-based study to determine a governance baseline of the Atlantic and Arctic basins within the lighthouse, recognising substantial disparities in regulatory contexts. The approach taken was as described below:

- **Step #1:** Defining the governance parameters and components to compare between States. This forms the basis for mapping the governance baseline.
 - Governance parameters were identified to standardise the information collection and characterisation of States and regional governance arrangements within the scope of the study in a manner that enabled commonalities to be identified and discussed. The project team decided on the governance parameters outlined in Table 2, based on the expertise of the project team and a review of the existing literature. It's important to note that the parameter 'people' was considered a cross-cutting parameter that pertains to the strategic direction, legal framework, and implementation.
 - Parameters were chosen to reflect the scale and scope of BlueMissionAA. The use of governance parameters when providing an assessment between states is because governance components are considered invariant, however associated parameters are variant (consistent with the theory of principles and parameters).
 - The project team identified guiding questions for each of the parameters, providing a common approach and direction for the analysis of each state and region (see Table 2). It is important to note that the guiding questions were context-dependent and completed per State where appropriate.
- **Step #2:** Identify the current state of governance within the Atlantic & Arctic Lighthouse A desk-based literature and policy document review (baseline review) was conducted using existing information about the current landscape for marine ecosystem and biodiversity restoration in the Atlantic and Arctic basins. This baseline review collected information available through research articles, existing reviews, and baseline study reports, as well as on primary sources (policy documents and legal acts).
 - The information was collated in terms of the governance parameters identified in Step #1 to compare between States and regional governance arrangements to conduct a baseline.
 - The mapping of the Atlantic governance baseline utilises information and reports available from a range of existing projects and initiatives. For the EU Member States this included reviewing the following websites: <https://www.marineplan.eu/>, <https://prep4blue.eu/> and <https://www.interregeurope.eu/governance> (e.g. Regional innovation governance: key learnings).
 - Regarding the Arctic States, there were limited existing review reports on marine protection and restoration. Consequently, the approach primarily involved analysing national policy documents and legal acts. Assessment reports from organizations like the Arctic Council, along with research articles, provided additional support for the analysis. However, for certain countries, national policy documents were not accessible in English. In those cases, the analysis was conducted in the national language, with translation services used for Faroese and Icelandic documents. This approach partially restricted the possibility to conduct in-depth analysis for these two countries.

- **Step #3:** Identify commonalities across states and regions in the existing governance, recognising the strengths and opportunities, and considering apparent gaps.
 - The comparative analysis across the sea basins and States was structured around the governance parameters, identifying 5-6 key observations pertaining to each governance parameter.
- **Step #4:** Discussion and identification of proposals for action for future consideration as part of T1.4.
 - Based on the comparative key observations, further discussion and reflection points were identified. These are suggestions for future proposals for action but will be refined as part of the discussions in the expert panel discussions in T1.4.

The methodology combined expert consultations and comprehensive desk research. Key policy and governance actors were engaged through discussions at conferences and webinars, including the BlueMission BANOS arena, UNESCO Ocean Decade Conference 2024, 2024 European Ocean Days, 2nd Blue Parks Community workshop, Ocean Decade MPA Forum – Marine Protected Areas: Progress, Obstacles and Solutions and the BlueMissionAA webinar series. These interactions helped identify crucial research areas that shaped the report's scope. Subsequently, an in-depth desk-based study was conducted to further refine and explore these identified areas, forming the primary approach of the research.

Table 2 Governance parameters and components used to determine baseline governance within the Atlantic & Arctic region.

Parameter area	Component governance term	Guiding question
Purpose / Direction	Strategic direction / Overarching strategy	What are the strategic vision and objectives for marine protection and restoration?
		Is there an overarching cross-sectoral (national) strategy or are objectives for marine protection and restoration formulated in strategic documents of a single ministry?
		If so, does the national strategy reference international and regional policies/conventions? Which?
		Who decided on / what groups decided on the strategic vision / objectives? What is the legal status of this vision?
		Has the role of OECMs been highlighted in the strategic vision?
Legal framework	Legal instrument	What is the primary legislation for establishing MPAs and restoration initiatives? What is the spatial scope of this legal instrument?
		Is there a site-specific management plan that references all relevant legal instruments affecting an MPA, or is legislation relevant to MPAs fragmented across legal instruments?
		Is there a system for marine spatial planning, and (how) are MPAs and restoration initiatives integrated into the spatial planning process?
		Are there different classifications of MPA/s / restoration, and what are their definitions? What legal status do the different MPA / restoration classifications have?
		Has the country declared areas as OECMs? If so, what are the relevant legal acts for the establishment of OECMs?
		Is there a legal act for the restoration of marine and coastal ecosystems in place?
	Legal institution	What decision-making bodies are responsible for the designation of MPAs / MPA / restoration classification? Is there a cross-sectoral / cross-department committee?
		Which governance levels are involved in the decision-making process?
	Science-policy interface	How is scientific advice considered in the decision-making process of marine policies (both MPA and OECMs) and restoration?
	Implementation	Delivery / Integrated implementation
Does the implementation of MPAs/OECMs reflect the strategic ambition?		
Who is the decision-making body for the implementation of the strategic direction? Which governance levels are involved?		
What are the processes used to demonstrate the delivery of the strategic direction?		
Is funding for MPAs based on state budget, or are alternative budgeting policies implemented?		
Adaptive governance		What adaptive management / feedback loops are in place to review the progress made on the targets set in overarching strategies, plans, and laws? What reporting regime is there, and to whom is the reporting done? Are there quantified and time-bound targets to report on?
People	Transparency	Is there a platform or reporting scheme that makes information on progress to overarching objectives and targets easily accessible for the public?
	Participation	What stakeholder engagement was there on the vision and objectives? Was there a consultation process in place?
		How are stakeholders engaged with / involved in the management of MPAs or OECMs? Are management responsibilities devolved?

4. Key observations across Atlantic & Arctic governance frameworks

The following section summarises the commonalities between States within BlueMissionAA and presents these in relation to the identified governance parameters.

Overarching consideration of people

As identified in the Methodology in section 4 the governance parameter 'people' is a cross-cutting parameter. The key observations below should be read and interpreted in this context and recognise that 'people' pervade through all governance parameters.

Overarching consideration of climate change

On 21 May 2024, the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (ITLOS) issued an advisory opinion on climate change and international law, emphasising the interconnectedness of international climate law and the law of the sea. This opinion underscores the need for coordinated efforts to protect marine environments.

All States within the study are cognisant of the challenges posed by climate change and seek to recognise and account for this within their strategic documentation and, in some cases, as part of their broader legal frameworks. What is less apparent is how climate change is accounted for in the design, implementation, and monitoring of marine protected areas. The baseline study identified:

- 1) Static lines being drawn on a map either as an individual MPA or as part of MSP supported by evidence informed decisions. This raises concerns about the adaptability of the governance and legal framework.
- 2) A monitoring framework constrained by the data available, and where data is available the timeliness of the data becoming available to inform decision making. This raises concerns about the adaptability of the scientific data collection processes and reporting.
- 3) Ocean governance is not static and for there to be effective governance there needs to be established effective feedback loops which provide the ability for decision makers at all levels to review performance against the specified purpose/direction of the MPAs and adapt and amend their governance and associated management accordingly.
- 4) Despite the intent of the legal framework for regular updates, the reporting timeframes in place across the basin are not currently conducive to providing information to support decision-making in a manner that supports timely adaptive management decisions. For example, within the EU, the EEA has a reporting frequency of 72 months (6 years), which arguably cannot be classified as responsive.

Strategic Direction

Key observations – Summary

- **KO1:** All States recognise the importance of the marine environment, and vertical integration from international conservation targets has been demonstrated among individual states. There are differences in standardisation of strategic conservation objectives, which are more harmonised across the Atlantic than the Arctic States. Reference to strict protection remains predominantly unspecified in national frameworks.
- **KO2:** Horizontal integration of strategic objectives for marine conservation into wider marine policy frameworks varies across States. Approaches range from integration of conservation into holistic marine management frameworks to dedicated plans for conservation, as well as an absence of specific marine strategies altogether.
- **KO3:** Regional and national frameworks provide inadequate specification and direction for marine restoration.
- **KO4:** The absence of standardised terminology for area-based measures in the marine environment leads to variations in area designations and reporting standards.
- **KO5:** There is an inadequate specification of the relationship between marine restoration and area-based measures (MPAs/OECMs).
- **KO6:** The importance of stakeholder engagement and participation is well recognised and accounted for when setting the strategic direction. However, there are apparent constraints imposed by established legal frameworks that impact the ability to achieve effective genuine stakeholder participation in marine protection decision-making processes.

KO1: Variation in vertical integration of international marine protection commitments across Atlantic and Arctic States

All States have incorporated references to international commitments, including CBD targets for marine protection, into their national frameworks, demonstrating vertical integration. However, differences exist in how this vertical integration is achieved when setting national strategic directions within the Atlantic and Arctic States. This can be attributed to States exercising their sovereignty and transposing international commitments into national strategies in a manner appropriate to their respective legal frameworks. Within the EU, the process is more prescriptive for Member States, with EU directives and strategies developed based on international obligations, which in turn confers obligations onto Member States in a standardised manner. In comparison, Arctic states do not have the intermediary step of a regional Union, leading to more divergent approaches to integrate international objectives. Within the Arctic, increased international ambition towards the Kunming-Montreal Agreement has not yet been reflected by all States in their national frameworks. The Arctic Council and other regional arrangements support the alignment and integration of international strategic directions into national objectives, but the absence of legislative authority limits their streamlining capacity.

The vertical integration of targets for strict protection within national strategic frameworks varies among states. At the EU level, the EU Biodiversity Strategy introduces a legally binding target for strict protection (applied to the EU as a whole, not individual Member States). However, how this is specifically incorporated into Member State strategic documents varies. For example, France has integrated strict protection targets into its national plan for protected areas. In Spain and Portugal, targets for strict protection are not explicitly stated in their strategic documents and plans. Interestingly, Ireland represents

a member state that is introducing new legislation, and the current drafts indicate that it will take a more explicit approach akin to France's approach. Whilst across the Arctic strategic ambitions for strict protection remain largely unspecified in the national policy ambitions, this should be considered in light of the international context; the final agreement of the CBD was adopted without a strict protection target, albeit this was included in a previous draft. As these countries are not part of the EU, they are not obliged to abide by the respective EU targets. For example, Norway's integrated plan for marine conservation only mentions the 30% target and contains no provisions for strict protection.

KO2: Diverse approaches to horizontal integration in marine conservation policies across States

The horizontal integration of plans for marine conservation within broader marine policy frameworks varies across States. Some States have developed comprehensive, integrated marine strategies that recognise both marine protected areas (MPAs) and other effective area-based conservation measures (OECMs) as part of a holistic approach to marine conservation. These strategies align MPA/OECM planning with broader objectives for sustainable use of marine resources and ecosystem-based management. Other countries have developed separate, dedicated plans specifically for MPAs and OECMs. This approach allows for more targeted strategies and measures tailored to the unique challenges and opportunities of area-based conservation but comes with the risk that these objectives are not sufficiently integrated into the wider seascape. In some cases, ocean-related targets might be reflected in national biodiversity policies, whereas some states lack a dedicated strategic plan for MPAs and OECMs in the marine environment altogether.

The examples below represent different approaches to horizontal integration:

- Norway's integrated ocean management plans implement ecosystem-based management principles and shall ensure a balanced approach to sustainable use and environmental protection. MPAs and OECMs are considered one of several elements of the integrated ocean management. On the specific implementation of MPAs and OECMs, the integrated ocean plans reference a separate governmental white paper (marine conservation plan), which provides the strategic direction on marine conservation. This reflects a hybrid approach that incorporates elements of both integrated and separate planning.
- Portugal has an integrated spatial planning policy representing a holistic approach to horizontal integration. This is particularly notable in the context of establishing horizontal integration to reflect integrated coastal management. This is demonstrated through the use of Coastal Zone Programmes (POC) supported by a system of marine spatial planning and territorial management (sistema de gestão territorial).
- The Ocean Strategy of Iceland contains no specific provisions for marine protection. Instead, conservation targets are references in national biodiversity policies. The national biodiversity policy is currently under revision, indicating a stronger emphasis towards the role of the oceans.

KO3: Limited focus on marine restoration in national and regional frameworks within BlueMissionAA Lighthouse

A common theme across the national and regional frameworks, within the BlueMissionAA Lighthouse, is the inadequate specification and direction for marine restoration. Both the Atlantic and Arctic demonstrate that ecological restoration of the marine environment has received limited attention in the strategic direction of national frameworks, whereas terrestrial restoration policy and legal frameworks tend to be more elaborated. The examples below represent varying degrees of specification:

- In Spain restoration is legally defined and is incorporated into its planning, largely focussed on in the context of integrated coastal management.

- In France there is an obligation on regions to define and implement regional biodiversity strategies. These national and regional biodiversity strategies contribute to the integration of the objectives of conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity into public policies and to the coherence of the latter in these areas. These are primarily terrestrially focussed but one of the objectives for the national strategy for protected areas is to “*support activities compatible with biodiversity conservation*” which aligns with the restoring of marine ecosystems.
- Norway has incorporated objectives (not quantitative) for marine restoration in its integrated plan for marine conservation, and the Norwegian Integrated Ocean Management Plans highlight the need for increased focus on restoration, especially of carbon-rich habitats.
- Iceland has an extensive policy for terrestrial ecological restoration (including wetlands). A green paper that has been produced by a governmental committee in preparation of an updated biodiversity policy notes that “*The possibility of restoring ecosystems in the sea and in coastal areas needs to be considered*”.
- In its most recent national reporting to the CBD, Greenland notes that restoration is not regarded as relevant for the Greenlandic context, due to limited disturbance from human activity. The increasing threat from climate change is however recognised.

Observations of the legal framework of States within the scope of this report highlight an overarching impediment for restoration projects is the lack of a legal status meaning there is no formalised reporting requirements. From an EU perspective the Nature Restoration Law was passed on 17 June 2024, which is anticipated to address this apparent gap in strategic direction. However, at the time of writing it is unclear how this EU law will be enacted by Member States in practice.

KO4: Inconsistent terminology undermines effectiveness of marine area-based measures

It is recognised that the successful implementation and assessment of the performance of area-based measures is undermined by a lack of standardised terms . This study identified that across the Atlantic and Arctic States, there is a proliferation of terms associated with the governance and management of area-based measures in the marine environment. As outlined in KO1, not all states have included a definition of the term MPA into their strategic documents. The operationalisation of terms such as ‘conservation’ or ‘protection’ is applied differently, which is reflected by mismatching or unclear reporting practices (KO14). While the EU and organisations like OSPAR provide guidance and criteria for designating and reporting on MPAs, this study indicates that individual States may interpret and apply these criteria differently when developing their legal frameworks.

The inconsistent use of terms can be observed both at a regional level and within States, and even be seen at a local scale with differences in the terminology and definitions used between individual sites.

- Despite the codified nature of the EU, differences exist in how terminology is incorporated into national legislation, if at all, and the intent of its incorporation. For example, in Ireland there is no MPA definition of whereas in Spain and Portugal there are legal definitions used. Although it needs to be recognised that Ireland is proposing a legal definition for MPAs in a new bill that is currently drafted.
- While some States use these terms interchangeably, Norway has defined ‘marine conservation’ as overarching strategy for managing the environmental dimension of ocean policy. Only areas protected under the Nature Diversity Act are considered ‘protected areas’. Areas protected through sectoral legislation can contribute to marine conservation. Norway is currently reviewing to include OECMs into the national reporting for conservation targets.

- Terminology and associated levels of regulations for protection categories applied in national legal frameworks may vary across states and do not always align with the IUCN categories. Inconsistencies in terminology hamper comparability between states. Greenland is one example where the national protection category for 'nature parks' does not directly align with the IUCN category.

KO5: Limited integration of active marine restoration in area-based measures

There is an inadequate specification of the relationship between marine restoration and area-based measures (MPAs/OECMs). Passive restoration, where the designation of an MPA/OECM removes the pressures on the ecosystem, allowing for natural recovery, is referred to at a strategic level. For example, the Nature Restoration Law identifies the close relationship between the concept of restoration and protection (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2024 on Nature Restoration and Amending Regulation (EU) 2022/869 (Text with EEA Relevance), 2024), and identifies MPA networks as an important element (Gregory Fuchs, Nico Stelljes, 2022; Salafsky et al., 2024). It is also recognised by the OSPAR definition of MPA, which includes 'restorative measures' (*Marine Protected Areas*, n.d.). These approaches can be referred to as passive restoration, where the designation of an MPA/OECM removes the pressures on the ecosystem, allowing for natural recovery. Examples of an OECM that achieves restoration outcomes ('rewilding') are lobster no-take zones in Norway, implemented through fisheries legislation.

In contrast, the integration and alignment of active restoration measures into MPA/OECMs are rarely specified at a strategic level, resulting in ambiguity regarding reporting and monitoring standards. This gap exists despite UNEP underlining that restoration measures, both within and outside the borders of an OECM/MPA, can enhance the efficiency of the protection (*Marine Restoration and MPAs*, 2024). For example, the Norwegian Integrated Plan for Marine Conservation states that eelgrass planting or removal of contaminated sediments can be regarded as active restoration measures. However, there is no further specification on how these relate to area-based measures (MPAs and OECMs) or the reporting standards.

KO6: Emphasis on stakeholder engagement and participatory processes in marine governance

The strategic documentation from various States promotes the establishment of participatory arrangements and recognises the importance of stakeholder engagement and participation. In most states, a legal obligation, such as the requirement to consult, ensures participatory processes are in place. For example, in Spain, the requirement for participation is enshrined in their constitution. These findings are evident in the participatory processes observed in governance implementation (see KO15) and are supported by observations from T1.3 case studies, highlighting the importance of participation at the local level.

Legal framework

Key observations - Summary

- **KO7:** The majority of Arctic States, have cross-sectoral legal instruments for marine conservation that are limited to the Territorial Sea, leaving the Exclusive Economic Zone without an adequate legal instrument for area-based protection. States have demonstrated progress towards addressing this gap. The potential of designating OECMs in the EEZ is considered as an alternative pathway to achieve conservation.
- **KO8:** Legal frameworks governing marine conservation often lack comprehensive authority to impose restrictions on all sectors that may exert pressure on designated protected areas or restoration sites. This limitation, combined with insufficient policy coherence and integration across various sectoral legislations, compromises the effectiveness of protection measures for marine conservation sites. These challenges are particularly pronounced in areas beyond territorial seas.
- **KO9:** Variability exists between Atlantic & Arctic States regarding how MPAs/Restoration projects are legally required to be recorded, monitored, and reported on.
- **KO10:** Allocation of national level institutional responsibilities for the governance of MPAs diverge across States. Designation of MPAs remains under the legal competence of States, but regional coordination mechanisms can support the governance processes.
- **KO11:** MPA governance involves multiple tiers of governance. The degree of decentralization or devolution varies across States, reflecting the coexistence of both top-down and bottom-up approaches to MPA governance and management.

KO7: Disparities in legal frameworks for area-based marine protection across the Atlantic and Arctic

While all Atlantic countries have legal frameworks for area-based management that cover their entire Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) through the nature directives and additional national laws, it is notable that the legal framework for area-based protection, through Natura 2000, is only for selected habitat types and species that are explicitly listed in the EU Directives. The spatial coverage of area-based protection frameworks in the Arctic remains largely limited to the territorial sea. Although there is a growing trend in the Arctic to extend terrestrial and coastal conservation laws to marine areas or create dedicated marine protection frameworks, significant gaps persist. In certain Arctic states, the use of area-based measures established through sectoral legislation (OECMs) has received increased attention and is recognised as a significant contribution to national and global conservation targets. These legal frameworks (typically management of living marine resources) extend across the entire EEZ. Some area-based fisheries regulation measures (e.g. bottom trawl prohibition in cold water coral sites) have already been designated as MPAs under OSPAR. For other areas regulated through fisheries regulations, the evaluation of OECM status is ongoing.

- In Norway, the Nature Diversity Act only covers the territorial sea (12 nautical miles). Outside this area, conservation measures can only be implemented as part of sectoral legislation. Large area-based measures have been enacted under the Marine Resource Act (fisheries legislation); their potential reporting as OECM is currently being assessed. In 2024, the Ministry for Climate and Environment presented a proposal for an exclusive marine conservation law, which would enable the establishment of MPAs in the EEZ.
- Iceland has gradually increased the geographical scope of its Nature Conservation Act to now cover the entire EEZ. Iceland reports cold-water corals protected through fisheries legislation as

MPAs to OSPAR and has recently announced additional fisheries measures as important contribution to international conservation targets.

- Nature conservation in the Faroe Islands has undergone significant improvements with the enactment of a new Nature Conservation Act in 2024. The Act introduces the establishment of area-based protection categories but does only extend out to the territorial sea. The Faroese Marine Environment Act is tailored towards pollution-related matters, meaning that there is no legal framework to establish MPAs in the entire EEZ.
- Greenlandic governance of marine areas is under shared competence with Denmark. The Greenlandic Nature Conservation Act covers land and the territorial sea (currently located at 3nm). Greenland is considering extending the territorial sea to 12nm, which would increase the scope for implementing area-based measures. Beyond the territorial sea, Danish authorities oversee the Greenlandic Marine Environment Act, covering shipping and pollution-related matters. No legal framework is in place to designate MPAs beyond the territorial sea.

KO8: Balancing socio-economic and environmental priorities: Challenges of spatial squeeze in MPA legislation and sectoral integration

'Spatial squeeze' is an increasingly contentious area where States seek to address this in a way that reflects a balance between their different socioeconomic priorities and environmental considerations. In most cases, MPAs are designated through environmental legislation. However, the achievement of conservation outcomes is often affected by activities regulated under other sectoral laws. The interactions and integration between MPA legislation and sectoral activities is a complex challenge. In several countries, fisheries management operates independently from, or at least not sufficiently integrated into MPA designation and management:

- In the EU context, the Nature Directives (Birds and Habitats Directive), significant aspects of the marine ecosystem are not included under the formal protection schemes. Only those habitats and species listed in the directives are accounted for and are established based on the premise of conservation priorities. This is further complicated by the fact that one Member State can establish an MPA and, nevertheless, another Member State can assert it still has access rights to the same area based on the Common Fisheries Policy. Within the EU, this creates a conflict between the protection of fishing rights and how both these rights are accounted for as part of the designation of MPAs and under which legal mechanism the MPA is established.

The complexity is also experienced within Arctic States, such as Norway. While the Nature Diversity Act can include provisions for various sectoral activities within MPAs, fisheries regulations within MPAs are under a different jurisdiction (different Ministry and legal Act). This dual system can lead to coordination challenges between nature conservation and fisheries sectors. This is demonstrated by the weak protection level in several Norwegian MPAs, where fishery regulations often remain limited. This reflects a common challenge many countries face with separate agencies responsible for conservation and fisheries management. This study identified that gaps and weaknesses in the legal mandate of MPA legislation and their interaction with sectoral legislation are being addressed through integrated planning approaches or environmental mainstreaming in sectoral legislation. For example:

- Across the EU states, the EU Marine Spatial Planning Directive has driven a significant shift towards a more integrated planning model for marine areas, moving away from sectoral approaches. While this provides a framework for holistic management, the full integration of nature conservation, including restoration and MPA planning, into the MSP process remains a challenge. The Marine Strategy Framework Directive and MSPD are intended to promote an ecosystem-based approach to designing and managing marine areas, including MPA networks. These directives provide a framework for Member States to develop national strategies and

planning documents. However, the specific coordination and implementation of these strategies vary between states, reflecting national priorities and approaches within the broader EU framework.

- Norway has developed an integrated management regime for all its marine areas through ocean management plans. These plans, endorsed by Parliament, provide a framework for ecosystem-based management that considers multiple sectors and activities. While the plans serve as a political framework, implementation occurs through sectoral legislation. Sectoral authorities remain responsible for decision-making within their respective areas, which can sometimes lead to challenges in balancing different interests. Current discussions on the establishment for a legal framework to designate MPAs beyond the territorial sea would strengthen the environmental provisions.
- An example for environmental mainstreaming into sectoral integration can be found in Greenland, where the legal framework for area-based protection does not encompass the regulation of resource extraction. According to international standards, this would only qualify for IUCN category V. However, environmental provisions under the Mineral Resource Act have been strengthened, including the establishment of a separate authority under the Resource Ministry to separate environmental regulations from licencing. These provisions can address shortcomings in the legal frameworks for area-based protection.

KO9: Variability in legal requirements for recording, monitoring, and reporting of MPAs and restoration projects

Variability exists between Atlantic and Arctic States regarding how MPAs/Restoration projects are legally required to be recorded, monitored, and reported on. (See KO13 below for respective implementation-related information.)

KO10: Variations in institutional responsibilities for MPA management and cross-sectoral coordination

The manner in which institutional responsibilities for establishing and managing MPAs are being divided varies significantly across States. At the national level, responsibilities for MPAs are often shared among different ministries. In the Arctic states, environmental ministries predominantly hold the mandate for the legal frameworks to designate MPAs, implying a need for cross-sectoral coordination. In some EU states, there has been a shift from sectoral departmentalization towards establishing ministries that hold competencies in all matters related to the marine environment, as demonstrated in Portugal with the creation of the Ministry of the Sea. In Ireland, a report from the Joint Committee on Environment & Climate Action recommended creating a ministry for marine affairs to consolidate responsibilities and improve coordination. It should be noted that within some EU States views with regards to having a centralised ministry compared to discrete sectoral ministries have varied and changed over time.

In recognition that *“incoherent division of mandates between organizations and levels of governance can hamper biodiversity integration in policymaking or implementation”* (MSP4BIO, 2024), some States have established high-level national coordination bodies to provide oversight between institutions and promote alignment through coordination, collaboration, and effective communication. The coordination role can be established through a formal approach, such as in Spain where the CIAM is a legally mandated body responsible for coordinating across institutions. Or a more informal process reliant on voluntary collaboration and coordination, such as the cross-ministry forums that have been established in Ireland. In Norway, as part of the process to implement integrated ocean management, a cross-ministerial steering group, under the lead of the Ministry of Climate and Environment, has been formally established.

Regional governance arrangements provide another opportunity to coordinate and streamline the implementation of marine protection. The EU reflects a codified approach to regional governance. In contrast, OSPAR and the Arctic Council constitute high-level intergovernmental forums to coordinate environmental matters and MPA governance. Regarding MPAs located in waters of national jurisdiction, OSPAR and the Arctic Council have no legal mandate to designate areas themselves but provide guidelines and coordination for member states, who then implement MPAs through national legal frameworks. The EU model is more directed and has a specified legal mandate.

KO11: Decentralisation and devolution in MPA designation and management

The designation and management of MPAs typically involve several tiers of governance. This study's observations indicate that states seek to demonstrate accountability through decentralisation and devolution. Specifically, this refers to the vertical flow of responsibilities across the levels of governance and is seen to vary significantly between States. It can also depend on the type of MPA and its objectives.

- In France, national MPAs legally require MPA management bodies to be established that have a statutory purpose and specific role. Significantly, these management bodies are required to have local representatives and provide an example of how legal mechanisms can support increased devolution of powers supported by an overarching centralised framework. Notwithstanding these responsibilities, decisions still need to be made by officials and ministers of the respective competent authorities.
- Norway's approach to MPA governance is combines top-down legal frameworks and national priorities with bottom-up, locally adapted management. Principal provisions are set in the Nature Diversity Act (NDA), whereas site-specific regulations (pursuant to the NDA) for each MPA are enacted to specify site-specific conservation objectives and regulations. The actual management is devolved to the local or regional level management board, depending on the specific circumstances of the area. Site-specific regulations are prepared by lower tiers of governance but adopted at the national level.
- In Iceland, there is a strong tradition for establishing co-management arrangements for protected sites. These arrangements typically involve local communities, stakeholders, and relevant government agencies working together to manage and protect the designated areas. Whilst the Icelandic Nature Diversity Act follows a rather top-down approach to area-based management, providing the legal framework for establishing protected areas and defining overall management objectives, an alternative pathway through site-specific legislation has substantially increased the utilization of co-management arrangements. These site-specific co-management arrangements have mainly been implemented for large terrestrial sites but also partially extend into the coastal environment. The degree of co-management involvement can vary between different protected areas.
- Ireland also represents a top-down governance approach whereby all responsibilities for the establishment and management of MPAs are located centrally. However, recent experiences associated with the drafting of the Marine Protected Areas Bill show how stakeholder views and concerns can directly influence the legislative process. Feedback from the recent Citizen Assembly focussed on marine protection and stakeholder reports have been accounted for in drafting of legislation.

Implementation

Implementation of MPAs constitutes management but as described earlier in the report management is a sub-component of governance. What is important is having a governance structure that establishes a framework to support effective management in order for the implementation of measures to achieve the strategic direction.

Key observations - Summary

- **KO12:** In many States there is an observed disconnect between strategic visions and practical implementation regarding the designation of marine protected areas (MPAs). Absence of management plans in some MPAs is another barrier.
- **KO13:** Fragmentation of reporting requirements and systems at a national and regional scale affects the ability to compare progress between States and across the BlueMissionAA lighthouse as a whole.
- **KO14:** A lack of standardised reporting on performance measures / effectiveness undermining the accountability for marine conservation performance within the Atlantic & Arctic.
- **KO15:** The study highlights that stakeholder participation often remains consultative rather than influential in decision-making, constrained by legal frameworks, and suggests the need for practical measures to balance centralised authority with meaningful local involvement in marine protection.
- **KO16:** There is a widespread issue of data paucity, along with significant gaps in data collection, standardization, and funding for marine conservation, which is a barrier to identification and prioritization of conservation sites.

KO12: Disconnect between strategic vision and implementation in MPA designation and management

This study indicates a disconnect between the strategic direction indicated in policy documents for establishing MPAs and the actual plan for their implementation. The EU Biodiversity Strategy and the CBD set ambitious targets for expanding the MPA network to cover 30% by 2030. The Mission objectives state that MPAs shall be ecologically representative and coherent and enhance connectivity across networks.

The selection of specific MPA sites to be designated as MPAs does not always align or clearly make the link with this overarching strategic direction.

- In Ireland, the draft Marine Protected Areas Bill 2022 includes a section within the Bill titled 'Identification of Potential Marine Protected Areas'. This demonstrates an aspiration to establish a formal process for creating a list of potential MPA designations that would then be subsequently reviewed and potentially implemented. The Bill also recognises existing authorisations, reflecting an acknowledgement of the need for MPAs to be integrated with broader marine planning and use. However, there is a lack of specificity about the linkage to the overarching strategic direction.
- This is in contrast with France, which doesn't have a defined process for identifying an MPA. It is, therefore, impossible to ascertain the connection between individual site designation and where it aligns with the national and EU strategic vision.

- In Iceland, the Natural Conservation Register's B-list is the strategic plan for areas considered prioritised for conservation within the next 5-year period. The list includes areas across terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine environments in Iceland. However, the assessment criteria used to determine inclusion on this list do not specifically evaluate marine habitats. As a result, the conservation value of Icelandic marine ecosystems is currently not factored into the strategic planning of nature protection in the country.
- In the case of Norway, the strategic vision for marine conservation has been continuously improved through updated governmental white papers, but the implementation of the strategic direction follows the marine protection plan where sites for prioritised areas for protection were identified back in 2004. All sites are in the coastal zone, and the identification did not take vulnerability into account. The proposed sites would not be sufficient to meet the 30% target, indicating a gap between the strategic vision and plan for implementation.

This is even more apparent for the qualitative targets, where strategic documents state that MPAs shall be ecologically representative and coherent and enhance connectivity across networks. While the strategic direction calls for effectively managing all protected areas, many existing MPAs across the lighthouse lack comprehensive, site-specific management plans that outline clear conservation objectives, measures, and monitoring protocols. The absence of management plans for all hampers transparency and does not allow assessment of how the designated site is explicitly linked to the overarching strategic goals of the MPA network. For example, in France and Spain, these are legally required for nationally governed MPAs, yet in Ireland, this is not a legal requirement.

KO13: Fragmented monitoring and reporting standards hindering effective MPA analysis and management

Within the lighthouse, different States and regional organizations employ various methodologies and standards for monitoring and reporting. The consequence of this lack of harmonisation results in data fragmentation across different projects, institutions, and countries, hindering comprehensive analysis and management. The quality and reliability of data can vary, affecting the accuracy of assessments and management decisions. For example:

- In Ireland, the designation of OSPAR sites does not confer any specific protection in terms of restriction of activities within these areas unless they are coincident with sites that are either SACs or SPAs (according to the Nature Directives). This means that the reporting of marine protection to OSPAR will differ from the EU reporting, as EU reporting only includes sites with legal protection status.
- In Iceland and Norway, areas protected through fisheries legislation (bottom-trawling prohibitions in cold-water corals) have been reported as MPAs to the OSPAR database. This indicates different reporting practices and varying use of terminologies at the national and regional level: Norway's white paper on marine conservation states that only areas protected through environmental legislation will be considered MPAs.

Regarding reporting systems, the EU has established reporting frameworks and dashboards administered centrally by the European Environment Agency (EEA), e.g., the EU Biodiversity Strategy Dashboard and the EU Biodiversity Strategy Actions Tracker. Despite the use of centralised dashboards, the concern is that the data being used to inform is not consistent among Member States, as identified above, which impacts the utility of these systems.

In comparison, the Arctic states have no shared and harmonised reporting obligations, causing fragmentation and a lack of transparency about the progress. The Arctic Council's working group on the protection of the marine environment (PAME) is working towards a Pan-Arctic Network of MPAs and has established an overview of currently protected areas. The database relies on information retrieved from

member states, and OECMs have not yet been considered. At the national level, there are varying reporting practices and access to databases where progress on MPAs can be tracked. There is an increasing trend towards utilising national GIS-supported platforms to monitor progress. The Norwegian database contains a specific dataset for marine protected areas, whereas the datasets are more fragmented or still under preparation for the other Arctic lighthouse states.

KO14: Limitations in marine conservation reporting and accountability impacting MPA effectiveness

A significant limitation in marine conservation reporting is that reporting obligations primarily relate to the presence/absence of an MPA and its environmental status. These reporting mechanisms do not record trends or provide a comparative analysis of areas that are not MPAs. Reporting frameworks identified in this study are focussed on reporting progress towards percentage coverage. The use of quantitative coverage as an indicator metric is rational given the difficulty of coordinating between states; however, in reality, it can be considered a crude performance metric.

Using percentage coverage as the metric for success, with the lack of a clear definition and overview of the actual protection level of a specific protection category in national legislation, impedes comparability. While it can be recognised that the process of harmonisation is ongoing, currently, variability remains regarding how States designate a site at the national level, EU level or under regional seas conventions. Examples of different uses of terminology in national protection frameworks are found in KO4.382. This, in turn, raises questions about the standardised reporting of performance measures and how this relates to MPA effectiveness.

Marine conservation efforts within the lighthouse involve multiple stakeholders at different governmental levels (local, regional, national, and international). Observations in this study have identified a fragmentation of responsibilities and unclear lines of accountability both nationally and at a regional level. This fragmentation can result in gaps where no single entity takes full responsibility for outcomes or failures. This translates into a lack of accountability.

Observations from this study have shown an inability to determine the effectiveness of management measures to meet strategic objectives and achieve meaningful change. The absence of effective performance feedback loops for the monitoring and evaluation of conservation measures removes accountability, as it means there is an inability to determine the effectiveness of management measures to meet strategic objectives and achieve meaningful change. This potentially results in stakeholders perceiving little consequence for non-compliance or reducing incentives to adhere to conservation measures. The lack of accountability can potentially undermine confidence and, ultimately, the success of meeting the deserved strategic vision. The need to strengthen accountability through performance feedback is intrinsically linked to setting a clear purpose/direction for marine conservation.

KO15: Limited public participation in MPA Governance despite consultative efforts

While many States have made efforts to increase public participation in marine protected area (MPA) governance, the reality is that local bodies and citizens are often limited to a consultative role rather than being actively involved in decision-making. This is exemplified by the current consultation process for Ireland's Designated Marine Area Plan (DMAP), where participation is restricted to providing input, even though the decision on the site has already been made and will ultimately be determined by the Ministry. Norway follows a comparable approach, where lower levels of government and stakeholders are consulted during the MPA establishment process, whereas the final decision on the site-specific regulation lies within the competence of the Ministry, approved by the government. Both France and Portugal have established participatory processes for MPA designation, but legal mandates constrain the scale and scope of participation, as decision-making powers remain with government authorities. In Spain and Portugal, the constitutional provisions for public participation do not override the fact that

ministers hold the legal authority to make final decisions. Norway follows a comparable approach, where lower levels of government and stakeholders are consulted during the MPA establishment process, whereas the final decision on the site-specific regulation lies within the competence of the Ministry, approved by the government. This legal reality limits the degree of public involvement that can be achieved. A site-specific legislation approach can be observed in Iceland, which has increased the potential for co-management of protection sites. At the same time, the diversification of management systems poses a challenge to the coordination across protected sites and vertical linkages to the national governance level.

It is important to note that this is not a reflection of states' unwillingness to increase participation. Rather, it is a consequence of balancing meaningful public participation with the legal obligations and mandates of government decision-makers. Even the European Union, which advocates for greater public participation, is subject to these constraints within its own legal framework. The challenge is to establish a balance between centralised authority and meaningful local involvement. Potentially advancing genuine stakeholder influence can be achieved through enhancing public awareness and citizen science initiatives.

The observation for MPAs is equally apparent for restoration projects and arguably more complex. Additional complexity is associated with the fact that restoration sites do not commonly have legal status, and therefore, there is no requirement or guidance to implement participatory processes. As T1.3 has identified, these projects were established through participatory processes, but these are commonly more locally focussed and less established.

KO16: Data gaps and fragmentation undermine marine conservation effectiveness and decision-making

A strong ocean policy depends on a sound understanding of our oceans, how they react to the cumulative impacts of human activity, and how we can wisely use what they have to offer (Ramses A, 2022).

Improvements in data availability have been made. However, the most recent Eurostat review of EU progress towards SDGs identifies that *"the available data do not provide an indication of the sites' conservation status nor the effectiveness of the protection they offer to species and habitats"* (Eurostat, 2022). Significant gaps remain in data availability, standardization, and effective utilization. A common theme of this report is the lack of baseline information with which to support the identification and prioritisation of marine conservation sites. Significant gaps in data coverage, particularly in remote and less-studied areas of the Arctic and deep-sea regions of the Atlantic. Limited data coverage and accessibility impact the establishment of different marine conservation sites, which impacts marine conservation governance in two keyways:

1. It undermines the ability to determine the effectiveness / impact of marine conservation at all levels. For example, any MPA or restoration project that does not have baseline information and comparative monitoring to 'control areas' (either areas outside the MPA, or areas with a different use classification within an MPA) is unable to determine what the impact of such measures has been.
2. Consequently, the inability to do this routinely at an individual site level has flow on effects at a national, regional and lighthouse level.

This raises questions about the fragmented nature of integrated planning for marine conservation. The paucity of comprehensive spatial data on biodiversity impacts decision-making. With increased spatial squeeze and the need to make trade-offs between marine users, it will become increasingly relevant to have strong evidence baselines for evidence-supported decision-making. Improved coordination and enhanced technical capacity are essential to address these gaps and ensure effective marine

conservation across these regions. Despite the wealth of different databases and online platforms, they are largely duplicative of each other. Data is often scattered across various institutions and databases, making it difficult to access and integrate. This is related to the observations under KO13.

5. Regional governance baseline within the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse

The designation and management of area-based protection and restoration measures are governed by national legislation and fall under the jurisdiction of nation states. However, strategic decisions, the development of legal frameworks, and their implementation is significantly influenced by international commitments and regional governance arrangements.

This section provides an overview of the regional governance arrangements in the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse relevant for the protection and restoration of the marine environment.

- OSPAR
- European regional governance (Atlantic)
- Arctic regional governance.

OSPAR

Strategic Direction

The OSPAR (Oslo-Paris) Convention is the regional seas convention in the North-East Atlantic, encompassing both the Atlantic and Arctic regions, including areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ). OSPAR connects fifteen countries (Belgium, Kingdom of Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom) and the European Commission to protect the marine environment. Initially focused on pollution prevention from land-based sources and the offshore industry, its mandate now extends to biodiversity and ecosystem protection. OSPAR only partially covers the BlueMissionAA lighthouse, i.e., through Norway and Iceland. The Faroe Islands and Greenland are not part of OSPAR nor included in the area calculations (OSPAR Commission, 2013). Both countries have however aligned some of their legislation with OSPAR.

Area-based protection measures are an important pillar of OSPAR's strategic direction. In 1998, OSPAR's contracting parties agreed on the establishment of an MPA network. This was further concretized as to *"implement a network of marine protected areas"* and to *"protect and conserve the biological diversity of the maritime area and its ecosystems which are, or could be, affected as a result of human activities, and to restore, where practicable, marine areas which have been adversely affected."* (OSPAR Commission, 2003a).¹

OSPAR aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD). It cooperates with intergovernmental bodies and supports the implementation of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive in EU countries.

The OSPAR Commission is tasked with marine environmental protection and coordinating conservation measures (OSPAR Commission, 1998). The Strategy of the OSPAR Commission for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic 2030, adopted in 2021, outlines strategic objectives relevant to the Mission Ocean objectives of the Atlantic Arctic Lighthouse (OSPAR Commission, 2023):

¹ This commitment was reinforced through OSPAR Recommendation 2010/2, amending Recommendation 2003/3 (OSPAR Commission, 2010).

Figure 3 OSPAR organigram. From OSPAR, 2024.

Legal Framework

OSPAR has no legal mandate to designate MPAs within its member states' national jurisdictions. This legal capability lies with the respective national authorities. However, the OSPAR framework includes mechanisms to encourage and coordinate MPA designations by its Contracting Parties within their national jurisdictions. The Intersessional Correspondence Group on Marine Protected Areas (ICG-MPA) is a subsidiary body established under OSPAR to coordinate MPA-related affairs (OSPAR Commission, n.d.-a). The national institutions from Contracting Parties collaborate under the OSPAR framework to share best practices, develop common methodologies, and enhance the overall effectiveness of MPAs.

Implementation of Strategic Direction

The OSPAR Commission implements its strategic directions by coordinating with contracting parties and intergovernmental bodies. In line with OSPAR Recommendation 2003/3, as amended by 2010/2, on the establishment of an OSPAR MPA network, contracting parties designate MPAs through national legislation and then nominate these to the OSPAR Commission. OSPAR provides a framework for coordination and reporting, as well as guidelines for the designation and implementation of MPAs, including:

1. **Identification and site selection criteria:** OSPAR has developed detailed criteria for identifying and selecting sites suitable for MPA designation. These criteria include ecological significance, naturalness, and representativeness, ensuring that selected sites contribute effectively to biodiversity conservation (OSPAR Commission, 2003a).
2. **Communication with stakeholders:** Effective communication and engagement with stakeholders, including local communities, industry, and conservation groups, are crucial for the successful establishment and management of MPAs. OSPAR provides guidance on best practices for stakeholder engagement (OSPAR Commission, 2008).
3. **Management plan outlines for MPAs:** OSPAR recommends that each MPA has a plan outlining the conservation objectives, management measures, and monitoring protocols. These plans are essential for ensuring the long-term effectiveness of MPAs (OSPAR Commission, 2003b).

- S5.O1: By 2030, develop a network of MPAs and other effective area-based conservation measures (OECMs) to cover at least 30% of the OSPAR maritime area, ensuring it is representative, ecologically coherent, and effectively managed.

- S6.O2: By 2025, develop a regional approach with relevant targets for restoring degraded habitats and implement actions to achieve these targets.

4. **Guidance on ecologically coherent networks:** OSPAR emphasises the importance of creating an ecologically coherent network of MPAs, where individual protected areas are connected and collectively contribute to the overall conservation goals. This approach enhances the resilience of marine ecosystems (OSPAR Commission, 2006).

Specific tools and guidelines developed by OSPAR for the effective management and reporting of MPAs include:

1. **The OSPAR MPA Database:** This database is a critical tool for tracking the designation, management, and effectiveness of MPAs across the OSPAR maritime area. However, the current data gaps and lack of detailed information on regulatory measures limit its effectiveness.
2. **OSPAR Guidance Documents:** These documents provide detailed instructions on identifying, selecting, and managing MPAs, ensuring they meet ecological coherence and conservation objectives. They include guidelines on stakeholder communication, management plan development, and network assessment (cf. section above).
3. **Biennial Status Reports:** OSPAR's status reports on the MPA network assess progress towards meeting conservation targets and identify areas for improvement. These reports are essential for tracking the effectiveness of MPAs and guiding future conservation efforts.

Status

As of 2022, only 2.9% of the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) in OSPAR was covered by MPAs, while territorial waters and high seas show coverage of around 20%. The Arctic region, including ABNJ, has the lowest MPA coverage rate at 2%.

A survey conducted by the Intersessional Correspondence Group on Marine Protected Areas (ICG-MPA) indicated that in 70% of the OSPAR MPAs, specific management measures identified by site managers were only partially implemented by legal or other appropriate means (OSPAR Commission, 2021). An observation supported by the Roessger et al. study which concluded 70% of OSPAR MPAs lack effective regulatory mechanisms, with strict protection measures being almost non-existent, impeding the achievement of conservation targets (Roessger et al., 2022). Several reported OSPAR MPAs lack management plans or detailed status reporting on the OSPAR database (OSPAR Commission, 2022).

OSPAR addresses these gaps by encouraging contracting parties to report detailed information on the management and effectiveness of MPAs. Compared to previous OSPAR status reports, the 2021 status report demonstrated progress has been made regarding the reporting on management information as well as implementation of MPA management measures. At the same time, it is also emphasized that important gaps in the assessment of ecological coherence and management effectiveness remain. (OSPAR Commission, 2021).

The lack of transparency and comprehensive data on the regulatory measures and management effectiveness is, however, a significant barrier to achieving and tracking the progress towards OSPAR's conservation targets.

OSPAR and MPAs in areas beyond national jurisdiction

Even though the scope of the BlueMissionAA governance assessment is restricted to the areas within national jurisdiction, it is relevant to emphasise that OSPAR has played an important role in advancing MPAs in ABNJ (Molenaar & Elferink, 2009).

40% of the OSPAR area cover ABNJ. While the OSPAR convention does not directly refer to MPAs in ABNJ, it has been observed that provisions included in the convention appear to be interpreted as grounds for the establishment of MPAs in ABNJ (Klerk, 2020). Nevertheless, MPA implementation efforts in areas

beyond national jurisdiction face challenges due to the limited legal authority included in OSPAR's mandate. As set out by Article 4.1, Annex V of the OSPAR Convention, OSPAR does not itself propose measures to regulate fisheries or shipping but shall address the competent authority or international body. OSPAR's contracting parties, however, can adopt MPAs in areas beyond national jurisdiction through a legally binding OSPAR decision (only binding for OSPAR parties), supplemented by an OSPAR Recommendation outlining management activities to be taken by the contracting parties (OSPAR Commission, 2021). Such legally binding decisions, however, are subject to international law and, thus generally apply without prejudice to the rights and obligations of states under international law, including the LOSC (OSPAR Commission, n.d.-b).

Like OSPAR MPAs within national jurisdiction, assessing the transparency and management effectiveness of implemented measures for high seas MPAs is challenging. While the OSPAR Convention typically includes timetables for implementing measures, decisions to establish MPAs in areas beyond national jurisdiction lack such provisions. Although reporting obligations by contracting parties could offer more insight into the implementation of measures, this information is not publicly available. The OSPAR status reporting provides limited details on the implementation of measures within MPAs in areas beyond national jurisdiction (OSPAR Commission, 2021).

The North-East Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC) manages fisheries and ensures sustainable fishing practices in the North-East Atlantic. To overcome this regulatory fragmentation between management bodies, OSPAR and NEAFC have established a Collective Arrangement. It ensures coordination and cooperation in establishing area-based measures in ABNJ, promoting the exchange of information and ensuring that suitable measures for the conservation and management of these areas are implemented. However, the legal competence of the arrangement between OSPAR and the NEAFC does not cover other human activities which might affect protected sites. Therefore, the two parties decided to widen their agreement for *ad hoc* participation of other competent organisations and bodies, such as the International Maritime Organization (IMO) and International Seabed Authority (ISA), to ensure a multilateral dialogue on management measures for specific areas.

The Collective Arrangement model in the North-East Atlantic established between a Regional Fisheries Management Organisation (RFMO) and Regional Seas Convention has received increased attention, not least in the light of the recent BBNJ (biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction) negotiations. The complementary institutional cooperation on a regional level provides for a more integrated approach and has the potential to advance and supplement the international governance system. However, the cooperation between OSPAR and NEAFC relies on a set of contextual elements, such as overlapping geographical mandates that might have facilitated their institutional cooperation. It has been argued that a collective arrangement model might face challenges in other sea regions, where, for instance, the RSOs do not extend into ABNJ or where no RSO has been established, e.g., the Central Arctic Ocean (Heij, 2022).

Figure 4 OSPAR in the ABNJ. From OSPAR, 2021.

European regional governance in the Atlantic

Strategic direction

Europe's regional seas are shared by a myriad of individuals, institutions, cultures, and activities (European Environment Agency., 2015), who depend on them for transport, energy, food, income, and leisure activities, as well as for the often less recognised life support functions such as climate regulation (European Commission, 2020).

The EU's targets for marine protection are harmonised with the CBD and aligns with the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals. Goal 14 'Life below water' (Figure 5). Aligned with international aspirations the EU adopted the European Green Deal (EGD) in 2019. The EGD sets the overarching strategic direction for Europe, and several key strategies directly stem from this.

Figure 5 outlines how the EGD encompasses a range of the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals, emphasising the broad mandate of the EGD. As the EU's new growth strategy, the EGD aims to transform the Union into a climate-neutral society while leaving no one behind and creating an economy where economic growth is decoupled from resource use. The vision and objectives of the EGD is represented in Figure 6.

Figure 5 The European Commission Priorities associated with the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals. From (Directorate-General for Communication, n.d.)

Figure 6 The European Green Deal. From(Pjs et al., 2019).

The EGD comprises a set of policy initiatives designed to enable the transition to climate neutrality in the EU by 2050. An interim target has been set to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. As part of these policy initiatives, the Green Deal aims to protect, conserve, and enhance the EU's natural capital. Mission Ocean supports this Green Deal aim. The percentage targets for area-based conservation in the EU are aimed to be achieved at the level of biogeographical or marine regions, reflecting the different capacities of member states to

implement protection measures

Figure 7 Overview of the different European Green Deal strategies and plans with their related objectives (non-exhaustive). From CrossGov, 2024.

EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030

In 2020, the European Commission published a communication on the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, which is a central part of the EU's new growth strategy, the European Green Deal. The strategy aims to put Europe's biodiversity on the path to recovery by 2030 and sets out targets and commitments under strategies as shown in Figure 7 (European Commission, 2020).

The EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 laid the foundation for the EU's contribution to the international CBD negotiations. Under the Kunming-Montreal Biodiversity Framework, the global community has pledged to ensure that 30% of degraded terrestrial, inland water, and coastal and marine areas are under effective restoration by 2030 (Target 2) as well as to *“ensure and enable that by 2030 at least 30 per cent of terrestrial, inland water, and of coastal and marine areas, especially areas of particular importance for biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services, are effectively conserved and managed through ecologically representative, well-connected and equitably governed systems of protected areas and other effective area-based conservation measures”* (Target 3) (COP15, 2022). It is further emphasised that indigenous and traditionally managed areas shall be considered, and that sustainable use of the oceans shall not conflict with the conservation outcomes.

The EU Biodiversity Strategy is a political commitment and not directly legally binding. However, it proposes the establishment of a legally binding nature restoration law. The implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy can be described as cooperation-based, setting out roadmaps as well as monitoring and reporting mechanisms that put responsibility on different national governmental and sectoral authorities (Hallosserie & Chabason, 2023)

As part of the targets, the communication calls for 30% of the sea to be protected and at least 10% of EU seas to be strictly protected. The EU Commission's guidance document outlining criteria and guidance for the designation of protected areas according to the EU Biodiversity Strategy (Dinerstein et al., 2019) promotes increased harmonisation of reporting standards and assessment criteria; however, various national and international interpretations of what constitutes a MPA remain. The guidance document sets out non-binding assessment criteria to help countries reach their political commitment to implementing the Biodiversity Strategy (Dinerstein et al., 2019).

Legal framework

In response to the environmental challenges and human activities influencing Europe's seas, the EU has developed an extensive policy framework that seeks to manage and address these challenges and activities. The EU has a complex policy landscape associated with nature protection rules, specifically MPAs, and restoration, with over 200 pieces of legislation affecting marine environmental policy and management (Boyes & Elliott, 2014; European Environment Agency., 2015). This policy framework is aimed at the sustainable use of marine resources and the protection of marine biodiversity.

The evolutionary path of EU legislation has evolved from sectoral to framework directives, resulting in implementation through a large body of environmental legislation. Policy has been developed to monitor, conserve, and protect the marine environment. Sectoral directives have been superseded or subsumed into holistic or framework directives or those with a wider geographical remit, and the newer directives tend to have objectives that are not necessarily bound to national authorities but apply to all uses and users of a marine area, which brings in regional sea management and protection. This represents a holistic whole system approach, moving towards an ecosystem approach aligned with the CBD.

Given the evolutionary nature of EU legislation a natural tension between sectoral obligations required by the EGD through EU Directives such as achieving net zero, MPA targets and advancing the blue economy (see Figure 7). In the maritime context this tension is apparent in the interaction between EU Directives such as MSFD, MSPD and Natura 2000 Directives. Optimising decision making across the EU

Directives with respect to marine conservation will be strengthened by the new Nature Restoration Law. There is still a risk to marine conservation governance depending on the prioritisation between EGD objectives. The intent from the EU is to strive for a more holistic integrated approach. For example, the European Commission's communications on international ocean governance in 2016 and, more recently, the 'strengthening the international ocean governance framework' policy pillar in 2022 support the move to a more integrated approach (Decade Coordination Unit (IOC UNESCO), 2024; *International Ocean Governance - European Commission*, 2024). In 2022, a report on MPAs in Europe's seas made recommendations about how to advance EU MPAs. These recommendations identified the need for a more integrated approach for MPAs and Restoration projects. Their recommendations below are consistent with the observations made in this report.

- Europe needs to implement a modern, holistic approach to MPA design, management, and evaluation if EU MPA networks are to reach their potential in protecting marine biodiversity.
- The ecosystem-based approach introduced by the MSFD, and the CFP provides an opportunity to employ a holistic approach to designing and managing MPA networks in Europe's seas.
- Only comprehensively managed MPAs and MPA networks can help accomplish the visions and objectives of existing EU policies and legislation, i.e., halting biodiversity loss (European Environment Agency., 2015).

The key EU Directives are summarised below.

Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) – Directive 2008/56/EC enshrines in a legislative framework to promote an ecosystem-based approach for the management of human activities having an impact on the marine environment and recognises the importance of biodiversity and ecosystem functioning. The MSFD establishes the legal framework for determining a baseline of knowledge across Member States, with 2010/477/EU recognising that the initial assessment is the main process for identifying the essential features and characteristics as well as the predominant pressures and impacts on the marine environment, subject to its regular updates and to monitoring programmes (European Commission, 2010). It lists eleven Descriptors of Good Environmental Status, with Descriptor 1 prescribing that biodiversity is maintained, while Descriptors 2-11 consider a series of impacts arising from human activities and require that they do not cause significant harm to ecosystem functioning, according to the Directive.

The MSFD, specifically in Article 13(4), mandates that programmes of measures shall include spatial protection measures, which contribute to the establishment of a representative network of marine protected areas. These can be designated through nature directives or national frameworks (Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 Establishing a Framework for Community Action in the Field of Marine Environmental Policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive), 2008). Each Member State must prepare and implement a marine strategy for its marine waters in cooperation with other Member States sharing the same marine region or subregion. They must review and update this strategy every six years (European Commission, n.d.-b).

Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) – Is in response to the high and rapidly increasing demand for ocean space for different purposes (spatial squeeze). Maritime or Marine Spatial Planning is commonly defined as “a process of public authorities of analysing and allocating the spatial and temporal distribution of human activities in marine areas and space to achieve ecological, economic and social objectives”.

MSP is the key instrument guiding the implementation of the EU's overarching Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP) (Paramana et al., 2023). The IMP aspires to have a holistic approach to marine issues and ensure coordination between various policy areas in order to achieve the best use of marine spaces and promote economic development (Pharos4MPAs, 2020) (Soukissian et al., 2023).

Member States are supported, through the directive, in producing national plans for their waters (e.g. via an expert group that provides advice, and in cross-border cooperation), which should include spatial

uses of the marine environment and must be renewed at least every 10 years (Soukissian et al., 2023). This includes the European Commission's 'Blue Growth' strategy (adopted on 23 July 2014) to support sustainable development in five key areas (aquaculture, coastal tourism, marine biotechnologies, marine energies, and marine mining) (Pharos4MPAs, 2020).

Nature Restoration Law – In 2022, the European Commission proposed a new Nature Restoration Law aiming to restore ecosystems as a key component of the Biodiversity Strategy. The Law intends to complement existing environmental policies, such as the Birds and Habitats Directives, the Water Framework Directive, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Invasive Alien Species Regulation, and the Common Fisheries Policy.

On 17 June 2024, the European Council formally adopted the Nature Restoration Law. The regulation explicitly targets the restoration of nature in Europe with the overall target to repair the 80 % of European habitats that are in poor condition and to bring back nature to all ecosystems, from forest and agricultural land to marine, freshwater and urban ecosystems (Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on Nature Restoration, 2022). The Nature Restoration Law will set legally binding targets for nature restoration in different ecosystems that will apply to every Member State, complementing existing laws. The aim is to cover at least 20 % of the EU's land and sea areas by 2030 with nature restoration measures and eventually extend these to all ecosystems in need of restoration by 2050.

Article 5 of the regulation concerns the restoration of marine ecosystems and is of relevance to the Atlantic Lighthouse Area. The text is designed to build on the Habitats Directive and specifies that:

- Member States will put restoration measures in place for 30% of specified coastal and marine habitats that are currently not in good condition by 2030, for at least 60% by 2040, and 90% by 2050.
- Member States will aim to put in place within Natura 2000 restoration measures for marine habitats of specified species
- Restoration measures will consider the need for improved connectivity

Article 14 of the regulation specifies that Member States will prepare national restoration plans and carry out the preparatory monitoring and research needed to identify the restoration measures that are necessary to contribute to the Union targets.

Natura 2000 directives (the Birds and Habitats Directives) – Natura 2000 is a network of protected areas covering Europe's most valuable and threatened species and habitats. It is the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world, extending across all 27 EU Member States, both on land and at sea. The sites within Natura 2000 are designated under the Birds and the Habitats Directives. Additionally, the Natura 2000 directives (the Birds and Habitats Directives) cover many features within Special Areas of Conservation and Special Protected Areas, meaning that all activities, plans, and projects within and adjacent to these designated areas must be considered.

Overlapping legislation

In addition to the key legislation, it needs to be recognised that there is a raft of overlapping legislation which cover both:

- **Integrated coastal management:** Reflecting on the need to account for integrated coastal management and taking a Mountains to Sea (Source to Sea) management approach recognising marine conservation can be affected from terrestrial and river basin inputs. Examples of the overlapping nature of directives include the Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive, which focuses on larger areas and aims to consider cumulative effects includes:
 - **The Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive:** which focuses on larger areas and aims to consider cumulative effects.
 - **Water Framework Directive:** The Water Framework Directive takes a comprehensive approach to water environmental protection and regulation in aiming to achieve 'good ecological statuses of all waters in the EU including lakes, rivers, groundwaters and coastal waters. Under the Water Framework Directive, Member States are required to develop River Basin Management Plans to set out how they will achieve these objectives.
 - **The Floods Directive and Nitrate Directive:** The reality is that this legislation is focussed on the terrestrial habitats however the effect on the coastal zone is encompassed in the Water Framework Directive.
- **Sectoral legislation:**
 - **Integrated Maritime Policy (IMP):** Introduced by the European Commission in 2007. Its aim is to ensure that sea-related policies are developed in a joined-up way in order to allow the extraction of value from the sea and, at the same time, address the cumulated effect of conflicts of use and the deterioration of the marine environment (Commission of the European Communities, 2007). It recognised that compartmentalised policy development and decision-making were no longer adequate and that action under the different sectoral policies must develop in a coherent policy framework. As stated in the document, *"the Commission's vision is for an integrated maritime policy that covers all aspects of our relationship with the oceans and seas. This innovative and holistic approach will provide a coherent policy framework that will allow for the optimal development of all sea-related activities in a sustainable manner."*
 - **Common Fisheries Policy:** The CFP is a set of rules for sustainably managing European fishing fleets and conserving fish stock.
 - **EU Action Plan:** Protecting and restoring marine ecosystems for sustainable and resilient fisheries. This Action Plan seeks to identify how fisheries management can contribute to more effective protection and restoration of their marine biodiversity, thereby contributing to achieving the objectives of the Nature Restoration law (Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, 2024). Significantly, the Action Plan highlights the Commission's calls on the Member States to make full use of the CFP tools available and to phase out mobile bottom fishing in all MPAs by 2030 at the latest. (European Court of Auditors, 2020a)

- **1.** To comply with the MSFD and the BHDs, Member States adopt national laws restricting fishing in protected areas to its vessels ...
- 2.** ... but the CFP gives a Member State the right to fish in another Member State's waters. The restrictions adopted by national laws do not apply automatically to these foreign vessels so they can fish where national fishermen cannot.

Figure 8 Identifying the disconnection between MPAs and the extent of protection for MPAs outside coastal zones and the legal protection. From European Court of Auditors, 2020.

		Fisheries	Environment
12 nautical miles (nm) 100 nm in Macaronesia ^(a)	Territorial waters	Member States ^(b) European Union ^(c)	Coastal Member States
12-200 nm 100-200 nm in Macaronesia	Declared EEZs	European Union	Coastal Member States
Other areas ^(d)	Areas beyond EEZs	RFMOs ^(e)	RSCs and RFMOs (if international waters) Member States (if sovereign)

^(a) This rule applies to all EU outermost regions.

^(b) Member States regulate access of fishing vessels to these waters under a temporary exception

^(c) The CFP gives competences to the EU all over EU waters

^(d) CFP rules apply to EU vessels and EU nationals in international waters

^(e) The GFCM is competent for territorial, EEZ and international waters in the Mediterranean and Black seas

Figure 9 Responsibilities for environmental and fisheries policies. From European Court of Auditors, 2020.

Table 3 EU policy landscape to support the European Green Deal specifically relevant to MPA, biodiversity, and restoration (Mission objectives). Adapted from CrossGov, 2024.

Legal instrument	Objective	Focus	Type	Responsible Legal institution	Year
Birds Directive	Conserve all wild bird species in the EU.	Conservation	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	1981 (revised in 2009)
Common Fisheries Policy	Ensure long-term sustainable fisheries and aquaculture, the availability of food supplies and a fair standard of living for fisheries and aquaculture communities	Cross-cutting	Regulation	DG MARE EFCA EFSA	2013
Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive	Enhance sustainability reporting for better financial market decisions	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG FISMA	2023
Environmental Impact Assessment Directive	Account for environmental effects in project planning at the earliest stage	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2015
Environmental Quality Standards Directive	Achieve good surface water chemical status.	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2010
EU Action Plan on fisheries	Protect and restore marine ecosystems and achieve good environmental status; ensure sustainable fishing resource use.	Fisheries	Communication	DG ENV	2023
Floods Directive	Establish a framework for the assessment and management of flood risks aiming at the reduction of their adverse consequences.	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2021
Habitats Directive	Conserve natural habitats and wild fauna and flora in the EU both on land and sea habitats.	Conservation	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	1992
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	Achieve good environmental status (GES) in the marine environment as well as sustainable use and coherence with other EU law.	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2008
Maritime Spatial Planning Directive	Establish a framework for maritime spatial planning aimed at promoting the sustainable maritime economies and resource use	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2014
Proposed Nature Restoration Law	To restore degraded ecosystems; achieve the EU's climate mitigation and adaptation objectives; meet the EU international commitments.	Biodiversity	Proposal	DG ENV MS Reg. Authorities EEA	2022 (adapted)
Proposed Revision of the REPowerEU Directive	Achieve climate targets by 2030 and climate neutrality by 2050 through the increase of renewable energy; contribute to the European economy and to achieve climate and environmental objectives.	Energy	Proposal	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2023
Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive	To integrate environmental considerations into the preparation and adoption of plans and programmes.	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2001
Water Framework Directive	To establish a framework and substantive environmental obligations for the protection of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters and groundwaters.	Cross-cutting	Directive	DG ENV MS Reg. authorities	2000

Legal institutions

The comprehensive codified legal framework of the European Union is implemented by a range of competent European Union authorities. Table 3 outlines the key responsible legal institutions that are responsible for implementing primary and secondary legislation. A summary of key legal institutions associated with marine conservation is found in Table 3:

- **Directorate-General Environment (DG ENV):** The Directorate-General for Environment develops and carries out the Commission's policies on the Environment. It proposes and implements policies that ensure a high level of environmental protection and preserve the quality of life of EU citizens. Responsibilities include, but are not limited to:
 - Marine and coastal environment – EU Action to protect Europe's coasts, seas and oceans
 - Nature and biodiversity – EU action on environmental conservation and protection
 - EU action on water issues to protect water resources
- **Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE):** The Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries develops and carries out the Commission's policies on Maritime affairs and fisheries. The Directorate-General works to:
 - ensure that the ocean resources are used sustainably and that coastal communities and the fishing sector have a prosperous future
 - promote maritime policies and stimulate a sustainable blue economy
 - promote ocean governance at the international level
- **The European Environment Agency (EEA):** EEA is an agency of the European Union that delivers knowledge and data to support Europe's environment and climate goals. The EEA's core tasks are defined in the founding EU regulation and include:
 - supporting policy development and key global processes
 - offering analytical expertise
 - providing and maintaining an efficient reporting infrastructure for national and international data flows
- **EU International Ocean Governance Forum (IOG Forum):** Established in 2020 this platform was established primarily as an online engagement tool for experts and stakeholders from Europe and beyond (Dodgshun et al., 2021). Significantly, some of the IOG priorities are:
 - *"Initiate and lead the development of a global "one ocean conservation strategy" to identify, designate and establish networks of well-managed Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in support of the proposed target of protecting at least 30% of the ocean by 2030 (with 10% under strict protection)"*(Dodgshun et al., 2021)
 - Enhance efforts for ecological restoration of degraded marine and coastal habitats in support of the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration and global conservation targets
 - Strengthen holistic governance approaches to implement cross-sectoral and ecosystem-based management in pursuit of the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the Paris Agreement, the future post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework of the CBD, and other relevant processes (Dodgshun et al., 2021).

Implementation of strategic direction

The EU institutions implement the strategic direction and legal obligations as specified by EU legislation. The EEA is the statutory body responsible for maintaining an inventory of publicly available datasets for nationally designated protected areas.²

The tools developed for the data collation, data sharing and reporting are provided for in EU directives, for example Directive 2007/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council adopted on 14 March 2007 aims at establishing an Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE) for environmental policies, or policies and activities that have an impact on the environment (Joint Research Centre, European Commission, 2024). Furthermore, it sets the generic rules for building infrastructures and reference data sets. Notably, the working definition of a protected site for INSPIRE is an "Area designated or managed within a framework of international, Community and Member States' legislation to achieve specific conservation objectives" (Joint Research Centre, European Commission, 2024) (see Figure 10). Significantly, the EU is currently seeking to evolve INSPIRE as the public sector contribution to the emerging European data spaces, particularly the Green Deal data space.

Figure 10 Relationship between INSPIRE Implementing Rules and Technical Guidelines. From European Commission, n.d.

Consistent with INSPIRE, the key tools developed for implementing the strategic direction are:

- **European Nature Information System, EUNIS³:** The EUNIS database and system form the knowledge base for implementing the Biodiversity Strategy 2030. EUNIS is the reference information system to supporting the Natura process and environmental reporting connected to EEA, data is sourced from Natura 2000 data - the European network of protected sites, nationally designated areas (protected areas) (CDDA), and the European Nature Diploma Areas (Council of Europe). EUNIS represents the European member states' official source of protected area information and is used to contribute to the World Database of Protect Areas (WDPA)⁴ (European Environment Agency, 2024).

² Two versions of the public dataset are provided. The full dataset includes the entire geographical coverage including nationally designated areas in overseas entities ([Nationally designated areas \(europa.eu\)](https://nationallydesignatedareas.europa.eu/))

³ <https://eunis.eea.europa.eu/>

⁴ [Explore the World's Protected Areas \(protectedplanet.net\)](https://www.protectedplanet.net/)

- **European Environment Agency's Common Database on Designated Areas (CDDA)⁵:** The CDDA is the official source of designated protected area information from European countries to the World Database of Protected Areas, maintained. It is also used to inform EUNIS.(European Environment Agency, 2023)
- **European Environment Information and Observation Network (Eionet Portal)⁶:** is a partnership network of the European Environment Agency (EEA) and its 38 member and cooperating countries. EEA and Eionet gather and develop data, knowledge, and advice to policymakers about Europe's environment.
- **The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)⁷:** Service of DG MARE playing a pivotal role as a trusted source of in situ marine environmental and human activities data and data products. EMODnet creates an international marine data network providing open access to ocean data and products and links global and national databases. Within EMODnet, protected areas are incorporated as a layer of human activities.

There is no legal obligation to submit data to either Eionet or EMODnet. These databases are publicly accessible and made available for use by stakeholders as appropriate.

The EEA uses available data that is obtained across a range of databases to enable the production of summary statistics and the development of reporting dashboards⁸ and progress trackers⁹. This is facilitated by Directives that establish reporting frameworks applicable to all EU Member States.

Despite the plethora of technology and tools, use both at a national and international scale, including a wealth of different databases and online platforms data is often scattered across various institutions and databases, making it difficult to access and integrate.

There remains an absence of an established centralised assessment/performance criteria or an integrated platform that provides for an assessment of the effectiveness of ocean protection. The European Environment Agency., 2015b report recommended that EU Member States should consider setting relevant European criteria to evaluate the effectiveness of MPAs and their benefits through large-scale testing on existing regional networks of MPAs. This is in spite of the use of centralised dashboards due to concern is that the data being used to inform is not consistent between Member States.

A review of EU reporting systems such as Wise Marine (Marine Information System for Europe), Biodiversity Information System for Europe and the European Environment Agency Datahub, as well as international databases such as the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA), World Database on OECMs, Global Database on Protected Area Management Effectiveness (GD-PAME), demonstrated that restoration projects and the biodiversity trends associated with these projects is not incorporated. We were therefore unable to determine performance of restoration projects at a regional level. Even the MSFD reporting on Good Environmental Status doesn't include a category or assessment metric for restoration projects. For reporting to the EU broad reporting classifications can be used by Member States leading to inconsistencies between what constitutes MPA reporting from each Member State.

There is no standardised lexicon used resulting in variability between both Member States at an EU level as well as differences between regional bodies such at the EU and OSPAR. This undermines the ability to compare reporting. The baseline study identified that whilst governance frameworks are in place the common thread is that there is a lack of integrated assessment of the performance of these MPAs / restoration projects. The study by the European Environment Agency identified the need for consistent evaluation of the effectiveness of MPAs in protecting biodiversity, an approach that could be adopted for both MPAs and restoration projects (European Environment Agency., 2015).

⁵ [CDDA dataset — European Environment Agency \(europa.eu\)](https://eionet.europa.eu/cdda)

⁶ www.eionet.europa.eu

⁷ www.emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en

⁸ [EU Biodiversity Strategy Dashboard \(europa.eu\)](https://eionet.europa.eu/biodiversity)

⁹ [EU Biodiversity Strategy Actions Tracker \(europa.eu\)](https://eionet.europa.eu/biodiversity)

Table 4 demonstrates the variability in protected area reporting categories between EU Member States when Member State MPAs classifications are compared using the IUCN protected area classifications. The table highlights Member States can include nationally designated protected areas and Natura 2000 sites results in a range of classifications that are all contributing to the % indicator metric.

Table 4 Marine Protected Areas in the Atlantic Lighthouse area according to IUCN protected area management categories and proportion of national marine waters (EEZ) under strict protection. From European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2023.¹⁰

	Portugal	Spain	France	Ireland
Jurisdiction in the Atlantic area (km2) (EEZ+TS+IW*)	1795230	867336	264096	465060
Marine Protected areas (km2)	248524	1168	13281	179
Number of designated sites	63	63	37	48
IUCN Category of Protected Area				
Ia (km2): strict nature reserve	196	0	0	53
Ib (km2): wilderness area	5293	371	0	0
II (km2): national park	0	78	0.44	0
III (km2): natural monument or feature	0	1	496	0
IV (km2): habitat/species management area	106439	113	12785	122
V (km2): protected landscape or seascape	417	114	0	0
VI (km2): protected areas with sustainable use of natural resources	136178	46	0	0
Not assigned (km2)	0	446	0	0
*Strictly protected areas (Ia and Ib) (km2)	5489	371	0	53
Strictly protected areas (% EEZ/jurisdiction)	0.3	0	0	0

* In the absence of a definition for strict protection, the IUCN protected area management categories of Ia and Ib have been used as a proxy for strict protection.

The modes for revision of databases varies also significantly. For example, nationally designated protected areas are updated by Eionet partnership countries annually using spatial and tabular files. In contrast the Natura 2000 MPAs are updated by a separate European database of Natura 2000 sites. There is an apparent misalignment with reporting frameworks between different Directives both in terms of the reporting timeframes and frequency. The risk being numerous figures can be presented in official documents and can create uncertainty about what reported figures are the correct ones. This is exacerbated by observations about unstandardised reporting, and systems as described above.

The EEA identifies that related to the points raised above there are issues with data availability and data sharing agreements for the following potential operational criteria that could be used to assess performance (European Environment Agency, 2015). The two EEA observations below are symptomatic of the risks created as a result of lack of standardised reporting:

1. **No-take (no fishing) areas – Strict protection areas:** It is not possible to quantitatively assess whether EU MPAs are no-take areas or not, as no harmonised, easily accessible data are available.
2. **Enforcement effectiveness:** Data being provided by States to EMODNET shows that the data fields being collected and reported are not calibrated to determine effectiveness. This applies to the effectiveness of the MPA from an ecological restoration perspective and the effectiveness of monitoring, control and surveillance of an MPA.

¹⁰ The data used in this table is taken from the European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2023a. The data has originally been sourced from the EEA's Common Database on Designated Areas (CDDA) containing data from 2021. Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ), Territorial Seas (TS), and Internal Waters (IW) surfaces were extracted from the marineregions.org website and cross-checked with national data available from institutional websites.

Status

Despite existing policies designed to protect the marine environment, such as the MSFD and the Habitats Directive, it is acknowledged that Europe's marine ecosystems are degraded with a high proportion of marine species and habitat assessments continuing to show an 'unfavourable conservation status' or a status that is 'unknown'. Ongoing pressures on the marine environment include changes in sea use, overexploitation, pollution, invasive alien species and the effects of climate change.

While there are successful examples of management measures targeting individual marine species and habitats leading to improvements in their condition in some EU marine regions, this success is fragmented and does not offset the combined effects of multiple pressures from human activities across all of Europe's seas. Solutions for halting marine biodiversity loss and starting to restore ecosystem resilience are available but require implementation (European Environment Agency, 2019).

Figure 11 Marine protected area coverage in the EU, 2012–2021. From European Environment Agency, 2024a, pp. 2012–2021

Figure 13 Marine protected area coverage in EU Member States in 2021. From European Environment Agency, 2024a

target 2 is to protect at least 10 % of the EU's Sea area strictly. provides an overview of how much of each country's marine waters are classified as being strictly protected in the Atlantic Lighthouse area, according to the IUCN categorisation for protected areas. The status is that there is very little sea area currently under strict protection in any of the countries. Portugal has strict protection for the highest portion of its EEZ at 0.3%. However, overall, all the countries remain significantly below the 10% strict sea protection required to meet the target.

An overview of the current status of EU marine ecosystem protection is presented in Figure 11 and Figure. Of the four Atlantic countries within BlueMissionAA, Portugal has designated the highest portion of its EEZ as Marine Protected Areas, at 13.84%, while less than 1% of Spain and Ireland's EEZs are categorised as protected. With reference to Mission target 1, the current status is that each of the countries remain significantly below the 30% of EU sea area protection required to meet the target. Mission

Figure 12 EU Biodiversity Strategy Dashboard map on Marine protected area coverage values at national level. From Joint Research Centre, 2023

Table 5 Marine Protected Area coverage in the Atlantic Lighthouse area. From (European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2023).¹¹

Country	Jurisdiction in the Atlantic area (km2) (EEZ+TS+IW*)	Number of designated protected sites	Marine Protected Areas (km2)	Marine Protected areas (% Jurisdiction)
Portugal	1,795,230	63	248,524	13.84
Spain	867,336	63	1,168	0.13
France	264,096	37	13,281	5.03
Ireland	465,060	48	179	0.04

* EEZ= Exclusive Economic Zone; TS= Territorial Sea; IW= Internal Waters

Monitoring performance

Performance is monitored in terms of the percentage coverage aligned with the specified Mission Objective targets. The EU's monitoring report on progress towards the SDGs shows that the EU is making progress with regards to % coverage from MPAs and between 2012 – 2019 increased MPA coverage from 216 742 km² to 552 008 km² (*Sustainable Development in the European Union — Monitoring Report on Progress towards the SDGs in an EU Context (2022 Edition)*, n.d.). Data published in March 2023 by the EEA showed MPA coverage has more than doubled between 2012 and 2021 to 12.1%. Table 5 provides a comparison between the EU Member States that are within the geographic scope of this study.

EU Member States are expected to review their national protection status and pledges and report these to the Commission. Monitoring both the EU's and Member States' progress towards achieving the specified % coverage is complicated by the nature of reporting between Member States. There is an apparent heterogeneity between how Member States are classifying and reporting MPAs/restoration sites to the EU and subsequently to the WDPA. Data is sourced from Nature 2000 data, the CDDA and the European Nature Diploma Areas¹². One example of this lack of harmonisation is the way the Commission has incorporated OECMS. OECMs are only considered eligible for progress toward the Biodiversity Strategy if minimum criteria for national protection sites are applied (long term; specified conservation objectives and measures; management effectiveness).

The inconsistent use and reporting of OECMS is recognised and work is underway to mitigate this. For example, the IUCN published voluntary guidelines for the recognition of OECMs in 2018, and the European Environment Agency commissioned a scoping report on the potential of OECMs in the EU (Cristina Lázaro, Nigel Dudley, Harry Jonas, Edward Lewis, 2021). To date, there is no overview at the EU level on the sum of protection measures, including MPAs (Natura 2000 and nationally designated) and OECMs.

The EU Blue Parks Community (EU BPC) identified that the strategic direction set at an international level to protect 30% of the oceans needs protection that is both designed and managed effectively (EU Blue Parks Initiative, 2024a). Monitoring of the % coverage masks the questions of performance in terms of effectiveness. A point supported by the assessment that identified that out of the 6000 European MPAs many are still considered 'paper parks' (EU Blue Parks Initiative, 2024b).

¹¹ The data used in this table is taken from (European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation., 2023). The data has originally been sourced from the EEA's Common Database on Designated Areas (CDDA) containing data from 2021. The data includes: France –excluding Mediterranean and outermost territories; Ireland; Portugal – including the Azores; Spain – including Macaronesia and excluding Mediterranean waters. Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ), Territorial Seas (TS), and Internal Waters (IW) surfaces were extracted from the marineregions.org website and cross-checked with national data available from institutional websites.

¹² [Natura 2000 data - the European network of protected sites, nationally designated areas \(protected areas\) \(CDDA\)](#), and the [European Nature Diploma Areas \(Council of Europe\)](#).

This raises the question of whether the current monitoring framework meets all aspects of the mission objective statements. This is a concern supported by the scientific literature that has identified challenges of using percentage targets and made the assertion that this performance metric does not necessarily equate to performance (Zabala et al., 2024). Zabala et al. (2024) identified that “Achieving quantitative targets of protection will not be sufficient to conserve the world’s biodiversity”. The observation is that despite increases in conservation area coverage, there remains an attrition of biodiversity and thereby asserts that the success of conservation areas to save biodiversity is debatable.

Figure 14 EU Member States within the scope of the research project. From Eurostat, 2024)

Member States are required to report on the effectiveness of management with the EU legal framework providing guidance on how to assess effectiveness; for example, The Natura 2000 guidance provides an overview of conservation objectives and conservation measures that can be applied more generally to MPAs. Determining performance by assessing the effectiveness of the implementation of the conservation objectives and measures includes an assessment of existing management plans that contain monitoring and review mechanisms. While the EU provides guidance, there are difficulties associated with determining effectiveness, which can be related to the fact that not all MPAs have established management plans. Management plans are recognised as good practice, but EU legislation does not legally require them (European Court of Auditors, 2020b).

When reviewed at a local level, it has been observed that no assessment of how effective management plans have been at meeting the conservation objectives of each MPA is provided to the EU. An observation supported by the European Court of Auditors concludes the concern of EU MPA performance (European Court of Auditors, 2020b):

“Our assessment of the role of MPAs is in line with the European Environment Agency, which identified a lack of an effective, well-managed and well-connected network of MPAs. As a result, they provided limited protection of marine biodiversity.”

The 2022 Eurostat Monitoring report on progress towards the SDGs in an EU context report supports these observations, stating: “Although a positive development, growth in the extent of protected areas alone does not provide a good indication of how well species and habitats are being protected. In fact, the EU currently has no overview or assessment of how effective the management plans associated with designated MPAs in EU regional seas are.” (Eurostat, 2022).

The EU States whose marine governance systems were reviewed as part of this project have shown a common recognition of the need for blue finance. Their strategic documents acknowledge the need for funding mechanisms, such as the French strategic document, which states consolidation of funding for marine protection is an objective. It has also been observed among EU States that there is insufficient funding to sustain the management of MPAs (see section 6 for details).

Arctic regional governance

The Arctic area within BlueMissionAA falls outside the jurisdiction of the European Union, but there are strong mutual relationships, particularly in the field of environmental governance. The EU's 2021 Joint Communication, titled 'A Stronger EU Engagement for a Peaceful, Sustainable, and Prosperous Arctic', outlines close relationships with the Arctic region and describes the EU's policy directions. While geopolitical concerns and economic interests play a role, climate change and sustainable development are key dimensions of the EU's Arctic policy. The EU actively promotes biodiversity conservation, climate action, and Indigenous Peoples' rights. As an observer to the Arctic Council, the EU has become an influential actor in the Arctic region. EU funding initiatives and research frameworks are another important dimension of the EU's engagement in the Arctic, including the EU Mission Ocean (European Union External Action, 2024). As the EU Commissioner for Environment, Oceans and Fisheries Virginijus Sinkevičius expressed following the adoption of the new EU Arctic Communication, "*the EU is in the Arctic*" (European Union External Action, 2021).

The Arctic Council is the most important regional institution in the Arctic that is relevant to area-based marine protection and restoration and is therefore described in detail below. Beyond the Arctic Council, other regional forums and arrangements influence Arctic marine area-based governance and biodiversity conservation. To delineate the scope of this report and avoid duplication of existing publications, these are not presented in detail¹³. In addition to the OSPAR Convention, which focuses on protecting the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic (described in the OSPAR section above), these include the Nordic Council and the Nordic Council of Ministers, which address a broad range of environmental and sustainability issues among Nordic countries. Additionally, the Barents Euro-Arctic Council (BEAC) emphasises intergovernmental cooperation on environmental and economic matters in the Barents Region. International conventions and agreements also influence marine governance in the Arctic. Compared to other regions, the designation of Ramsar sites (Convention on Wetlands of International Importance) is underrepresented in the Arctic. In addition, species-dependent conventions and commissions such as NAMMCO (North Atlantic Marine Mammal Commission) propose management measures to be taken by its member countries (Wienrich & Lukyanova, 2022).

These institutions, while varying in scope and influence, collectively enhance the governance and cooperative efforts essential for the sustainable management and protection of the Arctic marine environment.

Arctic Council

Legal framework

The Arctic Council is the prominent high-level intergovernmental forum in the Arctic Region that promotes cooperation and interaction among the Arctic States and Indigenous Peoples of the Arctic. Established in 1998, its members include the eight Arctic states with territory within the Arctic region (Canada, The Kingdom of Denmark (including Greenland and the Faroe Islands), Finland, Iceland, Norway, The Russian Federation, Sweden, and the United States). To ensure the active participation of the Indigenous Peoples in the Arctic, the Arctic Council has the unique feature of according a permanent participant status to the six Indigenous Organizations. The Indigenous People's Secretariat facilitates their participation and gives them full consultation rights (Arctic Council, n.d.).

The concept of a 'global Arctic' has surfaced to emphasise the dynamic nature of the Arctic's boundaries, highlighting the interconnected environmental challenges that transcend territorial borders (Dodds, 2017). This is captured well in the common saying 'what happens in the arctic does not stay in the Arctic'. The repercussions of climate change in the Arctic, such as rising sea levels, thawing permafrost, and connections to the oceanic-atmospheric system, extend well beyond the Arctic region.

¹³ A detailed overview of regional governance arrangements in the Arctic relevant for marine conservation can be found in a study by the Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies (IASS) by Wienrich & Lukyanova (2022), available [here](#)

The influences on Arctic livelihoods, primarily instigated by non-Arctic states, are major contributors to these changes. To address such global environmental challenges, the Arctic Council has developed an extensive multilayer-membership system that includes non-state entities (Intergovernmental and Interparliamentary organizations as well as NGOs) and non-Arctic states as observers, providing valuable addition to the daily work of the Arctic Council's scientific assessments and monitoring. The work is structured into six thematic working groups and designated task forces that provide regular assessments and recommendations to the Arctic states and International Organizations. The working groups 'Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment' (PAME) and 'Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna' (CAFF) share the overarching responsibility for marine governance and biodiversity conservation in the Arctic. The European Union applied for an Observer status in the Arctic Council at the Kiruna Ministerial meeting in 2013, but the application was deferred due to geopolitically

Figure 15 The working groups of the Arctic Council. From AMAP, 2015.

different positions amongst the Arctic Council's member states. The EU may, however, observe the proceeding of the Arctic Council (Arctic Council, n.d.).

As an intergovernmental forum, the Arctic Council has no legal authority as found in international treaties or organisations and operates as a soft law body without regulatory competencies. The Arctic Council has however served as a venue for negotiating some legally binding agreements (oil-spill and search-and-rescue). In the field of marine protection, the Arctic Council has no regulatory competence and all area-based protection measures are established through national legislation (Arctic Council, n.d.).

Strategic direction

The ecosystem-based approach

Figure 16 The Ecosystem Approach. From Arctic Council Joint PAME, CAFF, AMAP, SDWG Ecosystem Approach Expert Group, 2019.

The notion of the Ecosystem Approach to Management (EAM) has existed for over three decades and is often used interchangeably with ecosystem-based management (EBM) or ecosystem approach (EA). In 2004, Arctic Council Ministers formally embraced the EA as a comprehensive principle within the Arctic Marine Strategic Plan to address the major challenges in the oceans (PAME, 2011). The updated Arctic Marine Strategic Plan from 2015 reiterates the principles of an Ecosystem Approach to Management (Arctic Council, 2015):

"Comprehensive, integrated management of human activities based on best available scientific and traditional knowledge about

the ecosystem and its dynamics, in order to identify and take action on influences that are critical to the

health of ecosystems, thereby achieving sustainable use of ecosystem goods and services and maintenance of ecosystem integrity" (Kiruna Declaration of the Arctic Council, 2013).

MPA Networks as Part of an Ecosystem Approach to Management

The overarching course of action for the Arctic Council is set by the Arctic Council's Strategic Plans (Arctic Council, 2021). The chairship of the Arctic Council is rotating between its eight members. The Norwegian chairship (2023 – 2025) has highlighted the oceans as one of four strategic focus areas, emphasising the role of an ecosystem approach to management, as well as increased cooperation for developing an Arctic network of MPAs and OECMs to conserve marine biodiversity (Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2023).

Figure 17 Marine protection as part of the ecosystem approach. From PAME, 2015.

A Framework for a pan-Arctic Marine Protected Area Network

The 2015 Framework for a Pan-Arctic Marine Protected Area Network was designed to promote the development of MPAs under an ecosystem-based approach, supporting and implementing the targets of the Convention on Biological Diversity (PAME, 2015). PAME's definition of a pan-Arctic network describes an ecologically representative connection of individual spatial measures. To provide flexibility in implementation, the framework sets out that both MPAs and OECMs should be considered eligible for the pan-Arctic network.

The framework further highlights that MPAs and OECMs should not be considered as isolated measures but integrated into the context of the wider seascape, emphasising the need for an ecosystem approach to management (see Figure 18).

Figure 18 EBSAs and areas of heightened ecological and cultural significance (AMSA IIC) in the Arctic. From CAFF and PAME, 2017.

Implementation

Identification of important biodiversity areas in the circumpolar Arctic

The CBD initiated a global process to identify 'ecologically or biologically significant areas' (EBSAs). Under the lead of the CAFF working group, 11 areas were identified. EBSAs are not MPAs, as they imply no direct human management implications but provide scientific basis under an ecosystem approach to management for marine spatial planning processes and the establishment of MPAs or OECMs. It should be noted that Russia was the only coastal state agreeing to define EBSAs within its national jurisdiction.

The EU Mission Ocean Arctic Lighthouse, covering only waters under national jurisdiction, is therefore not covered by any EBSA areas (AMAP/CAFF/SDWG, 2013).

A similar process has been undertaken across the Arctic with regard to shipping. The 2009 Arctic Marine Shipping Assessment recommended to identify areas of heightened ecological and cultural significance (AMSA IIC). Similar to EBSA, these are not a direct protection measure but provide the scientific baseline for implementing protection measures nationally or internationally. 98 areas of heightened ecological and cultural significance have been identified, whereof approximately 36% are located within protected areas (Barry et al., 2023). Internationally, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has set out criteria for the designation of Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas (PSSAs). Within PSSAs, the IMO can implement measures to reduce the impact of shipping (e.g. routing measures, stricter discharge requirements etc.) (IMO, n.d.). The criteria used for designating areas of heightened ecological significance are largely overlapping with the IMO's PSSA criteria. Despite similar assessment criteria, no PSSAs have been designated by the IMO in the Arctic. This could provide a potential leverage for reducing the impact of shipping on the Arctic marine environment. The Arctic Council has already played a significant role towards the adoption of the Polar Code, formally known as the International Code for Ships Operating in Polar Waters. Through collaboration and dialogue, the Arctic Council has provided a platform for member states to discuss and coordinate their efforts at the IMO. The Code regulates the challenges and risks posed by navigation in polar regions, aiming to enhance the safety of ships and the protection of the polar environment (Barry et al., 2023).

Status on progress towards area-based protection

Figure 19 Total number of strategic actions in Arctic Council working group documents referencing the strategic goals of the Arctic Marine Strategic Plan. From PAME, 2021.

Goal 1: Improve knowledge of the Arctic marine environment and continue to monitor and assess current and future impacts on Arctic marine ecosystems. Goal 2: Conserve and protect ecosystem function and marine biodiversity to enhance resilience and the provision of ecosystem services. Goal 3: Promote safe and sustainable use of the marine environment, considering cumulative environmental impacts. Goal 4: Enhance the economic, social, and cultural well-being of Arctic inhabitants, including Arctic indigenous peoples and strengthen their capacity to adapt to changes in the Arctic marine environment.

context (Arctic Council, 2015). Following the initial emphasis on delineating the concept for EBM/EA, the PAME working group is currently transitioning towards implementing this approach in the marine environment. The toolbox developed by PAME for area-based conservation measures and ecological connectivity provides a useful overview and guidance for the Arctic Council's member states (PAME, 2017).

The Arctic Marine Strategic Plan has been reviewed regularly to track the progress towards implementing the strategic goals through the activities of the Arctic Council's working groups. Whereas the strategic goal of improving the scientific knowledge and assessing future changes in the marine ecosystem is well anchored across the working groups, strategic goal 2 on the conservation and protection of marine ecosystems was by far the least referenced goal within their activities (PAME, 2021). This indicates that the Arctic Council has focused more on scientific assessments of marine ecosystems, while marine protection and conservation actions are still underrepresented.

The Arctic Marine Strategic Plan (2015-2025) includes the strategic priority of developing a pan-Arctic network of marine protected areas and encourages its member states to implement protection measures either nationally or through international organizations. The role of Areas of Heightened Ecological and Cultural Significance is highlighted in this

Figure 20 The MPAs in the Arctic. From CAFF & PAME, 2022

A common report by the CAFF and PAME working groups provides an update on the implementation of conservation measures in the Arctic and how they relate to international targets (CAFF & PAME, 2022). The database on protected areas retrieves information submitted by member states. Despite the recognition that OECMs can contribute to the goal of establishing a pan-Arctic network of protected areas, only MPAs were included in this assessment. Work under CAFF and PAME is underway to understand how the Arctic countries are using and understanding the criteria for the identification of an OECM.

The assessment concludes that 5.2% of the Arctic marine environment was under formal protection as of 2020, far from reaching the CBD Aichi target for 2020. The protection status within the areas varies according to national legislation. However, the Aichi target for terrestrial areas has been exceeded. Reaching the updated Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework marine target of the CBD in 2030, requires strongly increased effort (CAFF & PAME, 2022).

Due to the absence of a legal mandate for the Arctic Council, the implementation of a pan-Arctic protection network lies within the responsibilities of the individual Arctic coastal states. Different regulatory frameworks and policies for marine protection at the national level are thus a challenge to implementing the objectives (PAME, 2015). The role of the intergovernmental Arctic Council should therefore be regarded as a venue that can coordinate and promote national implementation of MPAs and OECMs through knowledge sharing and assessment standards.

Figure 21 Progress towards international protection targets in the circumpolar Arctic. From Barry et al., 2023.

6. Atlantic national governance baseline

Spain

The Spanish marine environment is experiencing a range of pressures, notably from “alteration and pollution of certain coastal zones, fishing, chemical pollution, physical alteration and the eutrophication of habitats and intensive urbanization of the coast” (European MSP Platform, 2024c).

The Spanish marine environment is divided into five marine subdivisions based on hydrological, oceanographic, and biogeographical characteristics. These subdivisions are:

- North Atlantic Marine Division
- South Atlantic Marine Division
- Estrecho and Alborán Marine Division
- Levantine-Balearic Marine Division
- Canary Marine Division

Figure 22 Spanish Marine demarcations. From Giret et al., (2019).

Strategic direction / overarching strategy

Spain adopted its maritime spatial plan, the Planes de Ordenación del Espacio Marítimo (POEM), in February 2023 by the Council of Ministers by Royal Decree. It establishes the requirement for each Spanish marine subdivision (North Atlantic, South Atlantic, Estrecho and Alboran, Levantine-Balearic and the Canary Islands) to create management plans for the Spanish maritime space (European MSP Platform, 2024c).

The POEM strategic direction at both a national and regional scale aims to support real, sustainable blue growth, which promotes maritime sectors while achieving and maintaining the good environmental status of marine waters (European MSP Platform, 2024d). The POEM defines the requirements for each regional management linked to the main milestones in the national marine spatial planning process, including specification of the geographic scope of the regional plans and the uses and activities to be included in the planning, which complement those collected in the Royal Decree 363/2017, of 8 April (European MSP Platform, 2024d). The objectives of maritime spatial planning will be determined in the respective maritime spatial plans:

- A set of specific planning objectives will be defined for each of the five marine subdivisions, considering the environmental objectives of the marine strategies, as well as the sectorial planning objectives.
- When establishing and implementing maritime spatial planning, economic, social and environmental aspects shall be considered, to support sustainable development and growth in the maritime sector, applying an ecosystem- based approach, and to promote the coexistence of relevant activities and uses.
- The maritime spatial plans shall aim to contribute to the sustainable development of energy sectors at sea, of maritime transport, and of the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, and to the preservation, protection and improvement of the environment, including resilience to climate change impacts (Giret et al., 2019).

Legal framework

The EU MSP Directive was transposed into national legislation through Royal Decree 363/2017 on 8 April 2017, establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning. This established the Law on the Protection of the Marine Environment (Ley de protección del medio marino, Law 41/2010) (European MSP Platform, 2024d).

Law 42/2007: The Law on the Protection of the Marine Environment (Ley de protección del medio marino, Law 41/2010) regulates the maritime areas within the 'maritime terrestrial public domain', which includes the territorial waters and natural resources in the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf. According to Article 2.2.3, the Law covers the marine waters (including the seabed, subsoil, and natural resources) under Spanish sovereignty or jurisdiction. The Law established that the Spanish Marine Strategies are the planning tools in each marine subregion (a total of five, one for each Spanish marine subdivision). This provides the legal basis for the development of the POEM.

Within Law 42/2007, Spanish MPAs are defined as:

"MPAs are defined as natural areas designated for the protection of ecosystems, communities or biological or geological elements of the marine environment, which due to their rarity, fragility, importance or uniqueness, deserve special protection" (Áreas Marinas Protegidas (AMP), 2007).

Specifically, Article 32 of Law 42/2007 states:

1. MPAs are designated natural areas for the protection of ecosystems, communities or biological or geological elements of the marine environment, including intertidal and subtidal areas, which are, in view of their rarity, fragility, importance or singularity, deserve special protection. Designated natural areas may adopt this specific category or be protected by any other figure of protection of areas provided for in this Law.
2. For the conservation of MPAs management plans or management tools shall be adopted which establish, at least, the necessary conservation measures and the limitations of the exploitation of natural resources.
3. Irrespective of the category or figure used for its protection, the limitations on the exploitation of the fishery resources in external waters shall be carried out in accordance with Article 18 of Law 3/2001 of 26 March 2001. State Maritime Fisheries.
4. This demonstrates the apparent difficulties in achieving horizontal policy coherence within Spain as there are competing interests between fisheries legislation and MPAs. The Sectoral Conference, on the proposal of the National Coastal Communities and the General Administration of the State, shall establish the common minimum management criteria applicable to the Marine Areas included in the Network.

Law 42/2007 produces a range of protected natural area classifications, resulting in numerous definitions within the Spanish legislation. Collectively, these areas are combined as part of the Spanish Network of Marine Protected Areas (RAMPE) (*Red de Áreas Marinas Protegidas de España (RAMPE)*, n.d.). The RAMPE was formally established and given legal force through Law 41/2020 on the protection of the marine environment. Whilst the RAMPE Master Plan, which all MPAs registered under RAMPE need to adhere to, is outlined in Annex I of the Royal decree 1056/2022. It states that the RAMPE Master Plan strategic objectives are:

- SO.1 Promote an ecologically coherent network that contributes to the conservation of natural heritage and marine biodiversity.
- SO.2 Promote planned, effective and coherent management of marine protected areas.

- SO.3 Develop a RAMPE governance structure based on transparency and the participation of the various actors involved.
- SO.4 Promote the development of management capacities for marine protected areas incorporated into RAMPE.
- SO.5 Evaluate the effectiveness of RAMPE.
- SO.6 Communicate to society the value of the conservation of marine protected areas.
- S O.7 Contribute to the strengthening of international strategies for the conservation of marine biodiversity and the Sustainable Development Goals in the marine environment (Real Decreto 1056/2022, de 27 de Diciembre, Por El Que Se Aprueba El Plan Director de La Red de Áreas Marinas Protegidas de España y Los Criterios Mínimos Comunes de Gestión Coordinada y Coherente de La Red, 2022a)

In Law 42/2007, restoration of ecosystems is defined as *“a set of activities aimed at re-establishing the functionality and capacity for evolution of ecosystems towards a mature state”*.

As per Law 42/2007, the definition of protected natural spaces is:

1. They shall have the consideration of protected natural spaces in areas of national territory, including inland waters, and maritime waters under national sovereignty or jurisdiction, including the exclusive economic zone and the platform. continental, which meet at least one of the following requirements and are declared as such:
 - a. Contain representative, unique, fragile, threatened or special systems or natural elements of special ecological, scientific, landscape, geological or educational interests.
 - b. Be dedicated especially to the protection and maintenance of biological diversity, geodiversity, and the associated natural and cultural resources.
2. Protected natural spaces may be exclusively terrestrial, terrestrial and marine, or exclusively marine, in their perimeter.

Law 41/2020: Regulates the maritime areas within the 'maritime terrestrial public domain', which includes the territorial waters and natural resources in the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf. According to Article 2.2.3, the Law covers the marine waters (including the seabed, subsoil, and natural resources) under Spanish sovereignty or jurisdiction. The Law for the Protection of the Marine Environment 41/2010 advances the work of the Natural Heritage and Biodiversity 4/2007 and sets the following national objectives:

- Establishment of five marine strategies covering the Spanish marine areas in the three marine subregions (Mediterranean, North Atlantic and Macaronesia). These are the planning tolls in each marine subregion.
- Reinforcement of the protection of marine biodiversity through the following actions: development and extension of the Spanish Network of Marine Protected Areas (RAMPE); designation of new marine protected areas, including marine Natura 2000 sites; approval of the Recovery and Conservation Plans for Threatened Marine Species; approval of the National Strategies for the Conservation of Threatened Marine Species; approval of the National Strategies to Fight against the Main Threats to Marine Biodiversity.

This Act sets the guidelines for the Management of Natural Resources issued by the Government and will establish the basic criteria and standards that must be included in the plans of the Autonomous Communities for the management and use of natural resources.

Spanish legislation recognises and seeks to address the terrestrial marine interface with the Spanish Constitution (Article 132.2) defining the 'maritime-terrestrial public domain'. The importance of this is advanced through the Regulation on Coasts (Reglamento General de Costas), which seeks to provide protection for the maritime-terrestrial public domain by:

- Determining the maritime-terrestrial public domain and ensuring its integrity and proper conservation, adopting, where appropriate, protection and restoration measures, as well as adaptation measures, considering the effects of climate change.
- Ensuring public use of the sea, its shores, and the rest of the public sea-land domain, with no exceptions other than those derived from duly justified reasons overriding public interest.
- Regulating the rational use of these goods in accordance with their nature, purpose, and with respect for the landscape, the environment and historical heritage.
- Achieving and maintaining adequate water quality and seashore level (Article 2 of Law 22/1988, of July 28).

Legal institutions

Figure 26 provides a summary of the Spanish Government institutions identified as part of the Marine Parks research project. The key legal institutions responsible for marine conservation within Spain are:

The State Council on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity is the public participatory body for nature conservation and biodiversity. Its composition, functions and rules of procedure are regulated by Royal Decree 948/2009 (modified by Royal Decree 649/2011). The State Council advises on rules and plans related to natural heritage and biodiversity; takes note of the annual reports on the state of Spanish Natural Heritage and Biodiversity; encourages dialogue and collaboration with administrations and institutions and economic and social actors involved in the sustainable use of biodiversity; and advises, as required, on technical and scientific matters in preparation for international meetings on biodiversity conservation. Committees of the State Commission for Natural Heritage and Biodiversity are predominantly terrestrial focussed but do include committees overlapping with marine conservation:

- Protected Natural Areas Committee - promotes cooperation between the representative bodies and management of protected natural spaces
- Wetlands Committee - coordinates activities regarding the conservation of these ecosystems
- Committee on Flora and Fauna - coordinates activities regarding the fulfilment of international agreements and community rules associated with flora and fauna

Given the State Commission for Natural Heritage and Biodiversity has Committees covering terrestrial, coastal ecosystems and protected natural areas its mandate is broad enough to facilitate an integrated management approach

Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (MITECO): As the Spanish competent authority for MSP this Ministry has the jurisdiction over MPAs and restoration. The legal framework outlines the authority over MPAs, and restoration is a central government role, however experiences for implementation of MPAs within Spain demonstrate that this responsibility is shared between central and regional governments.

Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment (MAPAMA): The central Government, in conjunction with coastal autonomous communities. The process of declaring and managing MPAs. MPA declaration is by royal decree following an approved MAPAMA proposal supported by a report from the Environmental Advisory Council and the Sectoral Fisheries Conference (article 27.1 of Law 41/2010) (*Áreas Marinas Protegidas (AMP)*, n.d.). MAPAMA is also responsible for implementing the RAMPE through Law 41/2020 (*Red de Áreas Marinas Protegidas de España (RAMPE)*, n.d.).

Committee on Protected Natural Areas: Established by Royal Decree 1424/2008, of August 14, 2008, this Committee determines the composition and functions of the State Commission for Natural Heritage and Biodiversity, dictates the rules that regulate its operation and establishes the specialised committees attached to it, will exercise the following functions in relation to RAMPE: Develop the Programme of Common Actions to achieve the objectives of the RAMPE Master Plan.

- Promote measures at network level through the Common Action Programme.
- Draw up the programme of actions.
- Ensure coordination with marine strategies and maritime spatial planning plans.
- Promote inter-administrative and intra-administrative cooperation.
- To report the monitoring reports of the actions and reports on the situation of the Network.

(Real Decreto 1056/2022, de 27 de Diciembre, Por El Que Se Aprueba El Plan Director de La Red de Áreas Marinas Protegidas de España y Los Criterios Mínimos Comunes de Gestión Coordinada y Coherente de La Red, 2022b)

Figure 23 Spanish governance institutions From (McAteer et al., 2023)

Implementation of strategic direction

Status

This study identified that only 0.07% of management plans have been assessed for their effectiveness, compared to the 60% target agreed to in COP-10 Decision X/31 for protected area management effectiveness (PAME) assessments being undertaken for MPAs and OECMs (UNEP-WCMC, 2024b).

Monitoring performance

The implementation of the Marine Strategies and MSP are intrinsically linked and have established review processes (European MSP Platform, 2024c). Each marine subregion has Marine Strategy Monitoring Committees, which were created to monitor the implementation of the five Spanish Marine Strategies, according to the Law on Protection of the Marine Environment (European MSP Platform, 2024c). Consistent with legal obligations, strategic environmental assessments are undertaken under the responsibility of the D.G. of Environmental Quality and Assessment and the D.G. of the Coast and the Sea.

Natural Heritage and Biodiversity Art 47 outlines the need for monitoring. The monitoring appears to be designated to be undertaken by the Autonomous Communities and provide information to the Ministry of Environment as per Article 45.1. This is done for three to six years, respectively, in line with Community Directives 79 /409/EEC and 92 /43/EC in the areas of the Natura 2000 network. The implementation of MPAs is specified by the legal framework, with the requirement for monitoring the MPA management plans outlined in Article 9 of Law 42/2007, of December 13, on Natural Heritage and Biodiversity Article 16. Plans for the Management of Natural Resources states:

"The Plans for the Management of Natural Resources are the specific instrument for the delimitation, classification, network integration and determination of their relationship with the rest of the territory, of the systems that integrate the patrimony and the resources natural of a particular spatial scope, irrespective of other instruments which can be established by the autonomic legislation."

RAMPE specifies the need for monitoring and evaluation processes to be in place and that there are criteria for this work. Notably, 'Marine protected areas incorporated into RAMPE shall have programmes for monitoring the status of conservation objects and their threats and programmes for monitoring human activities, both based on harmonised protocols that allow for the comparison of data at network scale.' These must be consistent with the monitoring programmes of marine strategies, demonstrating a coherent approach to monitoring (Real Decreto 1056/2022, de 27 de Diciembre, Por El Que Se Aprueba El Plan Director de La Red de Áreas Marinas Protegidas de España y Los Criterios Mínimos Comunes de Gestión Coordinada y Coherente de La Red, 2022a). It is notable that MPAs and other protected areas are not required to be part of RAMPE, meaning that some designated areas may not be in the RAMPE (Áreas Marinas Protegidas (AMP), n.d.). The RAMPE sets minimum criteria for recognition, and as such, it is unclear what criteria areas outside the RAMPE meet.

Accountability

Art 13(2) of the Natural Heritage and Biodiversity Act highlights the need to include processes for 'public information and consultation'. It states that it will be 'necessarily include'. Legally it is the obligation of public administrations to promote participation and activities that contribute to achieving the objectives of the law; identify and eliminate or modify incentives contrary to the conservation of natural heritage and biodiversity; promote the use of fiscal measures to incentivise private nature conservation initiatives; and promote education and general information about the need to protect wild flora and fauna species and conserve their habitats, as well as enhance public participation.

Ireland

Ireland's maritime area is approximately 490,000 km² (approx. 7 times its terrestrial landmass) and geographically represents a different area compared to other States within the Atlantic and Arctic basin, given the island of Ireland's location within the lighthouse. It comprises parts of the Irish and Celtic Seas, as well as the Atlantic Ocean and certain areas of the Continental Shelf, where Ireland has defined its EEZ (European MSP Platform, 2024a).

The Irish marine environment is transboundary in nature, with Irish waters experiencing warm southern waters mixed with cold northern waters, resulting in high productivity levels and a food-rich environment. Consequently, Irish marine waters have a rich and diverse range of species and habitats. These seas are home to various animals and plants, including plankton, cold-water corals, fish, cephalopods (such as octopus, squid, and cuttlefish), shellfish, marine birds, reptiles and marine mammals. The Irish maritime area contains a rich variety of physical habitats and associated species, ranging from shallow inshore reefs and sandbanks to canyons, seamounts, troughs and cold-water coral reefs in deeper waters (European MSP Platform, 2024a).

Figure 24 Map showing the limits of Ireland's maritime jurisdictional zones and the boundary of Ireland's Maritime Area. From Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020.

Yellow lines indicate boundaries of Ireland's claimed extended continental shelf area.

Strategic direction / overarching strategy

Ireland's overarching strategic direction has been developed in consistency with international legal obligations and transposed into national legal requirements (Figure 25). The key strategic plans and policies in place to manage its marine protected areas and restoration projects are:

National Biodiversity Action Plan (NBAP):

This plan sets out actions to protect biodiversity, including marine environments. It has been developed in accordance with the requirements of the CBD, Sustainable Development Goals, and EU Directives (Government of Ireland, Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023-2030.Pdf, n.d.).

Harnessing Our Ocean Wealth (HOOW):

The HOOW called for 'good environmental status' to be achieved for marine waters by 2020. The HOOW was an integrated marine plan from the Department of the Marine outlining how the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive will be implemented (Irish Wildlife Trust, 2018.). MPAs and restoration projects are encompassed within the Harnessing Our Ocean Wealth's stated purpose and objectives:

Figure 25 CBD Strategy and Action Plan – Ireland. From Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage Government of Ireland, 2024

Our ocean wealth will be a key element of our economic recovery and sustainable growth, generating benefits for all our citizens, supported by coherent policy, planning and regulation, and managed in an integrated manner (Inter-Departmental Marine Coordination Group, 2012).

- **Goal 1** focuses on a thriving maritime economy, whereby Ireland harnesses the market opportunities to achieve economic recovery and socially inclusive, sustainable growth.
- **Goal 2** sets out to achieve healthy ecosystems that provide monetary and non-monetary goods and services (e.g. food, climate, health and well-being).
- **Goal 3** aims to increase our engagement with the sea. Building on our rich maritime heritage, our goal is to strengthen our maritime identity and increase our awareness of the value (market and nonmarket), opportunities and social benefits of engaging with the sea (Government of Ireland, 2012).

National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF): Provides Ireland's comprehensive maritime spatial planning, integrating marine conservation objectives. The stated NMPF vision established under the marine planning policy statement is:

"Our vision for an integrated, holistic marine planning system in Ireland is for a marine planning system with clear forward planning, development management and enforcement elements that promotes and sustains ocean health, and supports the sustainable (recreational) enjoyment, management and use of Ireland's marine resource."

The NMPF is designed to be the guiding strategy document guiding decision-making and was published after a four-year consultation process (Government of Ireland, 2021). This Framework constitutes environmental, economic, and social objectives to ensure the sustainable future of Ireland's maritime area. The stated policies associated with protected marine sites:

- **Policy 1:** Proposals must demonstrate that they can be implemented without adverse effects on the integrity of Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) or Special Protection Areas (SPAs). Where adverse effects from proposals remain following mitigation, in line with Habitats Directive Article 6(3), consent for the proposals cannot be granted unless the prerequisites set by Article 6(4) are met.
- **Policy 2:** Proposals supporting the objectives of protected marine sites should be supported and:
 - be informed by appropriate guidance
 - must demonstrate that they are in accordance with legal requirements, including statutory advice provided by authorities relevant to protected marine sites.
- **Policy 3:** Proposals that enhance a protected marine site's ability to adapt to climate change, enhancing the resilience of the protected site, should be supported and:
 - be informed by appropriate guidance
 - must demonstrate that they are in accordance with legal requirements, including statutory advice provided by authorities relevant to protected marine sites.
- **Policy 4:** Until the ecological coherence of the network of protected marine sites is examined and understood, proposals should identify, by review of the best available evidence (including consultation with the competent authority with responsibility for designating such areas as required), the features, under consideration at the time the application is made, that may be required to develop and further establish the network. Based upon identified features that may

be required to develop and further establish the network, proposals should demonstrate that they will, in order of preference, and in accordance with legal requirements: a) avoid, b) minimise, or c) mitigate significant impacts on features that may be required to develop and further establish the network, or d) if it is not possible to mitigate significant impacts, proposals should set out the reasons for proceeding

Figure 26 Journey to the National Marine Planning Framework. From (Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, 2021a)

Within the NMPF, there are sectoral/activity-specific marine planning policies (SMPPs). Consistent with the EU's direction to move towards a more holistic approach, Ireland has now accelerated its implementation of a new marine planning system based on Designate Maritime Area Plans (DMAPs). DMAPs will build on the NMPF, creating maritime plans for particular spatial areas or activities, including sectoral approaches as per SMPPs (MaREI, 2020). This policy response marks a move away from a developer project-led approach to a state plan-led approach for managing multiple uses of the sea, including offshore renewable energy. The introduction of DMAPs in this new policy has generated concerns amongst other users of the sea, most notably the fisheries sector, which faces further access restrictions as new MPA legislation moves forward. However, these competing pressures have also created opportunities for the fishing industry to become new actors in the governance of offshore wind (Van Leeuwen, J., Van Tatenhove, J. Coelho, N.F., Adjei, M., Pereira, et al., 2024).

At the time of writing, the first DMAP consultation is underway, proposing an area located off the South Coast of Ireland for Offshore Renewable Energy, signalling the active implementation of Ireland's NMPF (Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, 2023).

Legal framework

Ireland has a comprehensive legal framework demonstrating vertical integrations with the legal structure extending from regional and international levels down to the national level. As a dualist demography, Ireland incorporates EU legislation into its national legislation. The EU Directives associated with MPAs and restoration have been enacted into Irish law. Table 6 identifies how the legal framework for MPAs and

restoration is implemented in the Irish context. The key Acts associated with marine conservation in Ireland are:

Wildlife Act 1976: This is the original nature conservation legislation in Ireland, and its purpose was to provide legal protection to wild animals, birds, and plants and regulate various activities related to hunting, trapping, and management of wildlife. The aims of the Wildlife Act of 1976 were:

- to provide for the protection and conservation of wild fauna and flora,
- to conserve a representative sample of important ecosystems,
- to provide for the development and protection of game resources and to regulate their exploitation, and
- to provide the services necessary to accomplish such aims.

The original Act of 1976 provides for different types of protected sites (see table below), as well as more general provisions on the protection of wild birds, animals and flora; restrictions to protect wildlife; and controls on wildlife dealing (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b). The amended Act provides for the designation of protected areas as shown in the table above but is limited in terms of providing designations for areas beyond the 12 nautical miles (nm) limit, encompassing land and the foreshore only (Morgane Bouvet, Fien De Raedemaeker, Inne Withouck, Maëlla et al., 2023).

The Marine Protected Area Advisory Group identified that the Wildlife Acts are underutilised for protecting marine areas, and they proffer that this may be due to the implementation of the Birds Directive and Habitats Directive, which occurred at a similar time .

Maritime Area Planning Act (MAP): Ireland seeks to take a holistic approach to MSP, environmental protection, and economic development within the maritime sector (McAteer et al. 2023). This Act legally underpins an entirely new marine planning system, which seeks to balance development, such as the Irish offshore wind energy potential, with the need to protect the marine environment.

This Act is intended to streamline the consenting process for numerous activities in the maritime area subject to decision-making by Local Authorities and An Bord Pleanála. It provides the vehicle through which spatial designations can be made in support of specific marine activities, such as the development of Offshore Renewable Energy, or protection (through the adoption of designated of MPAs)(Maritime Area Planning Bill, 2019). The interaction of this bill with the Marine Protected Areas Bill (discussed below) is unknown because at the time of writing the Marine Protected Areas Bill is still being drafted.

Marine Protected Areas Bill: The proposed legislation is intended to effectively balance all conservation requirements and the long-term, sustainable use of Ireland's valuable and diverse marine environment. This will be achieved by working in parallel with the Maritime Area Planning Act (2021) and the suite of existing legal biodiversity protection measures (*Marine Protected Areas*, n.d.). At the time of writing, a general scheme of the Bill had been drafted, but it had not been enacted into law. The general scheme is available online (General Scheme of Marine Protected Areas Bill, 2023). Significantly, the draft of this Bill will create a definition for an MPA and OECMS. The stated MPA definition in the draft Bill is:

"Marine Protected Area means a geographically defined area of marine character or influence which is protected through legal means for the purpose of conservation or protection of specified species, habitats or ecosystems and their associated ecosystem services and cultural values, and managed with the intention of achieving stated objectives over the long term."

Table 6 Summary of legislation and policies requiring protected area designation in Ireland's maritime area. From Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020.

Source	Objectives and definitions	MPA target	Implementation in Ireland
United Nations			
Convention on Biological Diversity, 1992	To halt the loss of biodiversity. --- Protected area is "a geographically defined area, which is designated or regulated and managed to achieve specific conservation objectives" (CBD Article 2) --- Marine protected area: "Any defined area within or adjacent to the marine environment, together with its overlying water and associated flora, fauna, historical and cultural features, which has been reserved by legislation or other effective means, including custom, with the effect that its marine and/or coastal biodiversity enjoys a higher level of protection than its surroundings."	Representative and effectively managed MPA networks should be put in place by 2012, so as to effectively conserve 10% of each of the world's marine regions. Article 8(a) specifies that contracting parties should: "Establish a system of protected areas or areas where special measures need to be taken to conserve biological diversity"	Less than 2.5% of Ireland's marine area has been designated for conservation purposes. National Biodiversity Action Plan Responsible authority: DHLGH (NPWS)
CBD Strategic Plan 2011-2020	"Any defined area within or adjacent to the marine environment, together with its overlying water and associated flora, fauna, historical and cultural features, which has been reserved by legislation or other effective means, including custom, with the effect that its marine and/or coastal biodiversity enjoys a higher level of protection than its surroundings."	Aichi Target 11: "By 2020, at least 17 % of terrestrial and inland water areas and 10% of coastal and marine areas, especially areas of particular importance for biodiversity and ecosystem services, are conserved through effectively and equitably managed, ecologically representative and well-connected systems of protected areas and other effective area-based conservation measures, and integrated into the wider landscapes and seascapes."	National Biodiversity Action Plan Responsible authority: DHLGH (NPWS)
UN Sustainable Development Goals (not legally binding)	Goal 14 Life Below Water	Target 14.5 - By 2020, conserve at least 10 per cent of coastal and marine areas, consistent with national and international law and based on the best available scientific information	National Implementation Plan 2018-2020 Responsible authority: DCCAE / whole of government relating to their functions (DHLGH responsible for Goal 14) OSPAR sites but the 19 OSPAR MPAs are SAC sites). Responsible authority: DHLGH
EU legislation and policies			
Birds Directive 1979 (as amended)	Ensuring biodiversity through conservation of habitats and species. No definition of SPA, but describes it as an area for the conservation of the bird species listed in Annex I, in the geographical sea and land area where the Directive applies, and also for regularly occurring migratory species not listed in Annex I.	Set up a coherent, ecological network of special areas under the title Natura 2000. Designate Special Protection Areas (SPAs)	Ireland's SPA network encompasses 570,000 ha of marine and terrestrial habitat. Legal backing: Yes. Transposed into Irish national law by the European Communities (Birds and Natural Habitats) Regulations 1997 (amended 2011-2015) ("the B&NH Regulations"). Responsible authority: DHLGH (NPWS)
Habitats Directive, 1992	Conserve biodiversity through a requirement to take measures to maintain or restore natural habitats and wild species listed in the Annexes to the Directive at a favourable conservation status.	Set up a coherent, ecological network of special areas under the title Natura 2000. Designate Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) for Annex I and Annex II.	There are 90 SACs selected for marine and coastal Annex I and II habitat/species present in Ireland. Legal backing: Yes. B&NH Regulations. Responsible authority: DHLGH (NPWS)
EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030	Long-term plan to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems	Proposal to legally protect a minimum of 30% of the EU's sea area and integrate ecological corridors and an EU Nature Restoration Plan, including legally binding targets in 2021	Commission's strategy must be passed by European Parliament before there can be any implementation of its proposals.
Marine Strategy Framework Directive	Achieve or maintain Good Environmental Status MPAs are not defined by the MSFD. In the report by the EC on progress made in the establishment of MPAs, MPAs are described as "geographically defined marine areas; whose primary and clearly stated objective is nature conservation; which are regulated and managed through legal or other effective means to achieve this objective" (EC, 2015).	Article 13(4) "Programmes of measures established pursuant to this Article shall include spatial protection measures, contributing to coherent and representative networks of marine protected areas, adequately covering the diversity of the constituent ecosystems, such as special areas of conservation pursuant to the Habitats Directive, special protection areas pursuant to the Birds Directive, and marine protected areas as agreed by the Community or Member States concerned in the framework of international or regional agreements to which they are parties."	Ireland's Programme of Measures includes the following relating to MPAs [and associated Descriptors]: Continue to ensure coherence of Ireland's network of marine protected areas by setting up increased protection areas using tools such as habitat protection orders, no-take zones etc. [1,4,6] Continue to consider whether sites justify selection as Marine Protected Areas. [1,3,4,6,7] Set up (temporary or permanent) Marine Protected Areas in functional zones for fish. [1,3,4,6] Develop a national strategy to create and manage Ireland's network of Marine Protected Areas. [1,4,6] Legal backing: EC (Marine Strategy Framework) Regulations 2011 and Amendment Regulations 2017 Responsible authority: DHLGH
* Note: The specific designation may not have legal backing per se but it may be covered by another legal designation or instrument (e.g. the B&NH Regulations), which helps ensure protection and prevent damage.			
DHLGH – Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage (formerly Department of Housing, Planning and Local Government) NPWS – National Parks and Wildlife Service, falls under Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage as of 30th September 2020 DCCAE - Department of Communications, Climate Action and Environment			

Legal institutions

Within Ireland, a range of government departments have responsibilities for managing the marine environment. The complex structure and interaction between institutions are a consequence of how the legal instruments developed over time to meet both changing international obligations and changing national priorities and resourcing.

The Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage (DHLGH): DHLGH is responsible for designating SPAs and SACs following the procedure laid down in Part 3 of the Regulations (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b). The Birds and Habitats Directives have been transposed into national law by the European Communities (Birds and Natural Habitats) Regulations, 2011-2015ii ('the B&NH Regulations'). Ireland's designation process started in 1997. As of February 2019, 439 SACs (270 of which have been formally designated by Statutory Instrument) and 163 SPAs have been selected (160 of which have been formally designated by Statutory Instrument).

Historically, DHLGH has been Ireland's primary competent authority responsible for MSP and MPAs. They are also the competent authority required to publish a maritime spatial plan with the following objectives, as specified by Section 16 (1) of the Maritime Area Planning Bill 2021;

The objectives of a MSP shall be—

(a) to analyse and organise maritime usages in the maritime area for the purpose of achieving ecological, economic and social priorities,

(b) to establish a national strategy for the Government in relation to the strategic planning and sustainable maritime usages in the maritime area,

(c) to apply an ecosystem based approach for the purpose of supporting proper planning and sustainable maritime usages in the maritime area, and

(d) to promote the colocation of different types of maritime usages in the maritime area (Maritime Area Planning Bill, 2021).

Up until the end of 2023 DHLGH have been responsible for issuing specific marine area consents (MACs) with the exception of offshore energy developments (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b).

Maritime Area Regulatory Authority (MARA): The Maritime Area Planning Bill 2021 established the Maritime Area Regulatory Authority (MARA). MARA was established on 17th July 2023 under the aegis of the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage. MARA is a new independent agency, established under the Maritime Area Planning Bill 2021, which will be responsible for regulating development and activity in Ireland's maritime area (European MSP Platform, 2024a). Its functions are set out in the Maritime Area Planning Acts 2021 and 2022, and it will have a key role to play in the new streamlined consenting system for the maritime area, including:

It is a new independent agency, established under the Maritime Area Planning Bill 2021, which will be responsible for regulating development and activity in Ireland's maritime area (European MSP Platform, 2024b).

- Assessing Maritime Area Consent (MAC) applications for the maritime area, which are required by developers before development permission can be granted
- Granting marine licencing for specified activities
- Compliance and enforcement of MACs, licences and offshore development consents

- Investigations and prosecutions
- Administration of the existing Foreshore consent portfolio
- Fostering & promoting co-operation between regulators of the maritime area.

The Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine (DAFM): This department responsible for agriculture, food, fisheries and forestry policies and funding.

The Department of Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC): This department is responsible for environmental issues such as climate change, waste, the circular economy and the Sustainable Development Goals (Government of Ireland, Ireland's 4th National Biodiversity Action Plan 2023-2030, n.d.). Responsibilities include issuing specific marine area consents (MACs) focussed on offshore energy developments (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b), and since a Government decision in 2023, their mandate was increased to include marine planning (transferred from DHLGH).

The recent most significant change was the transfer of marine planning responsibilities to DECC consistent with recommendations to *"consolidate and rationalise the regulation of marine development and activity to build on the National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF) and Maritime Area Planning Act (MAP Act) and give practical effect to Ireland's ambition to have a modern, fit for purpose, world-leading marine planning system."* (Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, 2024). The specific functions transferred were:

- Policy and legislative responsibilities in relation to marine forward planning and enforcement (under the MAP Act)
- Governance and oversight of the Maritime Area Regulatory Authority (MARA)
- Regulation of activity on the foreshore (under the Foreshore Acts 1933) as part of the migration to the new system operated by MARA under the MAP Act (Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, 2024)

Cross-sectoral Marine Spatial Planning Advisory Group: DECC is also leading the establishment of a cross-government structure to bring together all departments and agencies with a marine remit. This new group will provide for the alignment of marine policies and State investment in the maritime sector, giving leadership and oversight on a whole Government basis. At the time of writing, this group has been reactivated and is said to return to meeting regularly, providing an important vehicle for overseeing the implementation of the existing NMPF and informing the development of the next NMPF.

National Parks & Wildlife Service (NPWS) of the Department of Culture, Heritage and Gaeltacht: In Ireland, the National Parks and Wildlife Service (NPWS) provides performance reporting against international reporting obligations such as CBD Aichi Targets, and the status of all SPAs and SPCs under Article 12 of the Birds Directive (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b).

Project Ireland Delivery Board: provides a leadership and oversight role to implement the NMPF. Their role is to implement the central and successful underpinning of Project Ireland 2040 (the National Planning Framework (NPF) and the National Development Plan (NDP)) by aligning spatial and investment plans.

Overlapping legislation

Within the Irish governance framework, there are overlapping strategies, competencies and levels of implementation. For example, the National Planning Framework (NPF), which is related to the National Development Plan, is a parallel planning document. Both the NPF and NMPF recognise the inherent overlap of activity between the two regimes and the requirement for coordination (Government of Ireland, 2021). The need to recognise and account for the overlap between marine and terrestrial

planning is specified in the Planning and Development Act 2018 (Planning and Development (Amendment) Act 2018, 2018). This recognition is consistent with the MSP Directive requirements. The distinction is that the NPF and NMPF form the statutorily based spatial planning framework, whilst the NDP is the key investment plan, covering all sectors, irrespective of whether the investment is on land or sea (Government of Ireland, 2021).

Figure 27 Organogram for the Celtic Sea Planning Site, showing the statutory organisation information for Ireland. Implementation of strategic direction. From McAteer et al., 2023.

Status

Through the implementation of the MSFD and MSP, Ireland has a network of protected areas for species and habitats (SPAs and SACs), Wildlife Act designated areas, and OSPAR- and Ramsar Convention designated areas that constitute Ireland's MPA network. Ireland's SPA network encompasses some of the productive intertidal zones of bays and estuaries that provide vital food resources for wintering waterbirds. Marine waters adjacent to breeding seabird colonies and other important areas are also included in the network. The majority of the breeding seabirds and wintering waterbirds are considered to be regularly occurring migratory birds. This is reflected in the fact that the majority (> 80%) of Ireland's SPAs are designated for these two bird groups. SPAs are selected in Ireland according to four criteria:

- A site regularly supporting 20,000 waterbirds or 10,000 pairs of seabirds
- A site regularly supporting 1% or more of the all-Ireland population of a species listed in Annex I of the Birds Directive
- A site regularly supporting 1% or more of the biogeographic population of a migratory species
- A site considered to be one of the most suitable sites in Ireland for an Annex I species or a migratory species (number of sites depends on the importance of the Irish territory for the international conservation of the species)

Figure 28 Ireland's Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) in red and Special Protection Areas (SPAs) in blue designated for marine features and clipped at the mean high water line to show only the maritime component of these sites. From (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020).

Figure 29 All of Ireland's Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) designated for marine features, including offshore and near shore sites, clipped to the mean high water line. From (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020).

The majority of Ireland's network of protected areas have legal protection through national legislation, with the exception being OSPAR-designated areas based on the OSPAR list of threatened and declining species not included in the EU Habitats or Birds Directives (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b). These species do not have legal protection and are not included in the MPA network reported to the EU (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b).

The Marine Protected Area Advisory Group has identified the existence of OSPAR areas that are not legally protected as a gap in policy coherence that results in the ineffective protection of a range of species and vulnerable marine ecosystem

indicators (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b). Significantly, their 2020 report stated that "Ireland's network of protected areas cannot be considered coherent, representative, connected or resilient or to be meeting Ireland's international commitments and legal obligations" (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b).

In addition, the Marine Plan project identified that Ireland has implemented international and EU law domestically, except for the designation of Other Effective Areas of Conservation Measures (OECMs) and EBSAs (McAteer et al., 2023). INFOMAR research shows a range of vulnerable habitats that have not yet been integrated into Ireland's Natura 2000 or Marine Protection framework, including endangered shark nurseries and deep-water corals (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022). The Committee further recommends that MPAs include highly protected marine areas (HPMAs) as part of their designation and that coastal zone management be integrated into them (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022).

Monitoring performance

The Marine Protected Area Advisory Group identified that while monitoring and reporting on the status of marine biodiversity has progressed, there is still a general paucity of data, meaning there is still not a comprehensive understanding of the marine biodiversity status and the effectiveness of MPAs (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b). The Committee noted the lack of a cohesive approach to data gathering and monitoring of the marine environment (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022). A position supported by the observation in the WWF assessment report on 'Maritime Spatial Planning in the North-East Atlantic Ocean' that whilst the Irish governance and management framework includes monitoring obligations through the development of Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA), there is a lack of baseline information on the status of the protected areas and no associated assessment of effectiveness (WWF, 2022).

It is recognised that Ireland has not reached the coverage targets set at both the EU and national levels (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022). These observations are supported by the 2021 Aichi Biodiversity Target 11 Irish dossier, which reported marine protected area coverage of 9,943.9km² (2.3%), with only 86km² (0.9%) of these areas having had a Protected Area Management Effectiveness (PAME) assessment completed (CBD, 2021c). Compared to the 0.02% PAME assessments reported on the World's Protected Area database. Either of these reported figures is well below the 60% target, as per COP decision X/31, for completed PAMEs (CBD, 2021c).. The figures above highlight observations regarding inconsistencies in reporting and show this is apparent within and between States, as well as variability in how different international reports present the status and progress of MPAs and restoration projects. In terms of coverage targets and effectiveness, Ireland's MPA and restoration are not performing in a manner that can demonstrate that their network is meeting its strategic objective. The European Court of Justice judgement that Ireland has failed to effectively manage existing MPAs based on the absence of effective implementation of management plans across all MPAs supports this position (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022). These results demonstrate why the Commission has identified the need to develop and implement management plans for all MPAs (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022).

Nationally, performance assessments have identified the fragmentation of the legislative framework and institutions as undermining existing performance to meet the overarching strategic goals. For example, the Citizens' Assembly report on Biodiversity loss stated that an audit on monitoring and enforcement needs to be undertaken (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022). The Committee recommends a more integrated approach to monitoring and restoring biodiversity, and that consideration should be given to establishing a separate department for the marine environment to better address the challenges of climate change in relation to the marine environment (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022).

The development of Irish MPAs is mostly based on supra-national frameworks such as the OSPAR Convention and the EU Birds and Habitats Directives. However, such frameworks often lack respective legislation in Ireland to legally underpin protected areas (e.g., OSPAR MPAs do not ensure any legal protection to the respective areas on their own). OSPAR sites come under the OSPAR Convention to Protect the Marine Environment of the Northeast Atlantic, under which Ireland has committed to establishing MPAs to protect biodiversity (i.e., OSPAR MPAs). According to the NPWS, *"no legislation is currently used in Ireland to legally underpin protected areas established to fulfil commitments under*

international conventions". Listings under OSPAR do not confer any specific protection regarding restricting activities within these areas. All protection for OSPAR sites coincides with sites that are either SACs or SPAs or both (*Irish Wildlife Trust, 2018.*).

Table 7 demonstrates that there are a variety of MPA definitions within Ireland. Despite the range of legislative instruments associated with biodiversity, marine spatial planning, and protected areas, there is no definition of MPA in Irish law (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b). An operation definition was proposed by the Marine Protected Area Advisory Group of:

"A geographically defined area of marine character or influence which is protected through legal means for the purpose of conservation of specified species, habitats or ecosystems and their associated ecosystem services and cultural values, and managed with the intention of achieving stated objectives over the long term."

At the time of writing, protected areas can only be afforded legal protection in Ireland within the Habitats Directive (HD) and the Birds Directive (BD) frameworks or the Wildlife Acts. The Wildlife Acts apply only to land and the foreshore, to a maximum of 12 nm. Beyond 12 nm, areas can only be designated as SPAs or SACs under the EU Birds and Habitats Directives and only for the habitats and species that are listed in their annexes. Many threatened or declining species and habitats of national, regional and local importance, therefore, cannot be explicitly legally protected through area-based measures in Ireland (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020b).

The Joint Oireachtas Committee on Biodiversity report released in 2022 recommended *"the need to prioritise the designation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) as well as the immediate development and implementation of management plans for existing and future designated MPAs to restore biodiversity and prevent further damage"* (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022). The vision is the following *"Biodiversity in Ireland is valued, conserved, restored and sustainably used, maintaining ecosystem services, sustaining a healthy planet and delivering benefits essential for all people"*, supported by the following objectives:

1. Adopt a Whole-of-Government, Whole-of-society Approach to Biodiversity
2. Meet Urgent Conservation and Restoration Needs
3. Secure Nature's Contribution to People
4. Enhance the Evidence Base for Action on Biodiversity
5. Strengthen Ireland's Contribution to International Biodiversity Initiatives

Accountability

Ireland facilitates participation in the governance process through several participatory measures, such as consultations, referenda, and Citizen Assemblies. Each of these provides the ability to engage with decision-making but does not confer direct decision-making, which remains with the State. The closest demonstration of devolved responsibility is the use of Citizen Assemblies.

Public participation is a specified statutory requirement with the Maritime Area Planning Act 2021 (s18) specifically outlining the legal requirements to ensure public participation, which includes both *"involvement of interested persons in the preparation of a relevant document"* (consistent with co-design principles) and public consultation. The Act does not codify exact requirements but makes it clear that public participation statements need to be developed with components included as outlined in the Act (Maritime Area Planning Bill, 2021).

Despite established participation frameworks and processes, there is a lack of true accountability because the monitoring and reporting framework does not provide the requisite information to support decision-making and undermines the ability to learn and adapt (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022). Significantly, the 2023 Report to the Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action recommends a referendum to protect biodiversity either by incorporating the rights of nature, the right to a healthy environment, or both into the Irish Constitution (Oireachtas, 2024). This indicates interest in providing Irish citizens with direct influence on the legal framework through amending the Constitution, although the impacts of this approach and the reality of its implementation could conceivably affect accountability if nature or oceans are given legal status.

Furthermore, it is recommended that blue finance and finance of nature restoration be advanced, as well as a coherent policy approach to support environmental governance across government departments, and that implementation and enforcement of existing environmental law be given priority¹⁴. This is despite the Future Ireland Fund and the Infrastructure, Climate and Nature Fund (ICNF)'s funding mechanisms representing important developments in terms of allocating funding for biodiversity and nature initiatives (Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action, 2022).

Table 7 Summary of MPA definitions used within Ireland associated with marine conservation. From (Marine Protected Area Advisory Group, 2020a)

MPA type	Definition and purpose of the area	Number of currently existing marine sites
Natural Heritage Areas (NHAs)	Selected based on criteria such as the contribution to conservation of vulnerable, rare, or endangered species or habitats in Ireland or the Atlantic biogeographical region, representation of typical Irish habitats or ecosystems, and contribution to the conservation of geological, geomorphological, or fossil features as determined by the Geological Survey of Ireland.	No NHA has been established to date for marine habitats.
Refuges for Fauna and Flora	Designated on lands where the Minister of Housing, Local Government and Heritage considers that particular species of fauna or flora require special protection.	7 refuges having significant importance for seabirds.
Wildfowl sanctuaries	Areas over which shooting of wild birds is prohibited.	68 sites.
Nature Reserves	Areas of importance to wildlife that are protected under the Wildlife Acts. The criteria for Nature Reserve status include the habitat or ecosystem being of scientific interest, likely to benefit from protection measures, and being on state-owned or private land.	13 sites with marine elements.
National parks	Selected based on IUCN criteria, such as the presence of ecosystems minimally impacted by human exploitation, the presence of significant plant and animal species, geomorphological sites, and habitats of scientific, educational, and recreational interest or natural beauty.	No national park currently includes marine features.

¹⁴https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/committee/dail/33/joint_committee_on_environment_and_climate_action/reports/2023/2023-12-14_report-on-the-examination-of-recommendations-of-the-citizens-assembly-report-on-biodiversity-loss_en.pdf

Portugal

Portugal is an oceanic country with one of the largest maritime national jurisdictions in Europe. It represents 1,727,408 km², an area 18 times the country's terrestrial area, and has a coastline of around 2,500 km. The Portuguese maritime triangle (Mainland, Madeira, and Azores) constitutes 48% of all marine waters under the jurisdiction of the Member States of the European Union (EU) in areas adjacent to the European continent (República Portuguesa, 2021a).

Due to the length of its coastline and biogeographical position, Portugal must face the challenges of climate change, environmental protection, and biodiversity conservation as determinants of building its future as a nation. Given that 76% of the Portuguese population lives in the coastal area, where some of the most important sectors of maritime activities (coastal tourism, ports, and leisure) occur, Portugal has dramatically contributed to the appreciation of the sea for its geopolitical and geostrategic affirmation in the Atlantic and related maritime spaces (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019; República Portuguesa, 2021a). Maritime legislation and planning are a political priority.

Figure 30 Portuguese marine demarcations and functional units. From (Giret et al., 2019b)

Strategic direction / overarching strategy

The Portuguese Constitution establishes a unitary State, recognising the insular autonomy and the principles of subsidiarity, autonomy of local authorities and decentralization of public administration. The need for a strategic plan for Portugal is set at the highest level through the Portuguese Constitution, which states that the Portuguese territory is subject to constitutional liability and administration, a fundamental responsibility of the State, namely by:

*“e) Protecting and enhancing the cultural heritage of the Portuguese people, defending nature and the environment, preserving natural resources and ensuring a proper spatial planning; (...)
g) Promoting the harmonious development of the entire national territory, namely taking into account the ultra-peripheral character of the archipelagos of Azores and Madeira”.* (Cavaco, C., Mourato, J., Costa, J.P., Pereira, A., Vilares, E., Moreira, P., Magalhães, M, 2021)

Portugal's strategic direction is set by the National Strategy for the Sea (ENM). The National Strategy for the Sea 2021-2030, approved by the Council of Ministers on May 6th, 2021, is the public policy instrument presenting the vision for that period. It expresses the will and priority to protect the ocean and benefit from its potential sustainably and in the long term (Direcao-Geral de Política do Mar, 2023). The ENM states the ENM vision is:

“The vision of this strategy is based on promoting a healthy ocean to enhance sustainable blue development, the well-being of the Portuguese and affirm Portugal as a leader in ocean governance, supported by scientific knowledge” (República Portuguesa, 2021a).

The overarching vision and strategic objectives are broad in nature and take a holistic approach to setting Portugal's strategic direction. The associated ENM's strategic objectives align with the overarching vision and focus on areas where a difference can be made either on the blue economy or where the national relationship with the sea can be improved. The ENM has 10 strategic objectives,

aligned with the 2030 Agenda by the United Nations and the European Ecological Pact, of which one is related to protection and restoration (OE1 – Combat Climate Change and Pollution and Protect and Restore Ecosystems).

Specific recognition of the role of MPAs and biodiversity restoration is identified in the document's priority areas of intervention (AIP). AIP3 is titled 'Biodiversity and Marine Protected Areas'. This priority area is building on historical commitments and work such as the 2018 National Strategy for Nature Conservation and Biodiversity 2030, which reaffirmed the importance of protected marine areas, and in 2019, the strategic guidelines and recommendations for the implementation of a National Network of Areas Protected Marines (República Portuguesa, 2021a). Notwithstanding, AIP3 identifies specific strategic areas that need to be addressed:

- 1) Application of existing strategies
- 2) Development and implementation of management plans for existing protected areas, to increase the effectiveness of these biodiversity protection instruments.

Translating these strategic objectives and associated priorities for MPAs and restoration the ENM 2030 meets the political commitment Portugal has made to: *“Classify 30% of national marine areas by 2030, approving the respective management and conservation plans, and ensure that a third of these areas are strictly protected”* (República Portuguesa, 2021a). The ENM is supported by an ENM Action Plan 2021-2030, approved by the Council of Ministers (Giret et al., 2019).

Figure 31 Summary diagram of the National Ocean Strategy 2021 – 2030 including the Visions, Strategic Goals and Priority Intervention Areas. From República Portuguesa, 2021a.

Figure 32 Timeline for MSP in Portugal and maritime space including the proposal for extended continental shelf. From) (Frazão Santos et al., 2014)

Legal framework

The two main types of actions considered under the legal framework are active conservation actions, which comprise direct intervention on species and habitats for preservation and recovery when necessary, and other support actions covering actions regarding regulation, registration, monitoring and inspection. The management of nature conservation is primarily framed under two policy documents:

- The legal regime for nature conservation and biodiversity (Decree-Law no. 142/2008 amended by Decree-Law no. 242/2015), which sets up the main policy principles, instruments and types of action; and
- The National Strategy for Nature Conservation and Biodiversity 2030 (ENCNB 2030), which establishes national strategic guidance, as well as a number of concrete measures, inherent responsibilities and possible funding. Both documents consider nature conservation as a factor of national competitiveness and development and look at means to attain international goals.

The Portuguese spatial planning policy is framed by an integrated system for spatial planning and territorial management (sistema de gestão territorial). This is implemented through a set of hierarchical multi-level planning instruments and norms for their implementation, including the programming of territorial interventions and land use change. This has resulted in the Portuguese spatial planning policy framework comprising of a vast array of legislation and policy mechanisms.

For MPAs they are covered by the overarching EU Directives as implemented through national legislation. It is recognised that Portugal developed a new legal framework for MSP within which MPA and restoration is encompassed (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019). Table 8 summarises the way EU Directives associated with MPAs, and restoration have been enacted into Portuguese law.

In 2014 the MSP and Management Law was approved (Law No. 17/2014), the purpose of which was to “foster economic exploitation of marine resources and ecosystems services, while ensuring the compatibility and sustainability of different maritime uses and activities, accounting for intergenerational responsibility in the spatial use of national maritime space and aiming at job creation” (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019).

The MSFD was transposed into national law in November 2010 by Decree-Law No.108/2010 which established the Portuguese legal framework to meet MSFD and has had subsequent amendments in recent years (Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services, 2018). Decree-Law No. 108/2010 seeks to reflect both MSFD requirements and specific national characteristics and does so by developing four marine strategies:

- **Marine Strategy for the Subdivision of the Continent:** includes the national marine waters around the mainland, except for the extended continental shelf, and integrates the sub-region of the Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast.
- **Marine Strategy for the Subdivision of the Azores:** includes the national marine waters around the Azores archipelago, except for the extended continental shelf, and is part of the Macaronesia subregion.
- **Marine Strategy for the Subdivision of Madeira:** includes the national marine waters around the archipelago of Madeira, except for the extended continental shelf, and is part of the Macaronesia sub-region.
- **Marine Strategy for the Subdivision of the Extended Continental Shelf:** includes the continental shelf beyond 200 nautical miles from the baselines from which the width of the territorial sea is measured (Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services, 2018)

In Portugal maritime spatial planning is required to be coherent with coastal zone management plans. In addition, one of the objectives of the law refers to the protection and recovery of coastal ecosystems. Portuguese integrated coastal management is addressed through the Law of Land, Terrestrial Planning and Urbanism (Law No. 31/2014) which establishes the Coastal Zone Management Plans (POOC), subsequently renamed Coastal Zone Programmes (POC). These are focussed on considering a 'maritime zone of protection' reflecting a nationwide approach but in a manner that reflects the local nature of the POCs. In addition, one of the objectives of the law refers to the protection and recovery of coastal ecosystems. The Portuguese coastline is split into sections, each of which has a specific Programme for the Coastline (POC), which aims to create conditions for an integrated management of coastal areas. POC cover areas to include two buffer zones;

- The terrestrial buffer zone – a strip of land along the coastline, at least 500m wide (from the shoreline (backshore) towards the hinterland). The width of the strip can reach 1,000m, which is deemed appropriate for protecting coastal systems (e.g., dunes, fossil cliffs, coastal lagoons, wetlands, etc.) and inherent dynamics.
- The maritime buffer zone – the water strip that goes from the limit of the foreshore - i.e., the high-water level during spring tides - up to the 30m bathymetry line.

Legal institutions

Portugal clearly developed a dedicated governmental and institutional framework (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019). The key strategic document, i.e., the ENM, is developed, evaluated and updated by the Directorate-General for Maritime Policy of the Ministry of Economy (DGPM). Competent authorities responsible for implementing the ENM 2021-2030 are structured to distinguish between political and technical coordination.

- **Political coordination** is ensured by CIAM, which is the structure for reflection, coordination and strategic decision-making on the sea, chaired by the Prime Minister. CIAM is supported by a network of focal points designated by members of the Government and Regional Governments that constitute it.
- **Technical coordination** is the responsibility of the DGPM for the national MSP, which supports the implementation, monitoring, evaluation and review of the ENM 2021-2030 (República Portuguesa, 2021a). DGPM is responsible for the national implementation and mainland Portugal, whilst regional public administrations are responsible for the Azores and Madeira, respectively, e.g., the Regional Directorate for Maritime Affairs, Autonomous Region of the Azores and the Regional Directorate for Spatial Planning and Environment, Autonomous Region of Madeira (Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services, 2018; European MSP Platform, 2019). The autonomous regions of Madeira and the Azores have exclusive and shared competencies in maritime affairs together with the National Government (European MSP Platform, 2019).

Figure 33 National Strategy for the Sea (ENM) 2021-2030 governance model. From (Direcao-Geral de Politica do Mar. 2021)

Responsibility for maritime affairs passed in 2015 to a new Ministry of the Sea. The Ministry of the Sea is fully empowered to coordinate and develop maritime policies, although the articulation of sectoral policies is supposed to occur at the Interministerial Commission for Maritime Affairs (CIAM) (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019). Responsibility for MPAs and restoration is encompassed within key competent authorities whose responsibilities are broader to encompass MSP. Table 8 and Figure 34 summaries the institutional framework outlining the roles and responsibilities of Portuguese institutions. These identify the following key roles:

Directorate-General for Maritime Policy of the Ministry of Economy (DGPM): DGPM's legal status is provided for through Decree-Law No. 18/2014, of 4 February and Regulatory Decree No. 17/2012, of 31 January. The General Directorate of Maritime Policy (DGPM) is responsible for supporting the coordination and management of public policies related to the Sea. The DGPM is a Government Department that has administrative autonomy over developing, evaluating, and updating the ENM. In Portugal, the responsibility of maritime spatial planning policies lies with the DGPM, and the licensing responsibility is divided between DGRM and the Portuguese Environment Agency (Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente, APA).

DGPM performs executive functions in support of the CIAM, necessary for coordinating, monitoring, updating, and evaluating the implementation of the ENM and transversal measures and policies related to maritime affairs approved by the Government. DGPM's roles include:

- Proposing in coordination with the National Authority for Nature Conservation and Biodiversity, the creation of marine protected areas, ensure the management of those of national interest and collaborate in the management of those of regional or local scope, namely through the preparation/elaboration, assessment, and review of respective planning plans
- Participating at a technical and scientific level, in the definition and promotion of strategies for the protection of marine protected areas, defined at national, community or international level,

and coordinate national participation under the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR)

- Licensing and inspecting, within the scope of its powers, the use of waters in protected marine areas (Direção-Geral de Recursos Naturais, Segurança e Serviços Marítimos, 2018a).

Inter-ministerial Commission for Maritime Affairs (CIAM): Established in 2007 with the intent to bring together representatives of all the concerned ministries to ensure interministerial coordination that supports the monitoring and coordination of the implementation of the National Sea Strategy (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019). The ability of the CIAM to address cross-cutting policies is achieved through the composition of the committee, which consists of public institutions from the Ministry of the Sea, the Portuguese Environmental Agency, the Nature Conservation Institute, representatives of municipalities, autonomous regions of Azores and Madeira and representatives of economic sectors (European MSP Platform, 2019). Portugal does not attribute any competence for MSP to the CIAM (inter-ministerial committee), thus diverging from the other countries (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019).

A summary of the governance institutions that are involved with marine conservation are summarised in Table 8 at a governmental level, whilst Figure 34 provides additional information that identifies the additional roles of cross-cutting bodies such as the CIAM. It demonstrates that whilst there is one lead authority associated with marine conservation, jurisdictional overlap exists. Most notably with regards to the integrated coastal zone management and associated terrestrial and maritime planning instruments (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019). Casimiro & Guerreiro (2019) note that the Portuguese administration has sought to mitigate conflict associated with governance in the coastal zone by developing specific regulations for coastal MPAs and developing requirements around coastal protection and nature conservation through the PSOEM (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019). The prevalence of maritime planning reflects the importance, both cultural and economic, that Portugal places on the marine environment

Table 8 Portugal's institutional framework for the governance of the sea. From Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019.

Ministry of the Sea	
○ DGPM (Directorate General for Maritime Policy)	Responsible for MSP policies.
○ DGRM (Directorate General of Natural Resources, Security and Maritime Services)	Responsible for the implementation of MSP
○ IPMA (Portuguese Institute of the Sea and Atmosphere)	Responsible for research projects reverting to direct applications to use in operational activity. Searches for a progressive improvement of information provided to users, with the concern oriented to safeguarding people and property.
CIAM (Interministerial Commission for Maritime Affairs)	Coordination and monitoring of cross-cutting policies. Responsible to oversee the correct implementation of the National Sea Strategy.
Ministry of Environment and Climate Action	
○ Portuguese Environment Agency (APA)	EIA national Authority; Regulates coastal zone planning and management
Ministry of National Defense	Maritime security and national defense.

Figure 34 Organogram showing the statutory organisation information for Portugal. From McAteer et al. 2023.

Implementation of strategic direction

Enacting the ENM is achieved through the use of a Situation Plan and an Allocation Plan:

- **Situation Plan – Maritime Spatial Planning Plan (PSOEM):** This plan provides an overarching view of the multi-use of the marine environment, including protected areas and the spatial and temporal distribution of marine activities. The plan provides for existing and potential uses, reflecting the different timeframes associated with marine activities for the private use of the Portuguese maritime space (Casimiro & Guerreiro, 2019).
- **Allocation plan:** The allocation plan allocates areas and volumes of the national maritime space to uses and activities unidentified in the situation plan.

At a national scale, the action plan of the National Strategy for the Sea 2021-2030 (ENM 2021-2030) aims to provide an implementation roadmap and a monitoring and evaluation framework to meet the ENM strategic objectives and goals (República Portuguesa, 2021a). The action plan also focuses on activities related to knowledge of the ocean and the atmosphere and scientific research in different domains and to some administrative and governance aspects (European MSP Platform, 2019). The action plan measures related to the strategic goal related to MPAs and restoration are:

- Implement a national program for mapping habitats, ecosystems and marine and coastal ecosystem services, including the assessment of their condition and the implementation of priority restoration measures.
- Classify and effectively manage at least 30% of marine waters under national jurisdiction in accordance with European and international targets, including 10% of the maritime area under strict protection, and implement the National Network of Marine Protected Areas (RNAMP).
- Implement a national program for observation, high-resolution mapping and knowledge of the deep sea in the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) and extended continental shelf.
- Promote inventory, scientific knowledge and classification of nautical and underwater cultural heritage (using robotic systems and technologies), considering it in coastal management and in political decision-making instruments, namely in the Maritime Spatial Planning Plan (República Portuguesa, 2021b).
- Promote close national collaboration with the secretariat Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON), under the responsibility of AIRCenter, to lead international efforts in marine biodiversity conservation projects.
- Develop a study to assess the main conflicts between maritime activities, as well as their impacts on sensitive ecosystems.

Figure 35 National Strategy for the Sea (ENM) 2021-2030 governance model demonstrating the vertical integration between international, national and local governance authorities. From (Direção-Geral de Política do Mar, 2021).

The NME Action Plan includes measures to “identify legal regimes and administrative procedures relating to activities linked to the sea that require review, simplification or integration”. All measures associated with AIP3 ‘Biodiversity and Marine Protected Areas’ are detailed in the action plan.

Status

Coastal and marine ecosystems provide diverse services of great magnitude and economic importance for a coastal country. The latest national report on biodiversity submitted to protected planet as part of Portugal’s Protected Area Profile for the World Database on Protected Areas identified that for Mainland Portugal, there is no assessment of the impact of changes to biodiversity on ecosystem services nor of the sociocultural implications of this impact (UNEP-WCMC, 2024a). This study identified that despite 16.9% of the marine area being classified as having protected coverage, only 0.12% of management plans have been assessed for their effectiveness. This is in contrast to the 60% target agreed to in COP-10 Decision X/31 for protected area management effectiveness (PAME) assessments being undertaken for MPAs and OECMs (UNEP-WCMC, 2024a).

Monitoring and performance

Pursuant to Order No. 1/2017 of March 6, a working group was created to evaluate existing MPAs and propose the designation of new areas to create a national network of ecologically coherent marine protected areas (RNAMP). The RNAMP, as an instrument for the protection of marine life, will also contribute to supporting the sustainable management of fishing and other human activities in a relevant way. The working group included representatives from a diverse range of entities and was designed to provide a range of stakeholder views (Direção-Geral de Recursos Naturais, Segurança e Serviços Marítimos, 2018b).

According to the legal regime for nature conservation and biodiversity (Chapter 7.2.4), all the protected areas included in the RNAMP with classification at the national level are required to have a POAP. Classification at the national level can be assigned to one of the following categories: national park, natural park, natural reserve, or protected landscape within which there are different levels of protection:

- **Areas of full protection** – those that include landscape and natural assets of outstanding value and, therefore, of high ecological sensitivity. Human activity is required to be reduced to a minimum.
- **Areas of partial protection** – those that include relevant natural landscapes and assets and where land uses, and human activities need to adapt so natural habitats and biodiversity can be well-preserved.
- **Areas of complementary protection** – those having a role in providing for a transitional background and deterrent mechanism to protect the highest value areas against the negative effects of human activity (Cavaco et al., 2021).

Accountability

The main guidelines for framing and operationalising the ENM 2013-2020, within the framework of the application of the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), were established in the Partnership Agreement that Portugal signed with the European Commission, and it is worth highlighting that, given the nature cross-cutting ENM 2013-2020, part of its implementation involves not only the support provided by the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) but also the mobilisation of Cohesion Policy Funds, specifically, the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the Cohesion Fund (CF) and the European Social Fund (ESF) (Decreto-Lei n.º 200/2015, de 16 de Setembro, 2015).

The required funding to support the implementation of the ENM is made available through the Commission for the Implementation of the Integrated Territorial Investment of the Sea (ITIMAR) (República Portuguesa, 2021b). ITIMAR provides the framework for establishing effective and efficient processes for the application of the European Structural Funds and associated investment in shared management of national funds, such as the Blue Fund and the Environmental Fund, of the Financial Mechanism of the European Economic Area (EEA Grants) and other public and private investors in Portugal with interests in the sea area (República Portuguesa, 2021b). The role and responsibilities of ITIMAR are complemented by equivalent work and functional articulation of ENM 2021- 2030, particularly in the articulation at the level of smart specialization strategies and financiers in the maritime area and the future articulation at the level of Portugal 2030 (República Portuguesa, 2021b).

France

France's geographical position means it spans four of Western Europe's five major biogeographic regions (Atlantic, alpine, continental and Mediterranean).

The results in the marine ecosystem within French jurisdiction being home to a large diversity of species and ecosystems, as well as a mosaic of natural landscapes (Lefebvre & Moncorps, 2013). French ecosystems are home to about 10% of the 1.8 million known species on our planet. In particular, the overseas territories are home to 80% of French biodiversity, including 4/5 of the species endemic to French territories (Giret et al., 2019).

Figure 36 France's maritime delimitations. From (Giret et al., 2019)

Strategic direction / overarching strategy

France has a national strategy for protected areas adopted in 2021 that integrates both land and sea. This is the first unified strategy for protected areas for France and its overseas territories. The fundamental strategic document is the 2030 National Strategy for Protected Areas which is a strategy rooted in local settings with a vision to:

- Promoting interconnections between protected areas and their surrounding territories
- Promoting a variety of types of protected areas suited to local situations
- Promoting a protected areas governance mobilising local stakeholders

Within this Strategy protected areas are considered living entities, and some are at the same time biodiversity strongholds and the living environment of many citizens who are experiencing the early stages of a different relationship with nature. The new strategy has the ambition to deepen stakeholders' involvement in and the territorial integration of protected areas, which are not isolated 'no-go zones' but territories interacting with their surroundings.

The National Strategy for Protected Areas has been developed within the context of France's international and European commitments as well as regional agreements and multilateral programmes (e.g., the CBD, the EU Biodiversity Strategy etc.) The National Strategy for Protected Areas is based on two pillars:

1. A target of 30% protected areas, which constitute the framework for the protection of the territory;
2. A target of 10% strong protection, with a higher level of protection.

The overarching strategy is the National Strategy for Protected Areas which has seven objectives. This strategy is accompanied by a 3-year Action Plan (2021-2023) which includes measures to meet the strategic objectives. The 7 objectives in the overall National Strategy are as follows:

1. Develop a Network of Protected Areas Resilient to Global Changes
2. Support the Implementation of an Effective and Custom-Made Management of the Protected Areas Network
3. Support Sustainable Activities in the Protected Areas Network
4. Consolidate the Integration of the Protected Areas Network into the Local Setting
5. Strengthen International Cooperation to Stem the Erosion of Biodiversity
6. A Durable Network of Protected Areas
7. Consolidate the Role of Protected Areas in Furthering Knowledge Concerning Biodiversity

Figure 37 The French National Strategy for protected areas 2030. From (Office Français de la Biodiversité, 2021)

The National Strategy for the Management and Creation of Marine Protected Areas specifies the policy for protecting areas with a view to contributing to the knowledge of environments, healthy marine ecosystems, the maintenance and the sustainable development of maritime activities, better management of the interface between the land and sea and taking into account the issues defined at different levels.

The strategy is updated at least every 10 years. The new national strategy for protected areas provides a horizon for 2030 and will be accompanied by three three-year national action plans developed and fed by the territories. The new national strategy for protected areas was developed by all stakeholders during a 15-month consultation. It is accompanied by a first national action plan for the period 2021-2023, the implementation of which mobilises all the actors who participated in the development of this new strategy (Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion, 2023).

The new strategic approach takes a co-constructive approach whereby the intent is to bring all protected areas together and integrate them into an integrated national policy (Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion, 2023).

Legal framework

France has a codified legal framework that clearly establishes roles and responsibilities as part of outlining the legal powers in place to meet the National Strategies. The overarching legal tool is the Environment Code. The Environmental Code Article 110-4 specifies the legal requirement to develop and implement a national strategy for protected areas. This strategy is updated every 10 years. The legally required aims that have to be covered by the national strategy are:

1. Protect the environment and landscapes,
2. Preserve and recover biodiversity,
3. Prevent and mitigate effects of climate change and
4. Enhance natural and cultural heritage of the territories.

This is a legal requirement as the Environment Code Article 110-4 to specify the definition and procedures for implementing strong protection, linked to the 10% strict protection requirement. Decree No. 2022-527 of 12 April 2022 defines the concept of strong protection as well as the terms and conditions for the implementation of this strong protection. Decree No. 2022-527 defines strong protection as:

“A strong protection zone is defined as a geographical area in which the pressures generated by human activities likely to compromise the conservation of ecological issues are absent, avoided, eliminated or severely limited, and this in a sustainable manner, thanks to the implementation of land protection or appropriate regulations, associated with effective control of the activities concerned.”

The principle of the National Strategy for Protected Areas and the two targets (1. A target of 30% protected areas, which constitute the framework for the protection of the territory; 2. A target of 10% strong protection, with a higher level of protection) are enshrined in Article 110-4 of the Environmental Code. This sets the legal obligation to meet the targets.

Decree No.2022-527 Art2 states the following areas are recognised as areas of strong protection, whilst Article 3 refers to maritime areas and states:

- I. *The maritime areas included in the protected areas listed below, created after the date of entry into force of this Decree, are recognised as areas of strong protection:*
 - a. *the heart of national parks provided for in Article L. 331-1 of the Environmental Code;*
 - b. *the enhanced protection zones and the integral protection zones created by the acts of classification as a nature reserve taken pursuant to Articles L. 332-1 to L. 332-27 of the same code;*
 - c. *areas covered by a protection order issued pursuant to Articles L. 411-1 and L. 411-2 of the same code.*
- II. *The maritime areas, included in the protected areas listed in I, created before the date of entry into force of this decree shall meet the criteria of Article 4 within 24 months and shall be recognised as strong protection zones by this date at the latest.*
- III. *Other maritime areas with significant ecological challenges, primarily located within marine protected areas listed in Article L. 334-1 of the Environmental Code, may be recognised as strong protection areas, on the basis of a case-by-case analysis established in accordance with the procedures defined in Articles 4 and 6.*

Art 4 provides the requirements to define an ad-hoc strong protection (not included in Art3(I)) and makes it clear the criteria including having a management document including monitoring. The institution with the authority to establish a strong protection zone is outlined in Art 6 and makes it clear that this is the Maritime Facade Council for each mainland France metropolitan maritime frontage. This body meets annually. As per Art L219-6-1 of the Environmental Code the composition and function of the coastal maritime council is set by the Minister responsible for the sea. This group is responsible for developing a strategic coastal document and an action plan for the marine environment. Significantly L219-9 requires the maintenance of good environmental status including developing and implementing an action plan for the marine environment that includes an initial ecological assessment, definition of good

environmental status and a set of environmental objectives and indicators. These need to be submitted to relevant base committees for comment as part of the land/marine interface.

Of note is that integrated management of the sea and coastline requires a strategic document as per ArtL219-3 that defines *“the objectives of integrated sea and coastal management and the provisions corresponding to these objectives, for each of the maritime coasts and overseas sea basins, in accordance with the principles and guidelines defined by the national strategy for the sea and the coast. In addition to the draft strategic document for the coastline or sea basin, a summary of its content is made available to the public, in accordance with the procedure provided for in Article L. 123-19.”*

The Minister for Nature Protection and the Minister for the Sea jointly recognise a strong protection area (Art 8). This provides legal recognition of the need for cross-departmental work coordination. The Act identifies that there needs to be recognition of the differing roles and responsibilities between the Minister's portfolios to support marine protection.

Restoration

Article 110-03 identifies that the national biodiversity strategy *“provided for in Article 6 of the Convention on Biological Diversity, adopted in Nairobi on 22 May 1992, is drawn up by the State in consultation with representatives of local authorities and their groups, socio-economic actors, in particular small and medium-sized enterprises, and environmental organizations, including naturalist associations, as well as members of the scientific community.”*

This obligates regions to define and implement a regional biodiversity strategy taking into account the guidelines of the national strategy and drawn up under the same conditions of consultation. Local authorities and their groupings participate in the definition and implementation of this strategy at the level of their territory. The national and regional biodiversity strategies contribute to the integration of the objectives of conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity into public policies and to the coherence of the latter in these areas.

Legal institutions

Given the establishment of new authorities through the Environmental Code there are now multiple organisations involved in MPA management. This means that France's protected areas are managed by OFB and 'Others are managed by separate operators: other public institutions, local authorities, professional bodies, associations, etc.' The main French governance institutions responsible for implementation of marine conservation are summarised in Figure 38. The key institutions and their roles are summarised below:

The French Office of Biodiversity (Office Français de la Biodiversité): The primary central organisation responsible for having a key role at both domestic and international levels. The French Biodiversity Agency (OFB) is a public institution dedicated to the protection and restoration of biodiversity in Metropolitan France and its Overseas Territories, under the supervision of the ministries responsible for Ecology and Agriculture & Food. The OFB directly manages or co-manages protected areas, to which it dedicates human, financial and technical resources:

- 8 Marine Nature Parks (6 in mainland France and 2 in the French overseas territories);
- The Agoa Sanctuary for marine mammals in the West Indies;
- 110 marine Natura 2000 sites and 4 terrestrial Natura 2000 sites;
- 8 National Nature Reserves (RNN);
- 10 National Hunting and Wildlife Reserves (RNCFS) managed by the OFB, out of the 12 existing RNCFS;
- 6 Hunting and Wildlife Reserves (RCFS);

- 3 Corsican Hunting and Wildlife Reserves (RCFS de Corse);
- 1 Man & Biosphere Reserve;
- Sites of the Coastal Conservatory;
- 1 Biotope Protection order (APB). (<https://www.ofb.gouv.fr/en/managing-protected-areas>)

Significantly the OFB was established and manages protected areas but also delegates authority in some cases. This national strategy sets the vision for OFB whilst the Environmental Code provides the legal basis for its establishment and the definition of its legal responsibilities. The national strategy state:

"The local level will be responsible for implementing the strategy and for keeping higher levels informed about projects concerning new protected areas and local issues to be taken into account in applying action plans over the next decade."

This statement is enacted through the Environmental Code which outlines that the governance of protected areas can be devolved / delegated by the OFB Directors to the councils of protected areas. Specifically, 131-8 and 131-9 and 131-9(6)(III) of the Environmental Code outlines the legal basis for implementation:

"The Office and the local authorities shall coordinate their actions in areas of common interest. The regions or local authorities exercising the powers of the regions and the office may jointly set up, within the framework of an agreement signed between the parties, regional biodiversity agencies in which the departments and local authorities exercising the powers of the departments may be associated. These agencies carry out their tasks within the scope of the Office's missions, with the exception of police missions and the issuing of hunting permits."

Other statutory bodies responsible for governance and management of the MPA include the following):

- **The Conservatory of coastal areas and lakeshores (Conservatoire du littoral):** The Conservatoire du littoral is a public administrative establishment of the State placed under the supervision of the minister responsible for nature protection.
- **Local collectives, NGOs and associations, which can be managers of marine protected areas:** Those areas not managed directly by the OFB are managed by others public institutions, local authorities, professional bodies or associations.¹⁵
- **Conference on protected areas (CAP):** The CAP was established to support the management of protected areas within France. Significantly the CAP has statutory recognised and is used to provide advice on 'protected areas' policy, and is led by the OFB.

¹⁵ Managing protected areas ([ofb.gouv.fr](https://www.ofb.gouv.fr)).

Figure 38 French governance institutions. From (McAteer et al., 2023)

Implementation of strategic direction

Status

As reported by OFB France's protect area network covers 23.5% of waters and 21% of land. This percentage coverage now constitutes nearly 1756 Natura 2000 sites, 355 nature reserves, 11 national parks, 58 regional nature parks and 8 marine nature parks (Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion, 2023; Office Français de la Biodiversité, 2024). OFB's reporting is specifically focussed on Marine Natural Parks, the network of which is shown in Figure 40. As of May 2022, there are eight Marine Natural Parks, six in mainland France: Iroise, Mayotte, Gulf of Lion, Picardy Estuaries and Opal Sea, Arcachon Bay, Gironde Estuary and Pertuis Sea, Ca p Corse and Agriate, Martinique (Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion, 2023).

Figure 39 The 8 Marine nature parks are managed by the French Biodiversity Agency (OFB). From Office Français de la Biodiversité, 2024.

Figure 40 Map of protected areas managed, co-managed or attached to the OFB. From Managing protected areas. From Office Français de la Biodiversité, 2024.

Monitoring performances

Most protected areas within France have management plans and some have evaluation tools to assess performance (Lefebvre & Moncorps, 2013). However, it is still recognised that there is a need to establish a comparable standardised assessment methodology. The 2020 independent assessment identified 98.5% of MPAs have management documents in place. This is consistent with the codified nature of OFB Marine Nature Parks which are legally required to have a management plan (Barbut et al., 2020).

Figure 41 Three-year trend in French Marine Protected Areas (MPA) with management plans. From (Barbut et al., 2020)

What is less apparent from this study is the effectiveness of these management plans. When compared to the 60% target agreed to in COP-10 Decision X/31 for protected area management effectiveness (PAME) assessments being undertaken for PAs and OECMs France does need meet the specified targets. As of May 2021, 113km² (0.03%) of marine protected areas have had PAME assessments completed (CBD, 2021a).

A 2020 assessment of the progress to meet the objectives of the National Biodiversity Strategy (SNB) identified that in spite of positive change for marine conservation and the creation of new MPAs, French authorities has still been unable to mitigate pressures on biodiversity. This raises the question of how effective marine conservation is given the dichotomy in the trends.

As identified by the Prep4Blue report the French MPA network uses a myriad of designations and levels of protection (Morgane Bouvet, Fien De Raedemaeker, Inne Withouck, Maëlla et al., 2023). This report identified potential issues with the fact that Article L334-1 of the Environmental Code (within

Figure 42 Assessment of progress towards achieving specific SNB objectives From (Barbut et al., 2020)

Chapter IV: Marine protected areas) sets out 11 categories of areas that are included as Marine Protected Areas. of MPAs (see Table 9) (Morgane Bouvet, Fien De Raedemaeker, Inne Withouck, Maëlla et al., 2023). Multiple classifications are not necessarily a concern in itself, however it presents a risk of fragmentation and added complexity when understanding how these MPAs link to the overarching strategy. This risk is compounded by the absence of a formal definition of an MPA in national law as identified in the (Morgane Bouvet, Fien, Inne Withouck, Maëlla et al., 2023).

Table 9 Specific French MPA designations and associated protection purposes. From Bouvet et al., 2023.

MPA type	MPA type purpose of the creation
National/Regional/Corse nature Reserve	F1; F2; F3; F8
(National) hunting and wildlife/Corsica Reserve	F1; F2; F3; F5; F6; F9
Nature marine park (NMP)	F1 – F9
National Park (NP)	F1 – F9
Biotope/geotope/natural habitat protected area ruling (B/G/NHPA)	Decree of Protection of the Biotope (DPB): F1; Decree of Protection of the Geotope (DPG): protect a landform of particular scientific, aesthetic or cultural value; Decree of Protection of the Natural Habitats (DPNH): protect a natural habitat, without the need to establish that it is also a habitat for protected species.
Specially protected areas of Mediterranean interest (SPAMI)	To protect sites that are important for the conservation of the components of biological diversity in the Mediterranean Sea. Sites which contain ecosystems specific to the Mediterranean region or habitats of species threatened with extinction. Sites of particular scientific, aesthetic, cultural or educational interest.
Public maritime domain (Conservatoire du littoral) (PMD)	F1; F2; F3; F4; F7; F8; F9
Listed in the list of the World Heritage of UNESCO	F1; F2; F3; F7; F8
Biosphere reserve	F1; F2; F3
Natura 2000 (Special Protection Area (SPA) /Special Conservation Area (SCA)/Site of Community Importance (SCI))	F1 (species and habitats justifying the designation of the site)
Ramsar	F1; F2; F3; F4
OSPAR	F1; F2; F3; F4

* Based on the typology of the Technical Paper n°88 of the Office Français pour la Biodiversité on management plans of natural spaces. F1: Good ecological status of species and habitats; F2 Good status of non-status species and habitats; F3 Rendering of ecological functions; F4 Good status of waters; F5 Sustainable use of resources; F6 Sustainable development of uses; F7 Maintenance of cultural heritage; F8 Social, economic, scientific or educational added value; F9 Landscape value.

Accountability

France has an established framework and processes in place with recent efforts designed to strengthen the involvement of local populations in the establishment and management of protected areas (Lefebvre & Moncorps, 2013). Consultation processes are in place at both the establishment and management. The requirement for participation and accountability is enshrined in national strategy which outlines the need to promote protected areas governance mobilising local stakeholders. Access to information and the principle of participation is legally required by the Environmental Code Article 110-1 which specifies:

- 4° The principle that everyone has the right of access to information relating to the environment held by public authorities.
- 5° The principle of participation, by virtue of which any person is informed of draft public decisions having an impact on the environment under conditions enabling him to formulate his observations, which are taken into consideration by the competent authority (Environmental Code, 2021)

General Code of Local Authorities includes the provisions for providing support grants to municipalities that have a significant territory that includes a protected area or adjoins a marine protected area. The details of the funding model are determined by decree of the Council of State. Municipalities being defined as “in metropolitan France, rural municipalities are municipalities characterised as rural, within the meaning of the National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies and according to the data available on 1 January of the year of distribution. In the overseas departments and regions, municipalities with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants are considered rural” (Environmental Code, 2021).

Under the purview of the OFB there are large marine areas governed by park management boards consisting of elected officials, government departments, users and professionals of the sea, scientists, associations, etc. A specific example of funding arrangements is the Iroise Natural Marine Park whose budget is allocated by the Board of Directors of the French Office for Biodiversity, based on the allocation allocated by the supervising ministries. Some projects may benefit from European funds. Finally, local

Figure 43 Summary assessment of the governance of the Sept-Îles National Nature Reserve (Réserve naturelle nationale, or RNN), Îles From (Schéré et al., 2023)

Governance characteristic of RNN demonstrating a top-down model governance structure, with the State at the top

Table 4. Summary of the strengths and weaknesses of the RNN Sept-Îles's current Advisory Committee, by principle of good governance.

Principle	Strengths	Weaknesses
Fairness and rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The current structure of the Advisory Committee remains within the regulations of the Environmental Code and there is parity between the different Colleges. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The structure is not fit for purpose as it is not equitably representative of all the various stakeholders involved with the RNN. •Young people are noticeably absent from RNN governance.
Legitimacy and voice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The meetings are generally well-attended, so stakeholders have the opportunity to voice their opinions and participate in discussions surrounding the RNN. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •There is an imbalance in speaking time between various stakeholders, with some having more of a voice than others. •There are not enough opportunities to participate (only 2 meetings a year). •A mediator is absent from these meetings; their presence would be beneficial to ensure everyone is able to participate.
Accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •There is good communication between the RNN and stakeholders about important events. •The public is kept well-informed via the local press (print and web news sources). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •There are issues of transparency, wherein the discourse of reserve officials is not transparent enough, leading to confusion, particularly regarding the content of press articles. •Minutes of meetings can be too superficial while scientific reports are considered too detailed and difficult for Advisory Committee members to digest. •There is a lack of interaction between the RNN and the public via social media platforms.
Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The management and monitoring of the RNN Sept-Îles by the LPO and its team on the ground is appreciated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •There is confusion around who holds the decision-making power and scepticism over the data being used to justify decisions made. •There is a push for co-management of

authorities can join the Park by carrying out actions that contribute to the implementation of the management plan or by financing projects (French Office for Biodiversity, 2019). The insert to the right summarises the governance characteristics and learnings of stakeholder engagement for this governance structure.

Participation of stakeholders in MPA planning and management in France is summarised in

Table 10

Table 10. In spite of the legal frameworks and aspirations independent assessments in 2020 identified that the SNB was being undermined by a lack of devolution and decentralisation that was undermining the actions being achieved to meet the ambitions. Observations on the strengths and weaknesses on the implementation process for French MPAs is provided below using RNN Sept-Îles as an operational example which addresses the views on the current governance structure. A paper on the RNN received the following feedback associated with concerns regarding accountability:

- *The current structure was found to lack representativeness within the Advisory Committee, as stakeholders cited other actors that were absent from (or too present within) the Advisory Committee.*
- *Some wondered why state representatives – who do not live in the Trégor region and who rarely, if ever, go to the reserve as ‘they are behind their desks, they are far away, they do not know what is going on’*
- *Indeed, another participant questioned: ‘Ultimately, users of the site are not sufficiently represent[ed]’.*
- *Finally, there was a noticeable lack of young people on the Advisory Committee. Not only was there no youth association, but young users also aligned their views with those of older members of their organisations (French Office for Biodiversity, 2019) (Schéré et al., 2023).*

MPA type	Management bodies		
	Name	Composition	Role
Nature reserve (NNR/RNR/CNR)	Advisory committee	Socio-professional actors and concerned users Qualified stakeholders and Nature Conservation Associations Local authorities, public institutions, local institutions Members are nominated during 5 years (renewable)	Gives advice on the functioning of the reserve, its management and the conditions of application of proposed measures. Can ask the NNR manager to carry out scientific studies and collect other relevant information.
	Scientific council (not systematically present in RNR and CNR)	Set out by the prefect	Assists the advisory committee and reserve manager on scientific issues
National Park	Board of directors	representatives of the French State, locally elected officials, scientists and users of the territory	Assists on all matters concerning the national park
	Scientific council	Appointed by the prefect of the department for 6 years (renewable). It is composed to qualify personalities on nature sciences and human sciences.	Assist the board of directors in everyday activities including monitoring and evaluation.
Nature Marine Park (NMP)	Management council	Composed of: Local representatives of the French State (in a minority), Representatives of the interested territorial communities and their competent groupings, Representatives of the interested regional natural park(s), Representatives of the management body of a contiguous marine protected area, Organization representatives of professionals, users, environmental protection associations and qualified personalities.	Has authority to decide on questions related to the park and to elaborate the management plan.
Natura 2000 sites (SCA, SPA)	Steering committee	Includes local authorities, representatives of owners, operators and users of the territories covered by the site. Representatives of the French State sit in an advisory capacity.	The aim of the steering committee is the elaboration and the monitoring of the implementation of the document of objectives,
Biotope/geotope/natural habitat protected area ruling ¹³	Regional Scientific Council for Natural Heritage (RSCNH)	RSCNH is composed by regional scientist and naturalists in the domain of terrestrial, aquatic and marine natural environments, and also human sciences. Members are nominated during 5 years renewable	consulted for its opinion (it is an obligation)
UNESCO World Heritage sites	National commission for heritage and architecture	Appointed by the Ministry of Culture for 5 years, members are composed of Representatives of the French State, representatives of an elected mandate, representatives of associations or foundations whose purpose is to promote knowledge, protection, conservation and enhancement of heritage, and qualified personalities.	The commission is consulted for the perimeter of the protection and the management plan.

Table 10 Summary of public participation in French MPAs outlining the Participation of stakeholders in MPA planning and management in France. From Bouvet et al., 2023.

7. Arctic national governance baseline

The following section provides an overview of national legal and policy frameworks for marine restoration and protection through area-based management measures in the coastal states within the scope of the BlueMissionAA Lighthouse (Iceland, Greenland, Norway, and the Faroe Islands). None of these Arctic states are members of the European Union and are, therefore, not directly subject to EU legislative and policy frameworks. However, they may align with or adopt certain EU policies and standards due to their close relationships with the EU and partly are strongly influenced by decisions made in the European Union, including in the legal sphere. Furthermore, Iceland and Norway are members of the European Economic Area (EEA), granting them access to the EU's single market and involvement in various EU programs and initiatives. Greenland and the Faroe Islands, as autonomous territories of Denmark, an EU member state, maintain a more complex relationship with the EU, which is characterised by strong political ties.

Norway

Norwegian marine environment and human pressures

Figure 44 Norwegian ocean management plan areas. the Barents Sea–Lofoten area, the Norwegian Sea and the North Sea and Skagerrak. From Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b.

Norway has the second-longest coastline in the world, stretching from high Arctic environments to the Atlantic waters of the North Sea, with sea areas six times larger than its land surface (Environment Norway, 2023). As per the geographical scope of BlueMissionAA, this report focuses on Northern Norwegian waters, including those around Svalbard and the Jan Mayen archipelago. The Norwegian Sea and Barents Sea experience significant alterations due to human impact, including rising temperatures, reduced sea ice and ocean acidification. Climate change is the primary driver affecting ecosystems. Main human activities in the area include fishing, maritime transport, and hydrocarbon extraction (Management Forum for the Norwegian Sea Areas, 2023). These marine areas face increasing future pressure not only from climate change but also due to the potential emergence of new extractive industries. Despite global efforts by governments and environmental groups to halt deep-sea mining, the Norwegian government has recently opened up for extensive deep-sea mineral exploration in the Norwegian Arctic (Norwegian Ministry of Energy, 2024).

Governance context

The Norwegian maritime territory consists of three sub-zones: Mainland Norway has an exclusive economic zone (EEZ), while Svalbard and Jan Mayen are surrounded by a 200 nautical miles (nm) fisheries protection zone (FPZ)¹⁶. In the FPZ, fishing resources are managed by Norway and shared among the signatories of the Svalbard treaty. Respectively, a fisheries zone instead of an EEZ has been established around Jan Mayen (BarentsWatch, 2023; Tiller & Nyman, 2015).

Norway is part of the European Economic Area (EEA) agreement and partially implements EU directives and regulations related to the environment (Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2023). Norway has

Figure 45 Norwegian maritime zone. From BarentsWatch, n.d.

transposed the Water Framework Directive (WFD) into domestic law, establishing a system for integrated water management for river basins. Norway has a large coastline, for which the WFD provides the main legal framework of cross-sectoral planning to achieve ecological objectives. It has been pointed out that the Norwegian implementation of the WFD is primarily intended for freshwater, lacking adequate consideration of crucial marine elements in coastal waters and thus not sufficiently ensuring ecosystem-based management on the coast (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b; Sander, 2023). In the marine areas, Norway has implemented a national governance system based on Norwegian Integrated Ocean Management Plans, which can be considered as paralleling the EU's Marine Strategy Framework Directive. These plans extend from the baseline to Norway's economic zone borders, guiding sectoral management at sea (the plans are described in detail under the sub-section 'implementation') (Sander, 2023). Coastal and marine governance (under the WFD and

Ocean Management plan system, respectively) are subject to distinct regulatory frameworks with little overlap.

Strategic direction

The oceans have a high priority in Norwegian policymaking, emphasised by a series of dedicated ocean strategies and white papers (Norwegian Ministries, 2019).

The Norwegian Integrated Ocean Management Plans are cross-sectoral plans that establish ecosystem-based ocean management. The environmental dimension and objectives of the Integrated Ocean Management Plans are further detailed and implemented through a series of dedicated white papers on marine conservation (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b). In the 1980s, the white paper 'Protection of Norwegian Nature' (No. 12 (1980–1981)) laid the groundwork for Norwegian nature protection policy. With the white paper "Conservation and use of the coastal zone" (No. 43 (1998-1999)),

¹⁶ The FPZ was established due to the special territorial status of the archipelagos. The Svalbard treaty from 1920 integrated the archipelago under Norwegian sovereignty, but differing interpretations of Norwegian sovereignty in the Svalbard maritime area have emerged. To accommodate other Svalbard treaty signatories, Norway opted for an FPZ instead of an EEZ.

special emphasis was given to the marine environment along the coast, resulting in the establishment of an advisory panel and drafting of a marine protection plan. Progress towards the objectives has been slow, and the first three marine protected areas were only established in 2013 (WWF, n.d.). Out of the 39 candidate areas identified by the 2004 marine protection plan, 17 have been protected as of 2023. In recent years, the parliament has requested the government several times to review the topic of marine conservation (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2019). In its white paper “Norway’s integrated plan for the conservation of areas of special importance for marine biodiversity” (No. 29 (2020-2021)) (hereafter referred to as “Integrated plan for marine conservation”), the government presented its renewed ambitions for marine conservation (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). Marine conservation is understood as an overarching approach, which includes both area-based marine **protection** enacted through environmental legislation, as well as other effective area-based **conservation** measures (OECM) enacted through sectoral legislation (mostly fisheries) (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). The eligibility of the Norwegian large-scale fisheries regulations with respect to the OECM criteria is currently being assessed.

The importance Norway pays to ocean governance also translates to its foreign policy (Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2016). Norway has taken a leading role by establishing the High-level Panel of a Sustainable Ocean Economy in 2018, consisting of heads of state and governments representing nearly 50% of the world’s coastline. The High-Level Panel has set the ambitious goal of achieving 100% sustainable ocean management within national jurisdiction by 2025 and supporting the global targets of 30% of ocean protection by 2030 (High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy, 2023). Marine conservation is regarded as one of three fundamental pillars of a sustainable ocean economy, along with sustainable use of resources and a fair distribution of resources. Sustainable Ocean Plans are considered a key pathway towards achieving the goals and strongly build on the Norwegian experience with Integrated Ocean Management Plans (High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy, 2023; Norad, n.d.). Norway has recently signed a Green Alliance with the EU to foster cooperation, including on the implementation of the CBD to achieve 30% ocean protection through MPAs and OECMs (Norwegian government & European Commission, 2023).

Legal frameworks

Environmental legislation for area-based management

In mainland Norway, area-based protection is implemented through the Nature Diversity Act, under the authority of the Ministry for Climate and Environment. In the Svalbard and Jan Mayen archipelagos, area-based measures are established through the Svalbard Environmental Protection Act and the Act for Jan Mayen, respectively.

The Nature Diversity Act (NDA) translates the CBD into Norwegian legislation (Naturmangfoldloven [Nature Diversity Act], 2009). It provides an overarching legal framework for establishing area-based protection measures, including various protection categories that can extend into the marine environment (national parks, protected landscapes, nature reserves, and natural monuments; NDA § 35-38) (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). In 2009, an exclusively marine protection category (“marine protection area” NDA §39) was introduced, but it is not tied to specific protection categories as for terrestrial sites. In this report, marine protection in Norway refers both to MPAs designated under NDA§39, as well as marine parts designated through the other protection categories of the NDA. Areas are designated through the NDA as the primary legislation and then enacted through site-specific regulation, defining the conservation objectives and restrictions applying to the respective area(s). The NDA requires the creation of management plans, but to date, most marine protected areas or marine national parks lack a management plan or detailed regulations on the marine areas. The Act sets out that restrictions on activity shall be proportionate, which underlines the Norwegian ‘liberal’ approach to protection: Not all activities shall be prohibited, but only those that are deemed necessary to achieve the conservation objective (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021; Rådgivende utvalg for marin verneplan, 2004).

An important limitation of the Nature Diversity Act to ensure effective protection lies in its complex articulation with fisheries legislation. Fisheries management is regulated through the Marine Resources Act under the competence of the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (Havressurslova [Marine Resource Act], 2009). While the Nature Diversity Act provides the mandate for regulating most sectoral activities within an MPA through site-specific regulation, the harvesting and utilization of living marine resources (e.g., fishing or kelp harvesting) is specifically regulated through the Marine Resources Act. However, the regulation of fishing activities under the Marine Resources Act within an MPA must operate "within the framework" set by the site-specific protection regulation for that particular MPA. Therefore, the fisheries authorities are involved in the process, as the site-specific regulations must define any restrictions on fishing activities within the MPA. This division of responsibilities requires coordination between the two

Figure 46 Marine conservation in Norway. From Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b.

As part of sectoral legislation like the Marine Resources Act, Petroleum Act, and Seabed Minerals Act (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). This creates a gap in cross-sectoral protection for areas outside the territorial waters. In May 2024, the Ministry for Climate and Environment has presented a proposal for a new legal act through which marine protected areas in the future could be designated beyond the territorial sea (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024a).

Svalbard is regulated under the Svalbard Environment Act, administered through the Governor of Svalbard. The purpose of the Act is "to preserve a virtually untouched environment in Svalbard with respect to continuous areas of wilderness, landscape, flora, fauna and cultural heritage" (Section 1, Svalbard Environmental Protection Act) (Svalbardmiljøloven, 2001). It regulates activities that might impact the environment on land and within the territorial sea (12 nm). There is no specific marine protection category, but protection categories on land (national parks, nature reserves, protected

Acts and their respective authorities to balance conservation and sustainable use of marine resources within MPAs (Norwegian Institute of Marine Research, 2021). In the context of Norwegian MPAs however it has been criticised that the cross-sectoral coordination and integration of fisheries regulation and other human activity into site-specific MPA regulation remains weak and does not sufficiently ensure protection in the designated areas (Norwegian Institute of Marine Research, 2021). Currently, site-specific regulations for most marine protection areas and marine natural parks set very limited to no restrictions on fisheries activities, some even being bottom-trawled (Flekkøy, 2024).

Another limitation of the Nature Diversity Act is that all marine protected areas are located within the coastal zone since the Act only applies to the territorial waters (12 nm from the baseline). Beyond this limit, the Act has no legal authority to establish MPAs or regulate activities, and conservation measures can only be enforced as

biotopes and geotopes, and cultural environments) can extend into the marine environment. As of 2023, 86% of Svalbard's territorial waters are protected through the Act (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). On Jan Mayen, a nature reserve has been established through a royal resolution under the Jan Mayen Act. The nature reserve covers almost the entire island and the territorial waters (Forskrift om Jan Mayen naturreservat, 2010).

Sectoral area-based regulations and the role of OECMs

Figure 47 Assessment of Norwegian Fisheries Regulations with respect to OECM criteria. From Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, 2023.

Green meets the requirements of an OECM; yellow meets the OECM requirement only if specific regulations are reinforced or changed; and red does not qualify as an OECM. Only quantitative targets for OECMs were considered, while criteria for effectiveness or ecological connectivity have largely been excluded.

Marine Resource Act, shall be categorised as “conservation” rather than “protection” (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). Area-based fisheries regulations cover extensive areas of the Norwegian seascape, and Norway is among the first countries to assess their contribution towards meeting national and international targets for biodiversity conservation (Hoel et al., 2023).

The Norwegian government underscores the importance of sectoral legislation, particularly fisheries regulations, in advancing marine conservation goals and reporting to international fora such as the CBD (Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, n.d.; Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021).

The Marine Resource Act is the legal framework for fisheries activities, regulating the management of living marine resources. In 2008, the environmental dimension of the Act has been considerably strengthened. It follows an ecosystem approach, integrating conservation and sustainable use within the same management framework. Norway's implementation of the ecosystem approach to fisheries is pragmatic, reflecting limited resources but has been regarded as rather efficient (Gullestad et al., 2017). Still, the approach does not account for cross-sectoral effects from other sectors on fisheries, limiting further progress towards a complete ecosystem-based fisheries management (Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, 2012). When an area requires regulation solely for fishing, regulations fall under the Marine Resource Act instead of the Nature Diversity Act. The 2021 white paper on marine conservation clarifies that area-based management governed by legislation other than environmental legislation, which would apply to the

On request by national fisheries and environmental authorities, the Norwegian Institute for Marine Research has provided a first expert-based assessment of OECM criteria applied to Norwegian fisheries regulations (Figure 46). The assessment concludes that many of the existing area-based fishery regulations would meet the quantitative OECM criteria. Since 1999, efforts to conserve coral reefs have been put in place through prohibiting bottom-trawling in 18 designated coral reef areas. These have already been reported as MPAs to OSPAR. However, these areas are relatively small and solely safeguarded against bottom trawling. To improve their effectiveness, it is essential to extend protection to other human

Figure 48 Areas closed to bottom trawling (green) and overlap of depth lines. From Barentswatch, n.d.

activities, such as aquaculture and drilling. The assessment concludes that these measures can be classified as OECMs (Norwegian Institute of Marine Research, 2021).

Large bottom trawl-free zones have been implemented in the deep-sea areas and around Svalbard through the Marine Resource Act (Norwegian Directorate of Fisheries, n.d.). For an area to be classified as OECM, its management rules must be permanent and specifically address significant human pressures. The assessment by the Institute of Marine Research underlines that areas where bottom trawling is prohibited have a positive impact on the marine biodiversity. Due to minimal economic activity from other sectors, it is recommended to consider that these areas meet the OECM criteria (Hoel et al., 2023). Since the Marine Resource Act is a sectoral legislation which only regulates living marine

resources, recent developments in hydrocarbon extraction and deep-sea mining exploration in these same areas would necessitate a reconsideration of their conservation status in the future.

Another OECM criterion is that the regulation should effectively reduce human pressure compared to a no-regulation scenario. An important share of the areas closed to bottom-trawling are located in the deep sea (see Figure 48). The report asserts that existing and potential future fisheries gear is unlikely to be designed for depths below 2000 metres. Parts of the fisheries regulations cover areas above 2000m depth. This raises the question whether the regulations prohibiting bottom trawling in these deep areas provide additional protection beyond what would naturally exist. Due to the absence of assessment methods, the report does not draw definitive conclusions on how these areas could be reported (Hoel et al., 2023).

In 2024, the Norwegian Society for the Conservation of Nature commissioned a report offering an alternative evaluation of potential OECM status for Norway's area-based fisheries regulations. This study reassessed areas previously identified as meeting OECM criteria by the Institute of Marine Research's 2023

report but reached significantly different conclusions. The researchers employed the IUCN-WCPA site-level assessment tool, diverging from the ICES workshop recommendations tool used by the Marine Institute. While there was some consensus on the OECM status of lobster and coral reef sites, the alternative evaluation report determined that the extensive bottom-trawl exclusion zones did not fulfil OECM criteria (Dunshea, G., Olausen, K. & Eckbo, N.H., 2024).

Area-based conservation measures can also be established as part of other sectoral legislation. This includes the Aquaculture Act, the Legislation on ports and navigable waters, Petroleum legislation, Activities of the Norwegian Armed Forces, and the Cultural Heritage Act. These do only restrict specific types of activity which may limit the pressure on marine biodiversity (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021).

Marine restoration

Norway has committed to contribute to international targets for marine restoration. A governmental white paper on Norway's strategy to implement the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Agreement is expected in 2024 (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b). The legal framework for achieving these objectives is largely parallel to the pathways for marine conservation measures (Nature Diversity Act and Marine Resource Act). Conservation measures can contribute to the restoration of areas that have been degraded, damaged, or destroyed. Passive restoration measures such as "rewilding" refer to management interventions where stressors are removed so that the ecosystem can recover. Active restoration measures designate the active re-establishment or improvement of the status of species and habitats. Examples of passive restoration measures are lobster no-take zones or fisheries management measures that contribute to rebuilding fish stocks, enacted through the Marine Resource Act (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). MPAs designated under the Nature Diversity Act can potentially contribute to restoration targets by restricting human pressure and allow nature to restore itself. However, as pointed out in the section above, the limited protection status within marine protection areas currently limits their contribution as a nature-based solution for restoration (Taraldset Haugland, 2023). The Integrated Ocean Management Plans emphasise the importance to implement conservation measures with restoration of blue forest ecosystems (saltmarshes, kelp, seagrass), with positive effects on marine biodiversity and carbon sequestration (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b).

Implementation of the strategic direction

Integrated management

Within one nautical mile from the baseline, Norway has established a system for integrated coastal zone management, where local government authorities (municipalities) are the principal planning authorities. Beyond the baseline, the national government has established Integrated Ocean Management Plans that extend from the baseline out to cover the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). These plans provide national coordination for ocean management and inform the implementation of legal measures within sectoral or cross-sectoral legislation. The Norwegian Ocean Management Plans offer an overarching framework for ensuring sustainable ocean governance. The establishment of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) is not the primary objective of these plans. Instead, they report on and consider MPAs as part of a broader integrated ocean management approach, where MPAs are regarded as one of several tools within ecosystem-based management (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021).

The Norwegian Integrated Ocean Management Plans

Norwegian ocean management is built on an integrated and cross-sectoral approach for knowledge-based decision-making but is equally defined by a strong sectoral management. Norway has a longstanding tradition of integrated ocean management, with a cross-sectoral planning system developed over the past two decades to ensure ecosystem-based management of its oceans. Increased focus on hydrocarbon exploitation required integration of environmental consequences and

interactions with other maritime activities (mainly fisheries), and the groundwork for integrated ocean management was laid in the white paper “Protecting the Riches of the Sea” No. 12 (2001–2002) (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b).

Three cross-sectoral management and advisory bodies are at the core of the integrated approach (see Figure 48). The Ministry of Climate and Environment is heading the steering committee and responsible for the development of the plans, involving other ministries (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b). The system is built on knowledge-based decision making where scientific advisory bodies provide knowledge about the status and monitoring of the marine environment (figure 49). In contrast to international models like the IPCC, which aim to strictly separate the production of scientific

Figure 49 Organogram of Integrated Ocean Management in Norway. From Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b.

knowledge from governance actors, the Norwegian model has a closely intertwined science-policy interface. While such an approach favours the production of management-relevant knowledge, scientific evidence can more easily be steered by political ambitions. The system is adaptive, and the management plans are updated every four years (Andersen et al., 2019).

Figure 50 Ecosystem-based Ocean management in Norway. From Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b.

Contrary to the EU MSFD which mandates legally binding marine plans for member states, the Norwegian Integrated Ocean Management Plans are purely political. They can be considered an overarching cross-sectoral steering instrument intended to guide and clarify sectoral activities, but measures are implemented based

on existing sectoral legislation. The knowledge basis which informs the management plans provides the basis for an ecosystem-based approach, but decision-making remains a political competence. The plans have no legal anchorage in sectoral legislation, leaving important room for manoeuvre to sectoral authorities in how far the plans are implemented in practice (Andersen et al., 2019; Sander et al., 2022). The Norwegian Ocean Management system has been described as a “pragmatic sector-based coordination rather than fully integrated management” (Hoel, 2009). The designation of so-called ‘Particularly Valuable and Vulnerable Areas’ (SVOs) highlights the unclear relationship between the vague jurisdictional status of ocean management plans and sectoral interests. SVO areas are identified

by scientific advisory bodies, signifying their special importance for marine biodiversity and biological productivity. The renewed Integrated Ocean Management Plans from 2024 have significantly expanded SVO coverage. However, SVOs have no legal status and do not directly restrict human activities but rather serves as a signal for increased vigilance to sectoral authorities (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b).

Delivery of the strategic ambition

Amongst its dual objective to ensure sustainable use and environmental conservation, the Integrated Ocean Management Plans shall contribute to the creation of a well-managed network of ecologically coherent marine protected areas in Norwegian waters. These environmental objectives of the Integrated Ocean Management Plans are further elaborated through dedicated white papers on marine conservation. The white paper "Norway's integrated plan for the conservation of areas of special importance for marine biodiversity" (No. 29 (2020-2021)) is the most recent document in this regard. The white paper outlines a strategic direction for marine conservation, aiming to achieve a 30% conservation target. However, it lacks a renewed overview of prioritised areas for implementing this protection. Instead, it refers to candidate areas identified in the 2004 marine plan as the basis for designating new protected areas. Approximately half of the areas from the 2004 plan have already been protected, and adding the remaining areas would in total contribute to 10% protection in the territorial sea. The Norwegian Institute of Marine Research further underlines that the sites in the 2004 plan were identified on their uniqueness and representativeness, whereas vulnerability was only considered in few areas (Norwegian Institute of Marine Research, 2021). This indicates that despite the strategic goal of 30%, there is no national plan in place to ensure implementation. Which areas will be prioritised for the establishment of MPAs under the proposed framework for area-based protection beyond the territorial sea remains to be clarified. The SVO areas identified as part of the integrated ocean management system could provide an avenue for future protection, but the government has not provided further specification on this matter.

Conservation and spatial planning

Norway's Integrated Ocean Management Plans are sometimes mistakenly considered as maritime spatial plans (OECD, 2020). They highlight the need for cross-sectoral collaboration, but spatial allocation remains under the competence of the sectoral authority.

The offshore hydrocarbon sector is an exception in this regard, to which the Ocean Management Plans provide spatial regulation (Schütz & Johansen, 2023). The absence of a spatial tool in the oceans has prompted discussions about the need for a legal instrument to designate space for economic activities in Norway, including the establishment of marine protection areas. In the coastal zone (up to 1 nm from the baseline), municipalities establish legally binding spatial plans pursuant to the Planning and Building Act. While sectoral legislation contains requirements for safeguarding marine biodiversity, this is often in conflict with the sectoral authorities' interest to develop economic activity. Conservation measures through sectoral legislation can only restrict the pressure from the respective sector, underlining limitations to an ecosystem-based approach in practice. Marine conservation is underlined as a central component of integrated ecosystem-based management (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b). The current lack of a legal framework for cross-sectoral marine protection is a clear limitation in ensuring the environmental dimension of the management plans. The implementation of a legal act to establish MPAs in the EEZ, as currently being negotiated, would provide a better framework for cross-sectoral management, improving an ecosystem-based approach to marine conservation.

Due to increasing conflicts of interest between established and new economic activities as well as safeguarding environmental considerations, discussions have emerged whether Norway requires a legal tool for marine spatial planning. The Norwegian government has not been following the EU MSPD model but has announced the establishment of marine economic plans as a tool for integrated sustainable ocean management. These plans are not considered a direct spatial tool but define overarching principles for economic activity in the ocean (WWF, 2023).

Status and reporting of progress

The Norwegian Integrated Ocean Management Plan states that previous objectives in marine conservation have not been reached, calling for increased efforts in establishing a network of marine protected areas (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024b). In 2015, the Norwegian parliament decided that only areas protected through environmental legislation (Nature Diversity Act, Svalbard Protection Act, and Act on Jan Mayen) would be eligible for reporting towards the Aichi and other international conservation targets. In 2021, these area-based protection measures accounted for 4.2% of the Norwegian seascape. The coral reef areas, which are protected through the Marine Resource Act (fisheries legislation), add an additional 0.3% (these areas are being reported as MPAs to OSPAR, however not internationally to the CBD (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). Inconsistencies exist between the actual protection level and the reporting of Norwegian marine protection efforts. In 2021, Norway reported all its marine protection areas as IUCN category 1a, implying the strictest protection. Yet, the current legal framework for Norwegian MPAs allows fisheries activities, including bottom trawling in most MPAs. The Norwegian Institute of Marine Research argues that Norwegian reporting does not align with the standards of the IUCN, stating that Norwegian MPAs could at best be reported as IUCN category IV (Norwegian Institute of Marine Research, 2021).

The Norwegian Integrated Plan for Marine Conservation emphasises that compared to other countries, Norway has so far taken a restrictive approach to reporting international conservation targets. In light of increased ambition for conservation targets and a history of strict reporting practices, the white paper states that *"It is particularly natural to adjust the current reporting routines by considering how more OEEMs, for example in the fisheries sector, can be included in the figures when Norway reports to the CBD"* (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021). Including the large trawl-free zones enacted through fisheries regulations would potentially increase the Norwegian share of 'conservation' to well above 40%. None of these potential OEEMs have been reported internationally yet, but the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries noted in 2024 to the Parliament that 44% of the marine areas are covered by *"effective area-based measures from fisheries regulations"*, referring to the 2023 assessment report from the Institute for Marine Research (Norwegian Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries, 2024). While recognising existing regulatory efforts as valuable contributions to biodiversity conservation is important, this should not undermine the additional effort needed to implement more marine protected areas through cross-sectoral environmental legislation, considering cumulative pressures from other activities' conservation value compared to a no-regulation baseline scenario.

Accountability

The Nature Diversity Act builds on the principles of devolution and decentralisation of management (Fauchald & Gulbrandsen, 2012). The formal decision to establish a marine protected area emerges from the Ministry of Climate and Environment but involves lower tiers of governance as a central component of the protection process. The Environment Agency and county governors carry out the consultation process to prepare a draft for the site-specific regulation, then the Ministry of Climate and Environment reviews and forwards the proposal to the government for final adoption. The county governors have the primary administrative authority for managing MPAs on an ongoing basis, including assessing exemption applications. Municipal and regional authorities are consulted during the establishment process and may have some management responsibilities depending on the specific MPA. The white paper for marine conservation highlights the importance of broad local participation to ensure a good protection process for MPAs. To enhance the involvement during the protection process, county governors may establish local reference groups that represent the various interests (Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2021).

In addition to international reporting, Norway has established national reporting schemes that provide information on progress, which are accessible to the public. The national reporting portal 'Miljøstatus' provides information on quantitative progress to the conservation objectives. While qualitative expert-based assessments on the protection status and ecological representativeness are included for terrestrial areas, the reporting on marine areas is less detailed. (Norwegian Environment Agency, 2023).

Iceland

Icelandic marine environment and human pressures

The Icelandic ecoregion is situated at the boundary of the cold East Greenland current and a branch of the warmer Gulf Stream and is characterised by high productivity and biodiversity. Over the last decades, Atlantic water masses have increasingly dominated previously Arctic water masses, leading to changes in species' spatial distribution and food web patterns. Changes in water temperatures at deeper depths have impacted the mix of demersal and benthic species, favouring an increasing number of Atlantic species. In addition to the indirect effects of climate change, the dominant pressure in the Icelandic Ocean that can be regulated on a regional scale comes from fisheries activity. While some fish stocks have been critically impacted by fishing, abrasion of bottom habitat through bottom fishing gear is another pressure on the ecosystem. Overall, fishing efforts for most gear types have declined. Due to low population density, coastal habitat loss from infrastructure is not considered a major problem in the ecoregion, but cumulative effects can occur at local scales (ICES, 2021, 2022).

Governance context

Iceland is a member of the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) and associated with the EU through the European Economic Area (EEA) Agreement, partially implementing EU regulations and directives relating to environmental issues. In 2011, Iceland transposed the EU Water Framework Directive into national legislation, and the first River Basin Management Plan (RBMP) entered into force in 2022 (Environment Agency of Iceland, 2023). Due to deep fjords and islands, the RBMP covers large coastal areas. For half of the coastal water bodies, the ecological status has been defined as high, while the remaining coastal waterbodies have not been classified (Umhverfisstofnun, n.d.)' Iceland does not participate in the Natura 2000 network of protected areas under the Birds Directive (1979) and the Habitats Directive (1992) and has developed its own national framework for conservation.

A peculiarity of Icelandic spatial delineation in the coastal zone is the ancient net line boundary, located 115m seawards from the low tidal line. Municipal spatial planning is mainly terrestrial and only encompasses coastal waters within the narrow net law line. Nationally designated protection areas within this zone require collaboration between municipalities, environmental authorities, and relevant nature conservation committees to align the municipal plans with the conservation values and objectives of the protected sites. A recent development in Icelandic marine policy is the implementation of marine spatial planning (MSP) through the Act on Marine and Coastal Planning (No. 88/2018). Implementation currently takes place through pilots in two fjords. Increasing economic activity in the coastal zone (mainly aquaculture) is the main driver for MSP, which shall ensure that licencing is compatible with other use interests and maintains biological diversity at sea. The Icelandic MSP plans to extend from the net line until the baseline (Skipulagsstofnun, 2016). Unlike the EU MSP Directive, which covers the entire EEZ beyond the baseline, Iceland's MSP is strongly focused on the coastal zone and excludes commercial fisheries from its scope.

Strategic direction

Marine policy in Iceland is deeply rooted in the nation's maritime heritage. The 2004 Icelandic Ocean Strategy recognises the ocean as the source of survival and prosperity of the Icelandic nation, striving to maintain a balanced approach to marine development while safeguarding its unique and precious marine ecosystems for future generations (Icelandic Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries, 2004). Iceland's policy on Arctic Issues has been updated in 2021, including environmental protection among its main objectives (Icelandic Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2021). However, these national strategies contain no specific marine area-based management or restoration provision or objectives.

Emphasis on biodiversity entered into Icelandic law and policy in 2008 with the first National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan but has not been revised since (CBD, 2021b).

In 2022, a government-mandated working group published a Greenbook on biodiversity with the objective of updating existing biodiversity policies, better integrating biodiversity into legal frameworks, and ensuring alignment with international obligations (Cabinet of Iceland, 2022). The Greenbook included a status review of the actions set out by the 2010 Biodiversity Action Plan indicates that little progress has been made concerning the oceans, confirming that biodiversity has not received much attention in Icelandic Ocean management. The green paper calls for a more strategic approach to marine protection and notes that future policy development for designating MPAs is underway. Existing regulations in the oceans have mainly been designed to improve the sustainability of the fishing sector and include measures to protect juvenile fish and harvesting control enacted through fisheries regulations. The potential of OECMs, such as restrictions on fishing gear, to contribute to conservation objectives is highlighted in the green paper, but to date, Iceland has not reported or assessed the potential of OECMs (Cabinet of Iceland, 2022).

Iceland has an extensive policy for ecological restoration; however, these are directed towards the terrestrial environment. While the initial focus of restoration in Iceland was to halt soil erosion, the value of restoration for carbon sequestration has been increasingly emphasised in climate mitigation policies (Aradóttir et al., 2013). Wetland restoration is high on the political agenda through recreating natural hydrological conditions and promoting the growth of native wetland vegetation. Some of them are situated in the coastal zone, such as estuarine swamps or tidal marshes, two of them being Ramsar sites (Ramsar, n.d.). For the marine environment, however, no specific restoration policies exist to date; the green paper on biological diversity notes that "*The possibility of restoring ecosystems in the sea and in coastal areas needs to be considered*" (Cabinet of Iceland, 2022). The potential for restoring coastal ecosystems as a nature-based solution for climate mitigation and adaptation, while also creating business opportunities, has already been recognised by small-scale companies along the Icelandic coast. These include kelp restoration and seaweed cultivation projects (Nickayin et al., 2022).

Legal frameworks

Area-based measures have mainly focused on terrestrial areas, with only a few marine areas under legal protection. Two alternative pathways exist for designating areas: Most areas are designated according to the Nature Conservation Act, and some areas have obtained formal protection through site-specific legislation. Sectoral legislation, mainly fisheries, can also have positive effects on conservation.

Institutional responsibilities

The Icelandic governance system consists of two administrative levels: national and municipal. The Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate is the main authority for nature conservation and environmental issues and coordinates implementation with various specialised agencies and services. To ensure that nature conservation is respected in municipal decision-making, each municipality has established a Nature Conservation Committee coordinating closely with the Environment Agency. At the national level, a national Nature Conservation Committee serves as an advisory body to the ministry (Parliament of Iceland, 2013). Compared to other Nordic countries, it has been pointed out that the institutional framework for nature conservation is highly fragmented and involves a large number of institutions with restricted mandates and few employees (Umhverfissráðuneytið, 2011). Nevertheless, nature conservation in Iceland increased significantly over the second half of the 20th century, and nature-based tourism has now surpassed fisheries to become the largest economic sector in Iceland (Petursson & Kristofersson, 2021).

Environmental legislation for area-based management

In 2011, a white paper on the Protection of Icelandic Nature was created to provide a basis for the Ministry of the Environment to draft new legislation on nature protection. The report offered general

recommendations for improving nature conservation laws and suggested reforms. Some of these recommendations were subsequently incorporated into a bill to amend the existing Nature Conservation Act (Jonsson, 2012). The revised Nature Conservation Act No. 60/2013 is the main legal framework for area-based protection in Iceland, covering the land, territorial waters, and the exclusive economic zone (Parliament of Iceland, 2013). The Act enables to establish area-based measures within ten categories, aligned with the definitions provided by the IUCN to ensure comparability (Cabinet of Iceland, 2022). The core of nature conservation in Iceland is centred around the implementation of the Natural Conservation Register. Every five years, the Ministry for Environment, Energy, and Climate proposes an updated version of the Natural Conservation Register. They then submit it to the parliament, which decides how to put it into action through a parliamentary resolution. The register is subdivided into three parts: A) *List of currently protected areas* B) *Strategic plan of areas which the parliament prioritises for protection in a 5-year period* C) *List of sites that are proposed to be protected* (Icelandic Institute of Natural History, n.d.-b). The Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate is the leading institution for nature conservation and decides upon the designation of protected areas. In cases where the restrictions affect issues regulated by other ministries (e.g. fish stocks), consultation is required. The Environment Agency draws management plans in consultation with local and scientific institutions and is responsible for supervising the implementation (Parliament of Iceland, 2013).

Shortcomings in marine conservation have been pointed out several times, which called for the improvement of the marine dimension of the Nature Conservation Act (Umhverfisráðuneytið, 2011). A gradual integration of the marine component can be observed in the evolution of the Nature Conservation Act. The original Act from 1971 only covered the land and near zone (115m seawards from low water mark), the revised Act from 1999 extended the scope to the entire EEZ and introduced special provisions for protection at sea, which have been further specified in the Act from 2013 that is currently in force (Parliament of Iceland, 2013). A major shortcoming that has been pointed out with the current Nature Conservation Act is its narrow focus on biodiversity conservation within specific areas listed in the Natural Conservation Register, calling instead for a more integrated approach where biodiversity is mainstreamed into broader planning and legal frameworks (Cabinet of Iceland, 2022).

The Nature Conservation Act primarily follows a top-down approach for area designation that, while allowing for the constitution of consultation committees, does not enable a system for true co-management. An alternative pathway for protected area governance in Iceland is implemented through site-specific legislation, anchoring principles of a bottom-up approach to protection (Petursson & Kristofersson, 2021).

Sectoral legislation and OECM

Whereas terrestrial protection has received a strong focus in Iceland, protection at sea has mainly been understood in the context of fisheries management to maintain sustainable harvesting. Icelandic fisheries management is structured around three main elements: 1) catch regulations for exploitable stocks, 2) Fishing gear regulations, and, 3) Protection and closure of areas (ICES, 2021).

Figure 51 Long-term regulations on fisheries. From SDI Iceland, 2024.

Red: Closure. Orange: Closure of spawning grounds. Green: Lumpfish gillnet closure.

Among the MPAs reported to OSPAR, 10 are cold-water coral sites south of Iceland, protected through the Act on Fishing in Icelandic Territory Waters No. 79/1997. While these areas are closed to all fishing, it has been criticised that their small size and fishing activity outside their boundaries limit their effectiveness in providing high-level protection (Bünter, 2022). In 2023, the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries announced a new regulation on protective measures for sensitive oceans and benthic habitats (Reg no. 188/2023), prohibiting bottom trawling in 2% of the Icelandic EEZ. The Minister presented the regulation as an important contribution towards the international 30% protection target of the ocean, calling for increased effort in this area (McBride, 2023). This indicates that area-based measures enacted through fisheries regulations are increasingly shifting from preserving commercial single-species to more holistic conservation measures for entire ecosystems. To what extent these area-based measures will be reported to international targets (as MPA or OECM) remains to be clarified.

Implementation of the strategic direction

Delivery of strategic ambition

The current B-list of the Natural Conservation Register, setting out the strategic plan of areas which the parliament prioritises for protection in a 5-year period, comprises areas within the terrestrial, freshwater, coastal, and marine environment. For the assessment of the conservation value, conducted to determine whether an area should be included on the B-list, there are currently no criteria specifically addressing marine habitats (Icelandic Institute of Natural History, n.d.-a). This implies that the conservation value of marine ecosystems is currently not considered in the strategic planning of Icelandic nature conservation. In a hearing letter to the 2022 published Greenbook on biological diversity, the Environment Agency expressed that the possibility of drafting a national plan for protected areas at sea should be assessed, parallel to the implementation of the B-part of the Natural Conservation Register (Environment Agency of Iceland, 2022). This would provide an important step towards increased focus and representativity of marine protection efforts. These provisions have not been included in the Greenbook, and it remains to be seen whether the envisioned future update of the Icelandic biodiversity policy

addresses this issue. The Environment Agency states that the possibility of drafting a national plan for protected areas at sea should be assessed, parallel to the implementation of the B-part of the Natural Conservation Register (Environment Agency of Iceland, 2022). This would provide an important step towards increased focus and representativity of marine protection efforts.

Status and reporting of progress

To date, efforts in area-based protection in Iceland have largely focused on the terrestrial environment. With around 26,5% of its land area under formal protection, Iceland ranks amongst the highest protected countries in the OECD (Petursson et al., 2016). Compared to terrestrial areas, area-based protection of the marine environment remains very limited. The Icelandic national GIS database includes no dataset for marine protected areas, making it difficult to provide an overview of current MPA/OECM coverage (Landupplýsingagátt, n.d.). Recent national policy documents refer to the existence of 14 MPAs. These areas have been reported as MPAs to OSPAR, but information about the sites on the OSPAR portal is largely absent. On international databases such as PAME and the World Database on Protected Areas, up to 43 areas are declared as MPAs (UNEP-WCMC, 2024c).

Monitoring and knowledge

Both the ocean policy and marine spatial planning framework (on the coast) call for an ecosystem-based approach. However, monitoring data of the coastal and marine environment is currently limited and fragmented, creating a barrier to effective marine protection policies. Monitoring of fish stocks, marine physical parameters and nutrient levels is conducted by the Norwegian Institute for Marine Research and the Icelandic Institute of Natural Sciences, while there is no large-scale monitoring of benthic habitats or communities (Cabinet of Iceland, 2022). In the context of coastal and marine planning, the need for improved environmental monitoring and research to ensure that planning and licensing can be implemented through an ecosystem-based approach was equally emphasised (Hafskipulag, n.d.). The establishment of a consultation and cooperation forum for biodiversity research and knowledge transfer (called BIODICE) across Icelandic research institutions and NGOs has contributed to compiling information about biodiversity in Iceland, counteracting the fragmented responsibilities in data provisioning (Cabinet of Iceland, 2022).

Accountability

The largest terrestrial protection areas in Iceland have been implemented with site-specific legislation and not through the Nature Conservation Act. The distinct institutional framework builds on co-management with local actors where the management board of the area is regarded as an independent body directly under the auspices of the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate (instead of reporting via the Environment Agency). Additionally, a separate part of the state budget is allocated to the management of the area. These provisions have significantly leveraged how the management can respond to local circumstances and regulate licensing and activities in the area (Petursson et al., 2016; Petursson & Kristofersson, 2021). A comparative analysis of protected areas in Iceland indicates, however, that there are large differences in the governance systems, both with respect to the co-management models and institutional arrangements. Another issue identified is the lack of coordination across the committees of protection sites, as well as their unclear vertical integration within the national governance landscape (Siltanen et al., 2022). In combination, Icelandic nature conservation law and site-specific legislation provide a pathway to establish area-based protection at sea. To date, no exclusive marine protected areas has been implemented according to this legislation. In the case where terrestrial protected areas extend into the sea, these marine areas mostly benefit from limited protection; two examples are given in the text box (Bünter, 2022; Parliament of Iceland, 1995; UNESCO, n.d.). The largest terrestrial protection areas in Iceland have been implemented with site-specific legislation and not through the Nature Conservation Act. The distinct institutional framework builds on co-management with local actors where the management board of the area is regarded as an independent body directly under the auspices of the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate (instead of reporting via the Environment Agency). Additionally, a separate part of the state budget is

allocated to the management of the area. These provisions have significantly leveraged how the management can respond to local circumstances and regulate licensing and activities in the area (Petursson et al., 2016; Petursson & Kristofersson, 2021). A comparative analysis of protected areas in Iceland indicates, however, that there are large differences in the governance systems, both with respect to the co-management models and institutional arrangements. Another issue identified is the lack of coordination across the committees of protection sites, as well as their unclear vertical integration within the national governance landscape (Siltanen et al., 2022). In combination, Icelandic nature conservation law and site-specific legislation provide a pathway to establish area-based protection at sea. To date, no exclusive marine protected areas has been implemented according to this legislation. In the case where terrestrial protected areas extend into the sea, these marine areas mostly benefit from limited protection; two examples are given in the text box (Bünter, 2022; Parliament of Iceland, 1995; UNESCO, n.d.).

The **Breiðafjörður** Conservation Area in Iceland covers a significant coastal and marine expanse. The area was designated through site-specific legislation, which constitutes an alternative pathway to protection in Iceland. While some subareas within it receive additional protection under the Nature Conservation Act, the entire region is classified as IUCN Category V. The conservation objective is to safeguard the landscape, geological formations, ecosystems, and cultural heritage. However, the current management plans and laws only address terrestrial parts, islands, and inner fjord areas. The ocean body and seabed, however, lack legal protection. Despite being listed as an MPA in some international databases, the absence of specific marine protection provisions indicates a low protection status.

Surtsey, a volcanic island off Iceland's coast, consists of 98% marine areas and holds IUCN Category 1a (strict nature reserve) status. The terrestrial and coastal areas are strictly protected, but the surrounding marine buffer zone has lower protection (allowing fishing). UNESCO considers the buffer zone boundaries sufficiently protect the volcanic islands Surtsey, but this highlights caution when interpreting Iceland's MPA coverage due to the actual protection of marine components being limited.

Figure 52 Overview of MPAs listed in the World Database on Protected Areas of the Marine Conservation Institute. From UNEP-WCMC, 2024b.

Total of 43 protected areas, covering 0,4% of marine areas. These include several terrestrial nature reserves or conservation sites designated under the Nature Conservation Act or site-specific legislation which extend into the sea.

Figure 53 Marine protected areas reported to OSPAR. From OSPAR Commission, n.d.

These include two hot spring natural monuments; two nature reserves (designated through the Nature Conservation Act), and the remaining ten sites are coral reef protection sites designated through fisheries regulations.

Greenland

Greenlandic marine environment and pressures from human activity

Greenland's marine environment spans from cold and fresh polar waters and year-round sea ice cover to warmer and more saline waters in the south. While the east coast of Greenland is sparsely populated except for a few settlements, most of the 56,000 inhabitants are found on the central and southern parts of the west coast (Grønlands statistik, 2023). Greenland's marine environment spans from cold and fresh polar waters and year-round sea ice

Figure 54 Marine activities around Greenland. From Wienrich, 2022.

cover to warmer and more saline waters in the south. While the east coast of Greenland is sparsely populated except for a few settlements, most of the 56,000 inhabitants are found on the central and southern parts of the west coast (Grønlands statistik, 2023).

Human activity is comparably low due to the sparse population, but selective species extraction and physical seabed disturbance from the fisheries sector are stated to be the largest direct human risk to the marine environment in the East Greenland Shelf ecoregion. Climate change is an important pressure, where reduction of sea ice and glacier meltwater runoff alter the salinity level with implication for ocean stratification, circulation patterns and ocean temperature. Sea ice coverage is reduced both in temporal and areal scale and becomes increasingly thinner, impacting the distribution of species (ICES, 2020). The Inuit, the largest societal group of Greenland, are strongly dependent on interactions with the natural environment, and impacts of climate change are challenging their hunting and fishing practices (Wienrich, 2022). With regards to waste management and hazardous substances on land and off the coast, there is a large deficit in infrastructure. Most of the waste is deposited in open landfills, discharged as grey and black wastewater (CBD, 2019). There is an increasing focus on building waste-to-energy incinerators (Hermansen, 2021).

The Greenlandic economy is dominated by a few sectors, fisheries is by far the largest sector in terms of employment and added value and contributes to 90% of the Greenlandic export value (Grønlands statistik, 2023). Greenland is also considering the farming and exploitation of species such as seaweed and sea urchins in the future, but no aquaculture infrastructure exist in Greenland to date (Wienrich, 2022). Prospects of oil drilling in Greenland have garnered both attention and controversy due to environmental and economic implications over the last decade. In 2021, the Greenlandic government announced to suspend its plans for offshore hydrocarbon exploitation and extraction. The decision was made to protect the marine environment and the fishing industry from the potentially high risks of a blowout or oil spill, that would have devastating consequences on the marine environment. The official announcement made clear that the decision should also be seen in the light of Greenland's climate ambition not to support fossil fuel extraction in the future (Greenlandic Ministry of Mineral Resources and Justice, 2021). In 2023, Greenland signed the international agreement from COP21 in Paris (Paris

Agreement), setting the course for the development of a national climate policy in Greenland (UN Regional Information Centre for Western Europe, 2023).

Governance context

Greenland is an autonomous territory associated to the Kingdom of Denmark that was being granted home rule in 1979. Home Rule was replaced by the Self-Government Act in 2009, transferring legal and administrative competence on many policy areas from Danish to Greenlandic authorities. The Greenlandic government and parliament deal independently with internal affairs, however questions related to foreign policy and defence remain under Danish control (Ackrén, 2019). This intricate arrangement extends to the governance of the marine environment surrounding Greenland. The Greenlandic territorial sea extends to 3 nm from the baseline, and the Greenlandic self-government is responsible for ensuring marine protection in the territorial sea. The responsibility in the EEZ outside Greenland's territorial waters is with Danish authorities (from 3-200m). The governance of the Greenlandic marine environment is therefore under shared competence that requires coordination between Greenlandic and Danish authorities, due to restricted spatial and sectoral competencies (Statsrevisoren, 2012). The allocation of competencies between Greenlandic and Danish authorities is regulated, but the interpretation of the legal document has not come without conflicts. With more than 90% of its population being indigenous peoples, movements amongst Greenlanders for increased independence from Denmark are rooted in a combination of historical, socio-cultural, political, and economic factors. The Greenlandic economy is strongly dependent on the annual block grants from Denmark and Greenland's yearnings for political independence are therefore strongly related to economic independence. A legal mechanism of the annual block grant foresees that earnings from natural resource exploitation would reduce the amount of the block grant once they exceed a certain threshold. Natural resource economy, strive for political independence and foreign affairs relations are therefore deeply intertwined and have influenced the relationship between Greenland and Denmark, as well as interests from foreign nations and investors (Christiansen, 2023).

Mainly influenced by the debate to regain control over fisheries policy, Greenlanders decided in a 1985 referendum to leave the European Economic Community (now EU) and have since the status of Associate Overseas Territory. In addition to large annual block grants from Denmark, Greenland receives funds from the EU. Those are largely allocated to social policies, only a small share is ear-marked for 'green growth'. The EU and Greenland have also signed fisheries agreement that gives EU fleets access to Greenlandic fishing grounds, and Greenland benefits from the economic turnovers (Directorate-General for Communication, 2023). This complex relationship between Greenlandic, Danish and EU authorities that all have an influence on the governance of the marine environment underscores the intricate balance between addressing the challenges posed by climate change and sustainable resource utilization in the Arctic marine environment.

Strategic direction

The Kingdom of Denmark is signatory to the CBD and as self-governing area, Greenland has administrative and legislative competency on several sectors, including biodiversity and living resources. The Greenlandic Ministry of Environment and Nature submits its own national report to the CBD as part of Denmark's reporting obligations. The early phases of Greenlandic conservation management were focused on specie-specific regulations (such as birds, narwhal and beluga, walrus, and polar bears), implemented through executive orders (Ministry of Environment and Nature, Government of Greenland, 2014).

In 2022, Greenland published its first national biodiversity strategy which is a key instrument for translating the Convention into national action. The Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 sets the objective to establish a network of sustainably managed important terrestrial, coastal and marine ecosystems. The strategy contains no quantitative targets but stipulates that management should be aligned with requirements in Greenlandic legislation and international agreements. It is further declared that ecosystem-based

management should be implemented and that biodiversity concerns shall be mainstreamed into sectoral legislation and municipal planning. Biodiversity and living resources are considered a main pillar for increased value creation (fisheries, hunting, tourism) that should be based upon the principles of ecosystem-based management (Government of Greenland, 2021).

In 2024, Greenland published a foreign, security and defence strategy entitled 'Greenland in the World. Nothing about us without us'. The foreword notes that this strategy can be considered an Arctic Strategy and is the first time Greenland spells out its Arctic ambitions independently from Denmark, calling for increased Greenlandic presence at the international stage. The strategy includes important strategic dimensions with regards to biodiversity and climate governance, emphasising its commitment to international biodiversity conservation targets (Ministry for Statehood and Foreign Affairs/ Government of Greenland, 2024).

Legal framework

Institutional responsibilities

Denmark and Greenland hold shared responsibilities in area-based management and nature conservation: Greenland is responsible for management on land and until 3 nm from the coast, whereas Danish authorities govern the marine areas beyond the 3nm covering the EEZ. In addition, Greenland's governance is sector driven and some of the sectoral governance systems under Greenlandic authority extend to the entire EEZ. With the Self-Governance Act of 2009, Greenlandic authorities have taken over legal and administrative competence in the field of mineral resources (formalised through the Natural Resource Act) that covers the whole EEZ (Statsrevisorerne, 2012). An implication of this intricate arrangement is that governance of the marine areas in Greenland requires shared cooperation between Danish and Greenlandic authorities, both due to sectoral and spatial exclusive competencies and overlaps.

Area-based measures in the territorial sea

The Ministry for Self-supply, Energy and Environment is the main authority for governing nature conservation in Greenland. The Nature Conservation Act (no. 29/2003) is a framework law that provides the legal basis for nature management and the development of executive orders for species, ecosystem, and area-based protection. It applies to wildlife consisting of mammals, birds, and other animals as well as to wild plants, including aquatic plants. Fish or clams, shrimps or other invertebrates that live in salt and fresh water are not included in the Act, since these are governed under the sectoral legislation under the responsibility of the Ministry for Fisheries and Hunting. Currently, twelve sites in Greenland have been designated as protected sites through executive orders under this legislation. The Ilulissat Icefjord protection site is further declared as a UNESCO World Heritage site and the National Park in Northeast Greenland has received the status of an UNESCO Biosphere Reserve. Greenland has also designated twelve sites as Ramsar protection sites, whereof three are simultaneously protected under the Nature Conservation Act. The Greenlandic Ramsar sites were designated due to international importance for wading bird species. Through an executive order adopted in 2016 (no.12/2016), the Greenlandic Government increased the protection level for nature and wildlife in the Ramsar sites through specific regulations for hunting and fishing. To date, six protection sites include areas in the marine environment, as listed below:

Table 11 Greenlandic protected sites with marine components. Adapted from Wienrich, 2022.

Site name	Designation type according to Greenlandic legislation	Marine area in km ²
Melville Bay at Qimusserarsuaq	Nature reserve	8412
Ilulissat Icefjord	UNESCO World heritage site	399
Kitsussunnguit - Green Ejland	Ramsar site	61
Ikka Fjord (Ivituut and Kangilinnguit)	Nature reserve	106
National Park in North- and east Greenland	UNESCO Biosphere reserve	87911
Unnarfoq	Nature reserve	0,1

The Nature Conservation Act does not regulate the exploration and exploitation of minerals and petroleum, which are regulated through sector-specific legislation. The Greenlandic classification system of the sites under the Nature Conservation Act does therefore not correspond to the IUCN categories. For instance, resource exploration and exploitation in Greenlandic 'national parks' is not prohibited as it is the case for the IUCN category 'national park'. Thus, all of the Greenlandic protection sites can only be classified as IUCN category V or VI (National Center for Miljø og Energi, 2016). It has however been argued that natural resource activities regulated under the Mineral Resource Act are subject to strict environmental rules, covering environment, nature and climate protection. In addition to Environmental Impact Assessments, Social Impact Assessments are required for larger licences, and the Act also includes provisions for environmental liability (Hojem, 2015). In 2013, an own agency has been created under the Ministry of Environment and Nature to separate the environmental regulation and permitting for extraction activities from the Ministry of Mineral Resources which grants the licences. The guidelines for strategic impact assessments and environmental impact assessments are inspired by guidance from the Arctic Council and OSPAR. In addition, environmental provisions under the Mineral Resource Act and related executive orders might protect sensitive species in areas outside of the Nature Conservation Act's site-specific legislation (CBD, 2019). According to IUCN categorization, none of Greenland's protection sites are 'strictly protected', however this statement can be differentiated when looking into the actual protection status. In the case of the large National Park of Northeast Greenland, only traditional harvesting by local communities is allowed, whereas the fauna is under complete protection from outside visitors that need permission for access (Tommasini, 2016).

Marine environmental protection

The existing protection sites with marine components are located within the 3 nautical miles from the baseline, where Greenlandic authorities hold the legal and administrative authority for protecting the marine environment and can designate protection areas through the Nature Conservation Act. Outside these areas, Danish authorities are governing the marine environment in the through the Law on the Protection of the Greenlandic Exclusive Economic Zone (no. 1543/2017). Sectoral instruments such as the Mineral Resource Act that are under Greenlandic authority, also apply in the waters of the EEZ governed by Danish authorities. The Danish Ministry for Environment holds legal competence in the governance of the marine areas, while monitoring and enforcement are under the responsibility of the Danish military. The Marine Environment Act for the Greenlandic EEZ governs pollution from ships and human activities (sewage, dumping, air pollution, oil), and has been updated in 2017 to include newest standards according to the Polar Code and international regulations. It is currently being reviewed to include the ban on heavy fuel oil in the Arctic that has been agreed on by the IMO in 2021 (The Government of Greenland, 2023). The Act contains no legal mechanisms for spatial protection of the marine environment, implying a lack in the legal framework for area-based protection in the entire Greenlandic marine environment.

The recently published Greenlandic Arctic Strategy states that Greenland will consider extending its jurisdiction of the territorial waters from 3 nm to 12 nm, which is the regular LOSC delineation (Ministry for Statehood and Foreign Affairs/ Government of Greenland, 2024). This would significantly change the governance of marine areas, providing an opportunity to increase environmental regulations under Greenlandic authority.

Indigenous people and nature conservation

In addition to conservation measures that are implemented through national legislation, traditional management practices of the indigenous population in Greenland contribute to achieving conservation outcomes and are considered an important element of ecosystem-based management. Livelihoods of indigenous peoples are built on an intrinsic relationship with nature, however their contribution to sustainable management of resources are not considered in the same way as legal conservation measures by the government (Indigenous Circle of Experts, 2018). Harvesting of marine mammals is a traditional subsistence practice that contributes to the Indigenous Peoples cultural identity and should be accounted for in the drafting of legal conservation regulations (Wienrich, 2022). The Pikialasorsuaq Polynya, an upwelling area of open water in sea ice with extreme high biological productivity, is located between Nunavut (Canada) and the north-west coast of Greenland. The area provides an interesting case for co-management with the Inuit communities as well as trans-boundary governance. Initiated by the Inuit Circumpolar Council (ICC), negotiations are currently ongoing to establish a protection zone that is managed under an Inuit-led management regime to safeguard and monitor the health of this important ecosystem that supports livelihood to the Indigenous Peoples. Planning will involve the utilisation of evidenced based Indigenous and western knowledge (Pikialasorsuaq Commission, 2019; Wienrich et al., 2022).

The importance of indigenously managed areas for conservation and their contribution to conservation targets is still being clarified internationally. The PAME (Protection of Arctic Marine Environment) working group of the Arctic Council has initiated a project to assess the contribution of indigenous knowledge for conservation planning and inclusion in marine resource management in the Arctic (PAME, n.d.).

Sectoral legislation and the role of OECM

The fisheries management system in Greenland is organised under the Fishery Act of 1996 under the auspices of the Ministry for Fisheries and Hunting. Total allowable catch quotas (TAC) are at the core of the fisheries management system. Larger offshore fishing fleets (with some exception for shrimp and cod vessels) are prohibited within the coastal zone of 3 nm, which is dominated by small-scale coastal fleets. Similar to the Marine Resource Act, the Fishery Act (no.18 of 1996) is a sector-based legislation that covers the entire EEZ. Some of the fisheries management tools can be regarded as other effective conservation measures (OECM) and include measures to protect benthic habitats such as cold-water corals from bottom trawling or protection of spawning grounds for certain species (CBD, 2019). One example of such measures can be found on the east coast of Greenland, where a redfish protection area has been established that bans bottom trawling. Another example is the requirement to use sorting grids for shrimp fisheries, that is considered an efficient conservation measure for juvenile redfish and halibut (OECD, 2003).

Greenland has also established seabird breeding sanctuaries (executive order no.1 of January 5th, 2017), ensuring protection during the breeding season. The Greenlandic CBD reporting notes that these areas can be considered OECMs (CBD, 2019). This is however not in line with the IUCN definition of an OECM, excluding temporary measures (IUCN-WCPA Task Force on OECMs, 2019).

Implementation

Status and reporting of progress

In 2019, Greenland reported to the CBD that 41% of terrestrial areas (through the Nature Conservation Act and Ramsar) were protected, in addition to 4.2% of the marine environment. Currently, there are no marine protection areas that are designated exclusively in the marine environment. All existing marine protections are actually extensions of land-based conservation sites that stretch into the sea. These protected areas are limited to the coastal zone, which extends 3 nautical miles from the baseline (which is the jurisdiction of the Greenlandic Nature Conservation Act) (CBD, 2019).

In the 2010 CBD reporting, Greenland reported that ecosystem-based management (EBM) is not fully applied in Greenland. Management of wildlife is largely focused on harvest control of individual species (Government of Greenland, 2010). One element that contributes towards EBM is the horizontal integration across sectors. Greenlandic governance has previously been sectoralised, establishing zoning and economic plans for each sector (NunaGIS, 2023). Greenland has stated to focus on cross-sectoral collaboration and assess the potential to progress towards more sector-integrated management plans in line with ecosystem-based management. The digital platform 'NunaGIS' has been developed, compiling datasets for spatial planning, but also including data layers about nature and biodiversity. The platform is still under development and the datasets are not yet available online (NunaGIS, n.d.).

In the most recent national reporting to the CBD, nature and ecosystem restoration is not regarded as relevant for the Greenlandic context. The reporting notes that habitats and ecosystems are only affected by a very small degree by human activity, however it is noted that climate change is increasingly threatening the state of the ecosystems (CBD, 2019).

Monitoring

In addition to protected sites designated under the Nature Conservation Act, Greenland has undertaken efforts to monitor the distribution and migratory pathways of vulnerable species. Important areas have been identified according to international criteria such as EBSA and particular sensitive sea areas (PSSA) under the International Maritime Organization (IMO). In total, 39 areas have been identified as highly important for Greenlandic biodiversity, but they have currently no direct implication for conservation management (Nationalt Center for Miljø og Energi, 2016).

Faroe Islands

Faroe Islands' marine environment and human pressures

The archipelago of 18 islands is located on a large shelf ecosystem, where most of the biological activity is found. A strong tidal boundary links the continental shelf to the open ocean. In this region, warm water from the Northeast Atlantic current meets cold water from the Arctic, resulting in strong ocean circulation patterns that create a dynamic and biologically productive ecosystem. Alterations in atmospheric and oceanic circulation due to climate change might lead to changes in the composition and biological productivity of the ecosystems (Faroese Ministry of Fisheries and Natural Resources, n.d.). Increasing water temperatures have led to the northward migration of species, with different impacts across targeted fishing species. Changes in trophic food webs have also altered the abundance of some important seabird species that are on decline (Nordic Council of Ministers, 2018).

The Faroese society has been historically very reliant on living marine resources, and the fisheries sector still contributes to around 20% of GDP and almost 95% of the export value. While the legal framework for fisheries is increasingly integrating sustainability principles, the effects of fisheries on the marine ecosystems remains a major threat (Danielsen & Agnarsson, 2018). Aquaculture has grown to a large industry and half of the export value is from farmed seafood products (Faroese Seafood, n.d.). Sand extraction from the bottom of fjords is extensively practiced in the Faroe Islands, and no specific legislation is in place. The extraction can cause changes to the topography of the fjords, but also cause habitat loss of species (such as sand eels), leading to changes on the ecosystem composition through trophic cascades (Nordic Council of Ministers, 2018).

Governance context

The Faroe Islands have gained governmental authority from Denmark through the Home Rule Act of 1948 (Prime Minister Office of Denmark, n.d.). The legal implications and differences between the Greenlandic and Faroese form of extended self-governance are highly complex, but they mainly differ with regards to which policy areas and spatial systems are transferred from Danish authorities to the self-governance system. In terms of marine governance, there is a striking difference: While Greenland only governs the coastal zone up to 3 nm from the baseline and the EEZ remains under Danish authority; the governance of the entire marine areas (EEZ) has been transferred to the Faroe Islands in 2003. This includes environmental governance, responsibility for maritime safety and full competence in the management of living marine resources and subsoil resources (Statsrevisorerne, 2012). The Faroe Islands have a third-country arrangement with the EU, distinct to Greenland's status as an Overseas Country and Territory (OCT). EU treaties and laws do not apply to the Faroe Islands, but cooperation has been formalised through three consecutive bilateral treaties (European Commission, n.d.-a). Increased cooperation is of mutual interest, and critical for the EU's engagement in the Arctic, where the Faroese Islands wish to be a strategic partner (Faroese Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Education, Research and Culture, 2020). In 2024, the Faroe Islands and the EU have signed a Memorandum of Understanding to foster further cooperation, including marine biodiversity protection and conservation among the key areas (The Government of the Faroe Islands, 2024).

The political, socio-economic, and environmental challenges the Faroe Islands are facing, are similar to its neighbouring countries. The Faroe Islands identify themselves as an Arctic nation, a view that has been fostered by a strategic assessment of the Faroese Government in 2013, underlining challenges, and opportunities for regional cooperation in the Arctic. Circumpolar affairs have high importance to the Faroe Islands and the Arctic Council is considered the most important forum for pan-arctic cooperation (Prime Minister's office of the Faroe Islands, 2013).

Strategic direction

As part of the Nordic cooperation platform, the Faroe Islands committed to the renewed global targets of the CBD, including the protection of 30% of ocean and land areas, as well as ensuring increased restoration of ecosystems (Nordic Council of Ministers of the Environment and Climate, 2022). The renewal of the Faroese nature conservation legislation which entered into force in 2024 is an important step towards enabling area-based protection measures, while its strategic implementation in Faroese policy remains to be clarified.

In the context of Faroese marine policy, the strategic dimensions have mainly revolved around other issues which are not related to area-based protection. A 2013 paper from the Faroese Prime Ministers' office stipulates that the greatest threat to the marine environment stems from the risk of oil and chemical spills of industrial vessels and this concern is reiterated in the recently published Arctic Strategy (Prime Minister's office of the Faroe Islands, 2013). Loss of sea ice in the Arctic is considered to bring new opportunities for the development of maritime industries, and the Faroese see themselves strategically well positioned to become an important maritime hub. The aquaculture sector, especially farming of Atlantic Salmon, has grown extensively. The potential of blue mussels and seaweed harvest is currently practiced at smaller scale, but the Arctic Strategy mentions this as an unharnessed potential to be developed in the future (Prime Minister's office of the Faroe Islands, 2013). In 2022, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Culture published an updated strategic document, entitled "The Faroe Islands in the Arctic" (Faroese Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Culture, 2022). Compared to the previous strategic document, the environmental and climate dimension is strengthened. With regards to conservation, it is stated that "*Especially sensitive areas or animal and plant species must be suitably protected, as needed*". There are however no specified targets or references to the marine biodiversity.

Considering restoration, a first large-scale restoration project on an island (Lendibati project) has been implemented, however the focus is rather terrestrial and aims to prevent erosion and biodiversity protection through the ecological restoration of drained wetlands and pasture grazing control (Barkved et al., 2024; Network Nature Nordic Hub, 2023).

Legal Framework

Environmental legislation in the Faroese Islands is under shared responsibility between the Ministry of Environment and municipal authorities (Faroese Ministry of Environment, n.d.-b). As of to date, no marine protected areas have been formally established through environmental legislation in the Faroe Islands. However, with the recent introduction of an updated Nature Conservation Act in 2024, the legal framework has undergone significant improvements. This revised legislation now provides a pathway for the future establishment of area-based protection in parts of the marine environment.

Environmental legislation for area-based management

The Nature Conservation Act (nr.48/1970) (Løgtingslóg um náttúrufríðing) has been the main legal instrument for nature conservation in the Faroe Islands over the past decades (Faroese Ministry of Environment, 1970). The Act stipulated a general duty of care in the environment and regulated construction of infrastructure outside designated areas but contained no provisions for the establishment of area-based protection measures. There have been several attempts to review the legal framework for nature conservation and ensure better alignment with international policy objectives for nature conservation. In 2023, the Act was amended by a new parliamentary Act on Nature Conservation (nr.70/2023) (Løgtingslóg um náttúruvernd) which entered into force in January 2024 (Faroese Ministry of Environment, 2023). The new legal framework aims to enhance biodiversity in accordance with the Convention on Biodiversity within Faroese legislation. While replacing certain provisions of the Nature Conservation Act from 1970, the new law significantly extends its scope. Local conservation committees, previously responsible for implementing the Act and managing permits, will be dissolved, and the authority to grant permits will shift to the Ministry of Environment. This centralization of decision-making is

intended to ensure that conservation measures are guided by professional expertise (VP Netavisin, 2022). A novelty in the Faroese legislation is that the new Nature Conservation Act establishes a legal framework for the designation of protected areas through decree by the Ministry of Environment. These areas can fall into five distinct protection categories, depending on the conservation objective: 1) Natural Parks 2) Landscape Conservation Areas 3) Nature Reserves 4) Species Protection Areas 5) Marine Protection Areas. Before an area is officially protected, the Ministry must announce the objectives and intended regulations for the defined area, allowing affected parties to provide feedback. The final decree for each protected area includes a management plan on how to achieve the conservation objectives. While activities within the area that affect the conservation objective can be restricted, these restrictions shall remain proportionate. For marine protected areas, fishing can still take place, as long as it does not conflict with the conservation objective. Importantly, the Nature Conservation Act only covers land and the territorial sea (12 nm from the baseline) (Faroese Ministry of Environment, 2023). These provisions are similar to the Norwegian Nature Diversity Act, which has been chosen as a model for drafting the Faroese legal framework (Faroese Ministry of Health, 2019).

Until 2003, the marine environment was managed by Danish authorities. In 2005, the Faroese government enacted the Marine Environment Act (nr.59/2005) (Havumhvørvislógin) (amended in 2020), which is designed to protect the marine environment and ensure that human activities are managed sustainably. Similar to the Greenlandic Marine Environment Act (which is under Danish authority), the Faroese Marine Environment Act main focus is on prevention and response measures addressing pollution, such as dumping, sewage, ballast water and oil spills. It applies to vessels, aircrafts, and infrastructure platforms in the marine environment. The Faroese Ministry for Environment oversees the implementation, whereas some parts related to oil and chemical spills in the coastal zone and harbours are partially delegated to municipal authorities (Faroese Ministry of Environment, n.d.-a).

The Nature Diversity Act has a restricted geographical scope, applying only to territorial waters, and the Marine Environment Act primarily focuses on pollution-related matters. As a result, there is currently no legal framework specifically designed for establishing area-based protection measures beyond the territorial sea.

Sectoral legislation and the role of OECMs

The Faroe Islands are not subject to the EU Common Fisheries Policy and manage their fisheries nationally, in accordance with the RFMO and ICES. The Faroe Islands' fisheries management system has faced recurrent criticism for its lack of sustainability and inability to prevent overfishing but underwent significant changes in 2018 with the introduction of the Marine Resource Act. Tradable quotas and fishing day limits were introduced, along with spatial regulations for vessel size, gear, and mesh. Temporal closures protect spawning grounds and benthic habitats, including cold-water corals. Three coral areas are now permanently protected from trawling, and ongoing mapping identifies other benthic zones that require protection. Trawling is restricted within territorial waters (12nm), except during a brief summer period, and large shallow areas in the EEZ are also closed to trawling for most of the year (The Government of the Faroe Islands, 2018). To what extent these regulations could be reported in the context of international conservation targets (as OECMs) remains to be clarified.

Implementation

Status

As a signatory to the CBD, the Faroese Islands have made several steps to implement and follow up on the Convention. So far, the Faroe Islands have only delivered one national report to the CBD in 2005, together with Denmark and Greenland. The national report and subsequent documentations from the National Museum of the Faroe Islands indicate that actions directed towards biodiversity conservation have mainly been of terrestrial focus and target invasive species, protection from grazing, impacts from agriculture and hydropower on freshwater streams and wetland drainage (Fosaa & Landsins, 2014).

The Faroe Islands are not a signatory party to the OSPAR Convention and have thus not nominated any areas. As of 2024, none of the area-based fisheries regulations were reported to international databases, nor assessed for their eligibility as OECM. The Act on Nature Conservation entered into force in 2024 but has not yet resulted in the designation of protected sites in the marine environment.

While some international databases list three marine protected sites for the Faroe Islands, these refer to Ramsar protection sites. In 2012, the Faroe Islands designated three islands as wetlands of international importance under the Ramsar Convention due to their unique seabird breeding habitats (Ramsar, 2012). However, the Faroese National Ramsar report from 2021 indicates that the protection status in these Ramsar sites falls short. Despite the establishment of a cross-sectoral management committee, there is no mechanism in place to inform authorities about human-induced changes in these sites. The report highlights the deteriorating status of wetlands both within and outside of Ramsar-designated areas (Faroese Environment Agency, 2021).

Figure 55 Ramsar protected sites in the Faroe Islands. From UNEP-WCMC, 2024.

8. Reflections

The following are reflection points, based on the report's key observations. These reflections have been grouped by the governance parameters identified in this study.

The key observations and recommendations provided in this report, combined with the findings of T1.3, represent a starting point for developing T1.4 discussion points, roadmaps, and work plans to develop effective governance frameworks as part of the implementation phase of BlueMissionAA.

T1.4 will seek to advance Atlantic and Arctic governance in a manner that recognises and respects the differences between States and across the spatial scales of governance. It will simultaneously provide a scalable and transferable approach that can be advanced in the broader European area.

Strategic Direction

- **R1:** How could shifting strategic thinking towards focusing on impacts improve the effectiveness of marine protection and achieve desired outcomes?
- **R2:** How could adopting an ecosystem-based approach to strategic thinking better integrate biological and socio-economic impacts into decision-making?
- **R3:** How can marine protection (MPAs / restoration projects) be effectively incorporated into and aligned with existing strategic directions and policy frameworks?
- **R4:** How can barriers to genuine stakeholder participation in decision-making processes for marine protection be addressed to enhance stakeholder roles?

Legal framework

- **R5:** Should and, if so how, could increasing the focus on granting nature a legal entity status be advanced at both national and regional levels?
- **R6:** Can devolution and co-governance support the success of the Mission Objectives? If so, what is the best approach to ensure balanced and effective vertical and horizontal integration?
- **R7:** How could reforming or restructuring legal frameworks and institutions increase flexibility and adaptability to support strategic direction implementation, address gaps in scope, and improve policy and legal coherence across the Atlantic and Arctic?
- **R8:** What is the best way to establish enduring sustainable funding models to support ocean protection?
- **R9:** How can governance structures be reviewed and adjusted to promote and ensure intergenerational justice (cf. R4)?
- **R10:** How can reporting obligations be strengthened and aligned?

Implementation

- **R11:** How can science-policy-society interfaces be improved in a manner that reflects the management needs for an integrated approach, e.g., an ecosystem-based approach, to MPAs/restoration sites?
- **R12:** How can an effective common monitoring and reporting framework and information structure be created, and at what level/under which institutional responsibility should these frameworks be integrated?
- **R13:** How can monitoring and reporting frameworks enables evidence-supported decision-making and shift towards the demonstration of management effectiveness and performance against specified strategic objectives?
- **R14:** What practical measures can be taken to further improve meaningful stakeholder involvement and ensure that participation goes beyond consultation so that it can influence final decisions?
- **R15:** What management and scientific processes are needed to provide the required information to support dynamic decision making and support effective MPAs / restoration sites?

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